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UNIVERSITY OF THE WEST OF SCOTLAND

THE IMPACT OF ISLAMIC BANKING ON
GENERATION Z

(A STUDY OF AL RAYAN BANK IN THE UNITED KINGDOM)

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Declaration

I, Ahmad Zulfakar, confirm that the research presented in this thesis, “The Impact of Islamic Banking on Generation Z: A Study of Al Rayan Bank in the United Kingdom”, is my own and where information has been derived from other sources, I confirm that I have indicated these in this research work.

Signed:

Date:

Ahmad Zulfakar (B00307588)

Dedication

In honour of my father, Muhammad Hadin Muhjad, who always supports and wants me to be the best, my mother, Maimunah, my brother, Ahmad Fikri Hadin, my sisters, Ika Putri Mauizah and Dwi Putri Rahmi, my lovely wife, Fitri Lisna Wati and my children, Muhammad Rayes Maqil and Mahreen Aleefa Syafiqah for all their care and love.

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Abstract

The issue of Islamic banking has received considerable critical attention in the business industry in recent years. There has been significant development in Islamic banking, especially in Western countries. In fact, the UK is the leading Western nation for implementing the Islamic finance system, and over 20 banks have already offered Islamic finance services, with five banks offering full Sharia (Islamic law). Focusing on the young generation (Generation Z) customer is one of the best strategies for long-term relationships, and they are also enormous in the current market to consider. This group defines self-identity as compassionate, loyal, open-minded, loyal, determined and responsible, and they might stay loyal to the brand and stick with the company throughout daily life. Moreover, Generation Z indicated that over half, 53 per cent of participants, would choose Islamic banking for their service in the banking sector. In addition, generation Z prefers traditional banking as a financial institution. In fact, 87 per cent of customers in this generation use the traditional way compared to a challenger bank system as their services.

Branding is one of the vital issues that has been considered a top management priority in the business sector, and it is the most valuable intangible asset for the company. Branding has been identified as the primary benefit for the company and its customers. Moreover, experiential marketing considers both the rational and irrational assumptions of consumer behaviour. Customers cannot shape their preferences among brands using rational attributes only. They seek a brand that creates experience. The self-concepts are related to the total set of an individual's thoughts and feelings concerning himself as an object, and it refers to the brand experience aspect that has demonstrated their determining role in the customers' choices.

Furthermore, financial service providers have long placed considerable faith in positive word-of-mouth communications to spread the significance of personal recommendations. WoM is an influential marketing tool for young customers in determining their bank selection decisions. Additionally, WoM communication is recognised as playing a significant role in influencing customer attitudes and behavioural intentions towards the products or services of the brand.

Accordingly, the main aim of the research is to analyse and examine factors that influence customers' perception of Islamic banking service, corporate social responsibility and service quality on satisfaction, brand experience and WoM, which is influenced by customer satisfaction from Generation Z Al Rayan Bank in the UK perspective. In this model, brand experience and WoM are dependent variables, and these variables are defined by attribute-based customer perception of Islamic banking, CSR and service quality. Therefore, the relative importance of the customer satisfaction factor also contributed to dependent variables as well as mediating variables between independent and dependent variables.

To achieve the aim study, quantitative research was implemented to this research. The quantitative strategy purposes to measure features, count them and use a statistical approach in an attempt to answer what has been conducted in research. It also generates a commonly implemented result of a study by using numbers rather than words to answer the questions of objectives. This study adopted Structural Equation Modelling (SEM) for data analysis through the PLS to analyse the influence between variables. Data sets were collected from the Generation Z customers of Al Rayan Bank in the UK. One hundred customers were selected as the sample population for this research.

The results indicate that Al Rayan Bank customers from Generation Z have yet to impact all the variables significantly. The findings illustrate that service quality is an essential determinant of customer satisfaction, followed by CSR on brand experience, Customer perception on brand experience, and customer satisfaction on WoM. The findings also indicate that there is no direct relationship among the rest of the variables. However, customer satisfaction mediates the relationship between service quality and WoM. Customer perception and CSR are two important antecedents of brand experience, with the strongest being CSR.

The finding contributes to the service marketing theory by providing additional insights into consumer behaviour, CSR, service quality, customer satisfaction, brand experience and WoM. Also, the findings will provide the United Kingdom bankers with empirically-based insights into customer perception of Islamic banking, service quality and CSR aspects, and holistic ideas for assessing and improving service quality in order to induce greater customer satisfaction, increase young customer perception, CSR issue, all of which will assist in creating positive brand experience and spread positive thoughts toward Islamic banking. Finally, the hierarchy model used to evaluate service quality will help bank managers assess bank service quality at the overall, primary and sub-dimensional levels. Additionally, the knowledge gained from this research will be used by students who are interested in the topic of Islamic banking in marketing perspectives to address issues regarding young generation customers of Islamic banking.

Keyword: Customer Behaviour, CSR, Service Quality, Customer Satisfaction, Brand Experience, Word-of-mouth, Islamic Banking. Generation Z.

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Islamic Financial Terminology		
No	Islamic Banking	Meaning
1	Halal	Lawful
2	Haram	Unlawful
3	Ijara	A leasing agreement (asset purchased by bank and leased to the customer over a specific period)
4	Mudaraba	An investment partnership (partnership financing contract under which one party provides the labour whilst other provides the capital)
5	Murabaha	Consumer loan (asset purchased by the bank and sold on to the customer with an agreed mark-up)
6	Musharaka	An investment partnership in which profit-sharing terms are agreed in advance, and losses re pegged to the amount investment (private equity)
7	Riba	Increase or addition (it denotes any increase or advantage obtained by the lender as a conditional of loan. Riba in all form is prohibited in Islam)
8	Shariah	Islamic law as revealed in the Quran and through the example of prophet Muhammad. A shariah compliant product meet the requirements of Islamic law.
9	Sukuk	Bond (Islamic type of bond representing the ownership by the Sukuk holders in the underlying asset.
10	Takaful	Islamic insurance (it is a risk sharing entity that allows for the transparent sharing of risk by pooling individual contributors for the benefit of all subscribers).
11	Zakah	Almsgiving (the obligation that an individual has to donate a certain proportion of wealth each year to charitable causes).

CHAPTER I

Introduction

In the new era of globalisation, people's life has significantly changed compared to the last decade in terms of information and communication technology development. Technology has played a crucial role in making life easier. Riza (2019) highlighted that improving technology regarding information and communication is a vital aspect of changing industrial activities from manual action to automatic, which is controlled by machine or technology activities and from offline transactions to online transactions. In fact, the growth of technology impacts human activities to improve daily life work more effectively and efficiently. Moreover, this improvement has considerably affected the banking sector industry. Financial corporations and banks have improved their functions as financial intermediaries by implementing various information technologies (Chang, 2002; Gourlay and Pentecost, 2002; VanHoose, 2003). According to Marzuki and Nurdin (2020) the improvement of financial technology has several primary purposes, for instance, providing convenient services to the broader community to obtain access to financial goods and services, supporting and facilitating banking transactions and assisting in improving financial activity literacy to the customers. Therefore, technology has played a crucial aspect in the banking industry around the world these days.

In the banking sector, Islamic finance has been the fastest-improving industry in the financial sector since the last decade, at an estimated growth rate of 15-20 per cent per annum (Haque et al, 2007). The emergence of the Islamic financial system has created a new dimension to economic concepts and specifically to Islamic finance institutions. It has been played considerably to compete in the global financial market (Fazlan and Mohammad, 2007; Hassan and Lewis, 2007). The Islamic finance system is defined based on the *Shariah* law or Islamic regulation, which consists of interest-free institutions (Hassan and Lewis, 2007). Compared to the conventional financial system, it prohibits usury or *Riba*, the collection and payment of interest. In addition, the system promotes profit sharing in all conduct of banking business, such as among stakeholders (BNM, 2007). Islamic financial institutions have existed rapidly around the world and received immense acceptance from Muslim and non-Muslim's customers (Aziz Za, 2006).

The increasing international interest in the Islamic system is a reflection of the success that this sector has achieved during its short history in the global market. The global market is concerned about this system because it provides economic added-value to stakeholders and goals to create equivalence in benefits and costs, free from harmful speculation is obtaining more attention and better global understanding (Kamal, 2011). Moreover, several Western supervisory institutions are incorporating amendments to their supervisory and regulatory legislation to accept Islamic banking and Islamic complaints goods for reinforcing the role of Islamic finance globally. In fact, several countries have adopted Islamic financial banks to offer goods and services based on Islamic systems in current years, such as European, American and Western markets.

According to Moody (2011) a massive number of banks in GCC nations and Asia are managing funds of over USD 300 billion and are encouraged to extend the market for introducing Islamic financial services.

It is inevitable that the growth of Islamic finance institutions worldwide, nevertheless, it is a requirement to improve goods and services which are in line with the modified needs and demands of clients to remain competitive in the business market (Thambiah et al, 2011). In the banking industry, there is a high level of competition these days, and it is getting more intensive around the world. The process of globalisation and liberalisation, together with digitalisation, has fuelled the intensity of business competition at present. With the high level of competition in the banking industry, the Islamic finance system is no longer regarded as a business entity striving to fulfil only the religious factor of the Muslim society but is more considered as a business that competes with a conventional system (Thambiah et al, 2011).

Islamic banking institutions are mainly located in the Middle East and Gulf regions, such as Saudi Arabia, Kuwait, Iran, and the United Arab Emirates and in south-east region Asia, such as Malaysia and Indonesia, also south Asia region. According to Islamic Banking Bulletin (2012) 13% of the share of Islamic finance corporations has been contributed by the Far East region and South Asia, while the rest of the share contributed to the rest of the world. The institutions have played significantly and become a vibrant industry in the economic aspect. Moreover, Maintaining the customers is one of the crucial factors to consider in any business sector. The customers' behaviour plays a crucial role in the banking industry (conventional and Islamic systems). Al-Ajmi et al (2009) argued that the customer considers several factors in adopting the banking system, such as several personal, cultural issues, economic and social. On the fundamental aspect of adopting banking services, Islamic institutions improved their relevant strategies to target the customer community, especially the young generation (Ashar and Yazdifar, 2016).

Figure 1. 1: Global Trends in Islamic Finance and the UK Market (The city UK, 2017).

From the UK perspective, a rapid improvement in Islamic banking has been shown (picture 1), which indicates the UK is the leading Western nation for implementing the Islamic finance system, and over 20 banks have already offered Islamic finance services, with five banks are offered fully Sharia (Islamic law). Moreover, the UK government has received involvement support from the Islamic finance sector to support some projects such as the Battersea power station, London Gateway, and the Shard (The city UK, 2017). In addition, another aspect of education, the UK is the world's largest nation, which provides 69 courses in Islamic finance. Therefore, the UK has been significantly involved with Islamic banking in recent years. In addition, Muslims in the UK are much younger than the average person and have larger than average households (Gatehousebank, 2019).

Targeting young generation customers for every business is one of the mandatory factors in the banking system because it could impact long-term relationships. Generation Z should be considered potential clients because it relates to grants, loans or financial aid from the family in terms of managing the customers for study (Jasin, nd). Consequently, this generation could obtain high income and thus build a significant attractive group of clients for finance corporations. This generation is enormous in the market. Moreover, this group defines self-identity as compassionate, loyal, open-minded, loyal, determined and responsible, and they

might stay loyal to the brand and stick with the company throughout daily life (Sparks and Honey, 2014). Therefore, this generation is a considerable requirement for the banking industry because it could enhance an excellent business, and it also impacts long-term revenue benefits.

Generation Z identifies as savers in the financial aspect, and this generation is in its infancy (Visioncritical, nd). They focus on saving money rather than spending the money. So, this generation significantly requires financial services to control their money. This generation also believes in being able to buy a house, travel around the world and invest money (Visioncritical, nd). In addition, this generation trusts the banks' service as an adviser and indicates more important factors compared to newspaper magazines, social media, finance apps, google and financial advisors. However, the most critical adviser comes from the family and friends as the first factor (Visioncritical, nd). Moreover, this generation emphasises the savers' aspect, which is an opportunity for any financial service corporation to renew and revitalise its brand. Therefore, generation Z identify as a savers customer and requires a financial service to control and maintain their money.

Problem Statement

Islamic banking and finance in the United Kingdom have grown significantly during the last decade in the market. London, as an international financial centre, attracts considerable Islamic funds through investment banks and other corporations' finance intermediaries having business links with Middle Eastern countries (Masood et al, 2009). According to (Housby, 2011) the UK government has asserted its explicit desire to tackle the financial exclusion of UK-based Muslims and assist ethical practices in the sector more widely. In addition. Housby (2013) argued that the potential demand for Islamic finance system services in the UK is significant. Although Muslims living in the UK indicate a strong desire to adopt Islamic finance services, it may not follow that considerable effective demand for such service actually exists at the grassroots level. Several Islamic finance businesses have failed in the UK market, such as Al Baraka Bank in early 1990. At present, established financial services have also been changing the way they compete for market share by launching challenger brands, which considerably position an excellent service to a new generation of potential customers, for instance, the young generation (Ftadviser, 2021).

According to Kaabachi et al (2022) Generation Z perspectives indicate different needs and expectations than other generations, regardless of fee and rate considerations. This generation hopes for a more substantial banking experience and better quality of service. Moreover, there are several main crucial aspects that they consider, such as ease of access to relevant information, better functionality and a more comprehensive range of personalisation of goods and services (Kaabachi et al, 2022). They are digital native customers and looking for an omnichannel banking experience, finding out and valuing personal exchanges when it comes to financial issues (Target, 2020). Receiving advice and support from their financial provider is vital. Due to a lack of financial maturity, they are more likely to find out any information through human interaction and use

banking staff compared to other generations, especially when setting up higher-value goods (Kaabachi et al, 2022). In addition, this generation emphasises the traditional values of freedom, friendship, health, ethics and transparency. Therefore, Generation Z mainly choose a great banking experience for their financial institution. Branding issues must be one of the main reasons for choosing the financial service for this generation.

Branding is one of the vital issues that has been considered a top management priority in the business sector, and it is the most valuable intangible asset for the company (Keller and Lehmann, 2006). Consequently, branding has been identified as the primary beneficial aspect for both the company and its customers (Kotler, 2003). Moreover, a strategy of brand differentiation has been made a priority amid higher competition in the marketplace (Bao and Sweeney, 2009). According to Maehle et al (2011) the functional qualities of brands have often become the crucial factor for consumer brand purchase. In addition, previous scholars have shown that customers appreciate brands which support them in enjoying daily life and creating and expressing their self-concepts (Mishra et al, 2015). The self-concepts are related to the total set of individual's thoughts and feelings concerning himself as an object, and it refers to the brand experience aspect that has demonstrated their determining role in the customers' choices (Coelho et al, 2019).

Furthermore, another customer behaviour strategy, which is one of the crucial factors in enhancing the business, especially for a long-term strategy of the banking sector, which is related to the experience of customers, is Word of Mouth. It refers to exchanging opinions (positive or negative) about a corporation's product (Almossawi, 2015). Word-of-mouth is one of the marketing tools for communication with other people. Mukerjee (2018) highlighted that WoM communication is more influential than communication through other promotional methods. WoM is a concept of informal communication between clients regarding the ownership, application, or characteristics of certain goods or services (Singh, 2013). Moreover, WoM communication is recognised as playing a significant role in influencing customer attitudes and behavioural intentions towards the products or services of the brand. Customer satisfaction is one of the fundamental factors to achieve a positive WoM from clients. In fact, Anderson (1998) stated that there is a crucial factor association between WoM and satisfaction. The customers might tell positive WoM to other people, such as friends, relatives, family, etc, whereas dissatisfied clients might pass negative WoM (Tucker, 2011; Jalilvand et al, 2012). Thus, it is essential to maintain the customer satisfaction issue to enhance the business at a high level of competition. Furthermore, feeling that one might obtain after adopting the service, other sources of WoM include communications from trusted people (Bergeron et al, 2003), and service quality (Parasuraman et al, 1998).

In the banking industry, the competition for clients has always been regarding delivering service quality remarkable. The measure of successful service mainly relates to the satisfaction aspect to achieve the end aim

of creating customer loyalty. Nevertheless, with the high competition in the banking sector, services are becoming similar to one another factor. Bank brands are growing undifferentiated in the minds of clients in today's business era, and the growing crucial of the bank sector to find differentiating value amidst competition is clearly proven (Wulandari, 2015). Moreover, a recent study highlighted that traditional marketing practices which only focused on customer satisfaction are not sufficient (Tsai, 2005). Banking, as one of the service sector players, requires finding an alternative concept of differentiation. Furthermore, McCole (2004) argued that in business, marketers should not only enhance the customer satisfaction factor to the experience created by a product and service. It is essential to consider the customer experience factor in the banking service for an excellent evaluation, and it might also impact the future strategy. In addition, Customer satisfaction is customer feedback in the form of evaluation after adopting bank service compared to customer expectations. Satisfied clients mean similarity between services' performance with customer expectation, encouraging clients to use the service. Kim et al (2015) argue that clients' perception quality influences the customer satisfaction. Generally, service quality is an antecedent of the border method of customer satisfaction (Cantalops and Salvi, 2014). According to Anderson et al (1998) the importance of each aspect of service quality that influences customer satisfaction varies with the situation.

Serving an excellent service is one of the critical aspects of the banking service. The firm should implement the best strategy for its customers by adopting experiential marketing, and it will create the best value (Williams, 2006). In addition, it is believed that "experience" is the next differentiation value to succeed in the competition of the market (Lush et al, 2007; Vargo and Lush, 2008; Johnston and Kong, 2011). Therefore, brand experience is one of the main concerns of the Islamic banking sector to enhance the best service and stay in the market of high competition. Furthermore, the brand experience aspect is not only the primary concern of every corporation banking industry, especially for long-term strategy. It is believed that after having a remarkable experience, the customers might communicate with other people regarding the brand of products and services they have.

In this context, it is inevitable the growth of Islamic banking in the UK during the last decade. In fact, total assets in this sector have reached more than \$2 trillion in recent years and are expected to become \$3.8 trillion by 2023 (Mambu,2021). According to Mambu (2021) 2,000 young customers, which include millennials and Generation Z, indicated that over half, 53 per cent of participants would choose Islamic banking for their service in the banking sector. In addition, generation Z prefers traditional banking as a financial institution. In fact, 87 per cent of customers in this generation use the traditional way compared to a challenger bank system as their services (The Financial Brand, 2021). However, younger clients are demanding financial change, and the Islamic finance market is no exception. In addition, this generation expects to align with their lifestyle and values without compromising on flexibility or ease of use (Mambu, 2021). Moreover, Islamic

financial institutions must adequately understand the young customers' generation because Generation Z could be different from other generations. They are technologically savvy and more globally mobile than the previous generations. Furthermore, Sohail et al (2014) argued that Islamic banking is not providing their service to their potential clients due to a lack of knowledge from the customers about the Islamic finance system. They do not provide information to the clients and do not inform the customers about Islamic banking products and services. Thus, it is crucial to measure the Generation Z customers of Islamic banking perspective in one of the existences UK's Islamic banking because this generation is a vast potential market for long-term strategy.

Furthermore, the perception of Generation Z customers' Islamic banking service is measured by an understanding factor that would predict clients' perceptions regarding adopting the service. There are several factor perceptions of Islamic banking services from customers, such as bank reputation, awareness of Islamic banking, relative advantage and perceived combability (Bisharat, 2014; Faisal et al, 2014; Aziz et al, 2015; Amin et al, 2013). In addition, the ethical responsibility issue is also a crucial determinant of Islamic finance because it relates to Islamic law and guidelines for all financial transactions in Islamic ways, and staff need to understand ethical responsibility, which could create customer satisfaction (Rahman et al, 2023). This generation is also expected to be more involved in the environment, justice and problems of other aspects (Jain et al, 2014). The members of this generation are also expected to have a more positive attitude toward community, emotionalism, environment, friendship, justice, and spirituality compared to the previous generation (Jain et al, 2014). As a result, Generation Z cares about the corporate social responsibility factor (Zenefits, 2021).

It is believed that there is a long process in the marketing field to analyse the customers from adopting a bank service to enjoying the service. In addition, it is argued that customer experience regarding the brand is one of the significant values from the customer perspective and afterwards, the customers will pass WoM communication to other people in terms of a product or service. As far as existing studies are considered from the perspective of the Islamic Banking system, an immense portion of these studies has focused on the Muslim nations where this finance institution mode has emerged. Rare literature is available to analyse and examine the factors and indicators which control the perceptions of clients toward Islamic corporations in Western countries such as the United Kingdom. In addition, the main focus of this study is Generation Z customers of Al Rayan Bank in the UK, as previously rare literature is available on factors impacting this generation. This young generation population has the potential to increase a nation's financial institution inclusion through innovation and digitalisation because they are more adaptable to technology and still prefer the traditional way if supported by an awareness factor which has a positive inclusive development. The present study is designed to determine the analysis of customers' perception of the Islamic banking service of AL Rayan Bank

for Generation Z in the UK to obtain an excellent experience and communicate to other people or communities regarding the product or service.

Aim of Research

The main aim of the research is to analyse and examine factors that influence customers' perception of Islamic banking service, corporate social responsibility and service quality on satisfaction, brand experience and WoM, which is influenced by customer satisfaction from Generation Z Al Rayan Bank in the UK perspective.

Research Objectives

From the study of related work, it is possible to identify the gaps in the existing literature on customer satisfaction, brand experience and WoM aspects. The study is focused on the Generation Z customers of Al Rayan bank in the UK with several factors such as customers' perception toward Islamic banking, CSR perception and service quality to brand experience and WoM. However, it is believed that customer satisfaction is a mediate variable among these factors. It is believed that measuring these factors could significantly improve the service of Islamic banking, especially in the marketing and management fields. It also recognises good perception as a potential tool of market competitiveness for the Islamic bank and tries to discover the importance of perception in the customers' perspective and offers several exciting and valuable insights for this sector business in planning future activities towards improving the customers' perspective and exceeding clients' expectations. Moreover, practising experiential marketing will result in the creation of value (Williams, 2006). Hence, the urgency to find competitive value in the Islamic banking sector is undeniable, which is driven by both practice and the academic world, and experience could be a differentiating value for bank marketing. In addition, good clients' perspectives could shape positive WoM, which assists banking industry marketing communication.

Furthermore, from the conceptual model proposed in the previous section, it is possible to observe that among the several factors that lead to brand experience and WoM factor, there is a role of customer satisfaction. Thus, the present study is focused on how to measure and track customer satisfaction for Islamic banking in the UK. Furthermore, the research further examines the relationship between customer satisfaction and the other main leading aspects of brand experience and WoM, for example, customers' perception of the Islamic banking service, CSR perception and service quality. In this way, the research study aims to assist the Islamic banking industry in analysing and understanding customer satisfaction in order to be able to implement better marketing strategies and mechanisms to increase brand experience and WoM. To reach this objective, a conceptual model for customer satisfaction, specific to Islamic banking services will be proposed. This conceptual model will indicate the different aspects that lead to customer satisfaction and their corresponding importance in the concept. Therefore, the research objectives are the following:

1. To analyse the main factors of Generation Z customers of Al Rayan Bank in the UK, which influence brand experience and Word of Mouth aspect.
2. To examine customers perceptions of Islamic banking, CSR and service quality on customer satisfaction, brand experience and WoM.
3. The role of customer satisfaction in mediating the effect of customers perception, CSR and service quality on brand experience and WoM.

Research Questions

The following research questions are for further investigation on the topic:

1. What is the main factor of Generation Z customers of Al Rayan Bank in the UK influencing the brand experience and Word-of-Mouth factor?
2. Does customers perception, CSR, and Service quality affect customer satisfaction?
3. Does customers perception, CSR, and Service quality affect the brand experience and WoM?
4. Does customer satisfaction mediate the variable of the customers perception, CSR and service quality on brand experience and WoM?

Justification and Significance of the Research

It has been established from the background review and statement of the study problems which a gap exists in the literature regarding how significant the growth of Islamic banking around the world is these days. The United Kingdom is one of the Western countries which has emerged with an improving Islamic banking system. In fact, UK's government plans to become the first Western nation to implement Islamic bonds (IFIS, 2007). In addition, it supports the role of London as an international financial centre (Housby, 2011). The banking sector is considerably improved in all the sectors of business, and with the development of philosophies relating finance activities to spiritual principles, Islamic banks have permeated the market in both Muslim and non-Muslim nations (Riaz et al, 2017). This process reflected growing that Islamic's economic and social were significantly aligned (Akhtar, 2007; Housby, 2011). Thus, it is believed that Islamic finance has impacted simultaneously on beneficial and detrimental (Hassan, 2008).

Several big companies of banking established Islamic banking principles, for instance, Saudi American Bank and Saudi British Bank. It also International institutions of finance, for example, HSBC and Citibank have been Involved in the market of Islamic banking system (Ahmad, 2008). The improving number of UK banks and companies are implementing to offer Islamic principles or Islamic law financial services. Consequently, the growing Islamic finance system in the UK has become more established compared to other nations with majority Muslim countries such as Malaysia, UAE, Saudi Arabia and Indonesia (Statista, 2020).

Figure 1. 2: Number of Islamic Fintech Companies (Statista, 2020).

In fact, there are 28 banks in the UK which have established Islamic fintech in the market. There are several central Islamic banks involved, such as Gatehouse Bank, Al Rayan Bank, Ahli United Bank, Qatar Islamic Bank (QIB UK), Bank of London & the Middle East (BLME), HSBC, and others. In fact, AL Rayan is one of the most popular and top Islamic banking and finance in the UK market (TheBanker, 2022). The bank was formerly the Islamic Bank of Britain, and it is a commercial bank which was established in 2004. This bank is the pioneer of fully implementing *Shariah* or entirely using Islamic law in the system among other banks in the UK. According to Comparebank (n,d) this bank has seen a surge in popularity amongst non-Muslim clients who are searching for an alternative to the conventional bank system in the UK market. In addition, the bank also offers young person's savings accounts to support a better future of saving with the Islamic system way and having an awareness of ethical finance. This bank became the first bank worldwide to issue a public sterling sukuk in a non-Muslim nation (TheBanker, 2020). Furthermore, this bank could offer an ethical option and a competitive pricing model. Therefore, it is believed that Al Rayan Bank is one of the famous Islamic bank services in the UK, which could contribute more to young people and consider more with the ethical or traditional finance system in the UK.

It has been established from the background review and the statement of the research problem that a gap exists in the literature regarding Islamic banking in the UK. Choosing Al Rayan Bank as an object of the research, especially for the young generation, is considerably the central gap of research because the

researcher has yet to see any similar study which concerns Generation Z in the UK using the Islamic finance system. Al Rayan Bank is one the favourite Islamic banks in the UK with entire *Shariah*. It has an excellent reputation with Islamic shariah and the significant growth of the company during the last decade. Moreover, it also could be a better understanding for the researcher to analyse deeply regarding the Islamic system because this bank entirely implements Shariah law or Islamic system in the product and their service. They are applying several factors of marketing variables to examine the customers which, is implemented customer perception of Islamic banking, CSR, service quality, customer satisfaction, brand experience and WoM to achieve the main research objectives.

It is a crucial issue that companies should consider more with the young generation as the best customers because it has a significant impact on long-term relationships. Maintaining and retaining this generation is significantly the best strategy, not only for a great experience but also for long-term profit. Thus, the findings of this research will be of immense contribution to future research, considering that banking businesses are becoming very competitive, especially in the UK market. Moreover, for the researcher, this research has enabled an uncovering of critical fields within marketing and business administration aspect. It will also benefit to students who intend to study the concept of the Islamic banking system with a young generation's perspective in the future.

Outline of the Research

Chapters

Chapter 1- Introduction	Comprises the introduction to the research, serving as the foundation of the research and presenting the rationale for undertaking this study project. Importantly, it provides the aims and objectives of the study. Finally, this chapter includes informing the chapter-by-chapter structure of the study.
Chapter 2- Literature reviews	Give information about models and theories relevant to the study. Findings of various studies have also been discussed in this chapter and also comprise information related to the Islamic banking sector. Provide the conceptual framework and generate a hypothesis.

Chapter 3- Research methodology Define research philosophies and thier justification to apply in the study. The data collection and analysis method and the nature of the study have been discussed. Different tools used in the study have also been presented.

Chapter 4- Result Discusses the findings from the main research. Deceptive analysis and statistical analysis are implemented to integrate the data generated from this full-scale research.

Chapter 5- Discussion Discusses the findings from the main study.

Chapter 6- Conclusion and Recommendation The study has been concluded in this section, and suggestions for the betterment of study findings have been presented.

The Summary of Chapter

This chapter has presented the study research background, followed by the company overview, the statement of the research problem, and the analysis of factors using Islamic banking in the UK from the Generation Z perspective of Al Rayan Bank. Moreover, this chapter provides the main aims of the study and respectively presents and discusses research objectives and research questions, which sets out to address and presents the primary purposes. Lastly, it provides the structure of the research.

CHAPTER II

LITERATURE REVIEW

Introduction

This chapter encompasses the literature review. It contains a background of relevant theories that assists this study in evaluating and analysing more detailed theories. The literature review helps the reader to present a better understanding of the specific subject in this research. Moreover, the primary rationale for conducting the literature review is to tackle the research issues referred to in the previous chapter to be more critical or specific regarding the theoretical aspect. Therefore, it provides several relevant theories of business and management contexts in this section, especially in the marketing aspect, because it relates to customer behaviour and banking. It provides business and management issues, Islamic banking, adoption of Islamic banking, Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR), Service Quality, Customer Satisfaction, Brand Experience and Word of Mouth (WOM). In addition, the chapter highlights the gap in the literature and suggests how this study might plug these in order to make an incremental contribution to the knowledge base. Finally, this chapter also explains how the hypotheses are generated.

Grand Theory of Marketing

Marketing is not only regarding advertising or selling a product or service to customers. Marketing actually encompasses numerous activities in the business sector. It is the process through which the firm wins and keeps clients. According to U.S Chamber of Commerce (2016) marketing is the matchmaker between what a business is selling and what clients are purchasing. It is also a win-win partnership between a business and its market, not always related to the client's aspect but with them. In the 21st, the definition and purpose of marketing are about a business discipline (Matusinska et al, 2019). Marketing was highly focused on the producer's interest, but it is no longer a valid assumption in current business. Doyle (2016) states that the current markets have become more complex, and more global and so has marketing as a professional discipline. Therefore, marketing is a critical aspect of the way firms interact with their clients to build relationships which are beneficial between them. In addition, business and management discipline implements marketing tools to identify their audience before advertising to them in the current market situation.

There are several advantages of adopting a marketing approach in the business, as products purpose to establish solutions to specific clients' needs. Firstly, it generates goods more likely to find a ready market, encourage customer loyalty, maintain the relationship between a firm and customers, promote awareness of competitors' action and goods offerings, creates potential to make differentiation products or service and provide marketing with a more significant impact on strategic planning (Drummond and Ensor, 2005). Therefore, the marketing process could be summarised into the following stages:

Figure 2. 1: The Marketing Process (Kotler and Armstrong, 2012).

The evolution of marketing has been significantly improved in the current year. Marketing strategy has led to considering more social responsibility, ethics and accountability in business. The strategy of marketing, which considers more on socially responsible activities and abiding by high ethical quality, could bring more impact on profit in the business (Matusinska et al, 2019). Moreover, the new definition of marketing perspective is introduced of stakeholders implies a shift from a dyadic view, for example, organisation and individual, to a triadic perspective (organisation, clients and other external stakeholders) (Vaaland et al,2008). It is important to consider the business for social responsibility issue as a whole as one of the stakeholders, and the business could make a decision which applies consideration to the well-being of society (Matusinska et al, 2019).

A big aspect which institutions should take into account when implementing socially responsible marketing is how goods affect the global environment. It involves several factors such as pollution generated by making the goods, forms of packaging used and the process of recycling, and energy used for production, which impact the environment and are responsible to society. There are several ways to consider society responsible. It implements operating standards which govern their socially responsible marketing practice, and financial aid causes that benefit society. However, in the current business, the company accomplish both improving green marketing products and aiding cause-marketing activities in to society (Matusinska et al, 2019). In addition, according to Levens (2012) socially responsible marketing could be both altruistic and profitable. Therefore, it is crucial in the modern era of business to consider more a socially responsible marketing perspective.

Consumer Behaviour

Consumer behaviour is an aspect of human behaviour. It is related to the actions, consequences and reactions which happen as the consumer goes through a decision-making process, reaches a decision and then puts the goods to use (Babin and Harris, 2013). In addition, consumer behaviour is defined as searching for, buying, using, evaluating, and disposing of goods and services which the consumers expect would satisfy their needs (Schiffman and Kanuk, 2007). The definition of consumer behaviour reveals two main central themes, which are a process of actions involving buying, usage and or disposal, and it relates to individual or group consumers in products, services, ideas and experiences (Ling, n,d). Moreover, according to Mowen (1988) there are three basic perspectives to the scholar of consumer buy behaviour, which are decision-making perspective, experiential and behavioural influence perspective.

Furthermore, the study of consumer behaviour has significantly improved over the years. According to Marsden and Littler (1998) there are five contemporary perspectives: behavioural, cognitive and interpretive (known as traditional perspectives), trait and postmodern (known as new perspectives). In addition, Pachauri (2002) argued that adopting the classification of perspectives into those that result from the positivist paradigm, such as behavioural, cognitive, rational, personality, attitudinal, motivational and situational influence, these are called traditional perspectives and into those resulting from non-positivist paradigm known under emerging perspective and consisting of the interpretative and postmodern perspectives.

The theory of consumer culture is also impacted on the consumer behaviour purchase. It relates to consumption as much less rational or conscious activities. Fahy and Jobber (2015) highlighted that consumption is defined as a more sociocultural or experimental activity which is laden with emotion and support to explain, for instance, why customers derive pleasure from shopping or look for specific meanings in a particular brand from the consumer purchased. There are several aspects of understanding consumer culture theory, which include cultural factors (language, religion, education, aesthetics and art, politics, economics, law, values and beliefs), social (reference group, family, roles and status), personal (age, occupation, personality, lifestyle and value), psychological (motivation, perception, memory and attitude) factor which are believed that those factors are the fundamental of consumer behaviour (Matusinska et al, 2019).

The scope of consumer behaviour theory has emerged not only in the conventional aspect but also in faith-based consumer behaviour, which is best termed as Islamic consumer behaviour (Amin, 2019). Consequently, the study of consumer behaviour has been implemented and involved improving acceptance by scholars in Islamic institutional and finance (Al-Mutairi, 2010; Rizal and Amin, 2017). Moreover, Dar (2002) argues that there has been a positive attitude of prospective clients, which accelerates demand through a developed customer base, it determines the demand and loyalty to Islamic banking goods in the consumer behaviour

aspect. In fact, from the clients' perspective, it could significantly impact the health and wealth of the goods through an improved perception and demand, which also affects the profit and growth of Islamic banks (Amin, 2019). It is believed that perception is a process of choosing, organising and interpreting stimuli into a meaningful whole. According to Koudelka (2018) it is to several extent consistent with customers' expectations. Furthermore, there is a dearth of study aids with respect to consumer behaviour and its link to Islamic home financing goods (Md-Taib et al, 2008; Abdul Razak and Md-Taib, 2011; Abduh and Abdul Razak, 2011).

Consumer Behaviour in Banking System

Consumer behaviour has inevitably become a burning aspect in today's competitive world, especially in the banking service. It is believed that clients usually search for better alternatives (Kassim and Souiden, 2007). Understanding consumer behaviour has become a herculean task for companies of the modern world in this sector. According to (Chaker, 2015) the service design of the banking sector is different from manufacturing, as services are intangible, and warranty or repair processes are not as important as recovery or reimbursement processes. Moreover, Saiz and Pilgore (2010) highlighted that bank companies should provide services according to the customers' needs, impacting the challenge of retaining clients and restoring public confidence. Additionally, Fejza et al (2017) the banks should also distinguish from customers, so if a bank needs to be inventive, it should include new services or systematically modify the existing in order to provide something innovative in the market. Another crucial factor in the service sector is unsatisfactory banking service, which might have a negative effect on the relationship between banks and clients (Anneli, 2014). Likewise, Flavian et al (2004) indicated that in order to compete corporations might exploit new resources of competitive advantage to offer distinguished services to their clients. Therefore, it is believed that in the service industry, banks should provide high-quality service at the essential requirement to gain a positive attitude from the clients.

In the banking sector, the trust issue is one of the crucial aspects to consider as a variable from the customers' perspective (Kantsberger and Kunz, 2010). Anneli (2014) states that its deficiency indicates a severe problem in the banking sector and it acts as an indication for bank managers to reduce the perceived risk in banking service. In addition, Saiz and Pilgore (2010) indicated that a considerable trust issue has a profound effect on the banking sector and it declines in consumer trust affects customer relationships and forces the clients to explore more suitable services elsewhere, thereby diluting the customer relationship. Thus, the trust issue is one of the significant factors in the banking industry because it can impact a positive experience of the customers' behaviour.

Furthermore, in customer behaviour, especially in the banking sector, employee behaviour is also relevant to the customers, especially for young generation. It is a crucial aspect in the service industry because it is

immediately integrated by clients while forming overall judgment (Lemmink and Mattsson, 2002). According to Browning (2006) staff behaviour is the interaction between service providers and clients. Consequently, it could relate to gesture factors such as voice, movement and attitude performance from the staff while serving clients (Tsaur et al, 2004). In the service sector, the staff is also supposed to deal with the emotional expression of clients (Rafaeli, 1989). In fact, less skilled staff may not be able to handle the situation when the image of the corporation is at stake (Lemmink and Mattsson, 2002). In addition, Law et al (2010) highlighted that employee's behaviour is as universal contribution of performance towards a company. The service behaviour for customer satisfaction is managed by human resource management with the management of knowledge, abilities, skills and performance of the staff. As a result, it could impact the service quality perception of clients through the management system (Tsaur et al, 2004).

Customer behaviour in the banking sector is not only in the conventional sense but, it is also extended to faith-based consumer behaviour or it is best termed as Islamic consumer behaviour. In fact, there are numerous previous studies on Islamic consumer behaviour existed. Thus, studying and understanding customer behaviour in the Islamic banking sector, vital in business fields, which warrants further empirical support. As such, the current study intends to analyse and examine the factors that could assist in determining consumer behaviour of the facility from the young generation's perspective.

Principle of Islamic Banking and Finance

In the new global economy, Islamic finance has become a central issue for the banking and finance sector. Islamic banking is an economic and financial framework that is based upon the principle of Islamic laws, also known as Shariah Laws. The laws basically prohibit the acceptance or giving of interest on the money borrowed or lent (*Riba*) (Iqbal and Molyneux, 2005). According to Ahmad et al (2010) *Sharia* law forbids any transaction in doing *Riba* because it is held to break the natural bonds between people, reinforce iniquity and lead to social unrest. Therefore, in Islamic banking, it enhances prohibiting interest remains the fundamental defining system of Islamic banking. Moreover, in the Islamic finance system, money is not to be held in savings; it is mobilised in the real economy by *Shariah* laws and, there are several financing instruments, for example, *Mudarabah*, *Musharakah* and *Murabahah*. According to Beekun and Badawi (2005), theoretical instruments of the Islamic finance system should obey that all instruments are adopted based on Islamic laws, especially in terms of socio-economic justice and prohibition on interest. Nevertheless, the Islamic finance system is a phenomenon which is much more than the prohibition of interest. It might also seek to establish a balance between earning and spending for the development of society as a whole (Haron and Hisham, 2003).

According to Chapra (1992) Islamic economic principles have four objectives required to obey Islamic laws: the equitable distribution of income such as plus, wealth, growth and stability. The Islamic principle might

promote a positive goal-oriented role for the government in raising moral consciousness and determining social and also economic reforms with suitable incentives. Therefore, the Islamic system has four central systems. First, free consent, in the system, needs the mutual consent of the two parties involved prior to any contract being applied. Second, Akbar et al (2012) stated that Islamic banking is characterised as an interest-free principle. In the Islamic principle, interest is not allowed in the priority system of laws, which could lead to a more stable system (Mohsin, 1986). Third, prohibition of *Gharar* (uncertainty, risk or speculation). El-Gamal (2000) argues that *Gharar* defines “the deal of factors whose presence and features in type, species, amount of thing, value, payment time etc are uncertain”. Last system, profit and loss risk sharing: Islamic banking principle encourages Muslims to invest in a Halal (lawful) way when doing business effectively and become partners in the corporation rather than becoming lenders. Thus, in the system, the depositors become investors and the manager works as operational partners who invest their capital and effort for the return of the profit. In addition, the agreement between them equally shared the risk with the sharing of partnership in the Islamic finance system.

Globalisation is increasing all of the time, especially in terms of the banking sector. Innovation is also a crucial factor to survive in the high competition of the market. Islamic banking has developed significantly since the last decade in terms of innovation and it still continues to grow by 2 trillion USD in 2015, estimated between 10 % and 20 % per year in different economic and financial segments around the world (ICD, 2016). Islamic finance corporation is not only growing in Muslim countries but also involving non-Muslim nations (Iqbal and Mirakhor, 2013). Thus, Islamic banking is one of the alternative solutions to the financial system using traditional ways that have been growing significantly in the last decade.

Islamic Banking Products and Services

The Islamic finance system basically emphasises free interest in the Sharia laws, equity participation, joint ventures and profit-sharing in the regulation of Islamic principles (Ahmad, 1994). Nevertheless, according to Rosly and Bahar (2003) in terms of profit and loss sharing in the Islamic finance system is the main strict principle of the system. Furthermore, Islamic finance encourages promoting social justice through its goods; it offers ethics and endeavours to gain an equal distribution of wealth and income (Riaz et al, 2016). In the Islamic finance system, several products offering to customers, for instance *Murabahah* (Mark-up financing), *Ijarah* (leasing), *Musharakah* (equity participation), *Mudarabah* (trustee finance contract system) and Sukuk (bonds) adopted as an alternative to interest-bearing goods (Housby, 2011).

Islamic Banking vs Conventional Banking

The fundamental aspect of Islamic banking is emphasised risk sharing (Mirakhor and Zaidi, 2007), as explained by Khandelwal (FRSGlobal, 2009) due to the main system of Islamic banking is prohibited relating the interest in Islamic laws, suppliers of funds become investors instead of creditors. The provider of financial

capital and the entrepreneur share business risk in return for shares of the profits, and this system also has an impact on risk management. Nevertheless, implementing profit-sharing concepts in Islamic finance changes the nature of the risks of Islamic banking.

Figure 2. 2: Risks in Conventional Banks vs Islamic Banks (FRSGlobal, 2009).

The Islamic system is based on the model of profit and risk sharing and avoidance of the concept of interest. In addition, the system provider is not automatically entitled to payment in full of principal and periodic distributions. However, that risk also requires consideration of the finance provider along with the borrower. However, Islamic finance contrasts with the conventional banking concept of lending. As a result, a number of considerations are also considered when assessing the risk profile of Islamic banks.

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Table 2. 1: Differences between Islamic Finance and Conventional Finance (Akkizidis and Khandelwal, 2007)

The figure above shows the main different aspects of the banking concept and mainly emphasises the interest, or it called *Riba*. *Riba* is defined as earning which is received without any justification for a business transaction (Abdel-Haq and Al-Oma, 1996). The Islamic method also focuses on the profit-sharing policy, which is illegal to charge money from clients for borrowing and lending money. On the other hand, a conventional system could charge clients for the service fee as a source of profit (Dusuki and Abdullah, 2007). Therefore, on the core of principles, both banking concepts are entirely different from each other. Mainly the Islamic finance concept enhances the brotherhood aspect (Dusuki and Abdullah, 2007).

The Islamic finance system has been in existence for the modern era in the last three decades and it is still in many respects an infant industry. Figure 2.3 shows that Islamic finance institutions are striving to build their reputation by exploiting ‘blind spots’ in the market and trying to improve their competitive advantage. Moreover, Islamic finance is also considered the most regarding rivalry for clients’ loyalty and faces a high level of uncertainty. However, the conventional banks are already in the maturity stage in terms of market aspect and they dominated regardless of the high level of customers and entrepreneurial actions continue but are greatly deemphasised (Kamal, 2011).

Figure 2. 3: Development Stages of Islamic Banking (Kamal, 2011).

Industry Overview

According to the City UK (2015) the United Kingdom is a huge market for financial corporations providing Islamic financial solutions in the EU with total assets of \$4.5 billion by the end of 2014. The prior fully fledged Islamic system compliant in the UK is the Islamic Bank of Britain (IBB), which was first established in 2004 and was taken over by Masraf Al Rayan and renamed Al Rayan Bank in October 2014. In current years, the UK has the most improved Islamic banking sector in the Western country with fully implemented Shariah systems such as Al Rayan Bank; the bank of London and the Middle East country (Benamraoui et al, 2020). Al Rayan bank is the only stand-alone retail bank and has eight branches and over 50,000 customers across the UK market (Al Rayan Bank, 2017). In addition, this bank offers the largest range of shariah-compliant retail financial goods in the UK, including Islamic mortgage alternatives, home purchase plans (HPP) and buy to-let purchase Plans (BTLPP), and ethical current accounts and saving accounts.

Al Rayan Bank's parent business is Masraf Al Rayan QSC (MAR) a Qatar-based Islamic bank which provides banking, financial and investment services. MAR was founded in January 2006 and is licensed by Qatar Central Bank. It is also the second-largest Islamic bank in Qatar by market value (Al Rayan Bank, 2017). Moreover, in May 2015, the bank was nominated by Global Finance magazine as one of the best Islamic

corporations in the world, in the annual list of the world's best Islamic financial businesses. This is the second time that this bank has selected the award.

The move your money switching scorecard shows Al Rayan Bank to be one of the top three ethical current account providers. The campaign compared over 70 UK and global financial institutions implementing five key indicators such as customer service, culture, supporting the economy, honesty and ethics. This bank obtained a "Good" 74% score (Al Rayan Bank, 2017). In terms of customer service, the bank received 100%, receiving few complaints regarding the service. And this bank achieved high rankings on its bonus policy and also lacked risky investment. Overall, this bank has excellent credibility in the market of UK and around the world.

Customer Perception to Adopt Islamic Banking

According to Zach (2019) customer perception defines to clients' awareness, impression and opinions or thoughts toward a firm, brand and product; multiple factors, including direct and indirect interactions with the goods and service of a company shape it. Business Dictionary (2020) states that customer perception is related to a marketing concept which encompasses a clients' impression, consciousness or awareness regarding a firm or its offerings. The concept of perception is the process through which clients choose, interpret and organise the information which is collecting from the customers' perspective in terms of the sense in order to provide customers with a meaningful and coherent analysis of the product or service. Moreover, it is essential to analyse the customer perception and awareness aspect to measure the success of any business endeavour based on finding out the factors which drive clients' buying decisions (Tijjjani et al, 2021).

The growing system of Islamic banking has been significantly improved worldwide, which led to the interest of numerous scholars or studies to analyse the aspects of marketing discipline. Customer behaviour in adopting the Islamic finance institutional is one of the highlight issues in the business sector. There are several aspects of customers when adopting Islamic finance, for instance, reputation of finance institutional, social norms, service quality, convenience, attitude of staff bank, effectiveness of CSR, pricing of Islamic banking goods and services, and consumer awareness (Abou-Youssef et al, 2015; Dusuki and Abdullah, 2007; Echchabi and Aziz, 2012; Souiden and Jabeur, 2015). Moreover, it is believed that the religious aspect is one of the crucial factors from customers to adopt Islamic banking, especially in the Muslim majority countries. Nevertheless, several studies have also attempted to analyse the behaviour of non-Muslims toward Islamic banking in minority and majority-Muslim countries (Mbawuni and Nimako, 2018; Said, 2017). Furthermore, the usual focus on adoption research has always been on a new product, and a minimal but growing number of studies has been on adopting of financial services (Thambiah et al, 2011). Over the last decade, several adoption studies have been conducted in the area of Internet banking adoption, mobile banking adoption,

online banking adoption, and self-service technology adoption (Black et al, 2001; Gerard, 2003). However, in the area of adoption, Islamic banking still has not numerous existed.

It is believed that the growth of Islamic banking has significantly developed during the last decade around the world. Numerous people have adopted the traditional ways of their financial service system to control and manage the financial aspect. The term “Adoption” is to accept formally and put into a consequence to decide something (Tara et al, 2014). Moreover, in terms of “Islamic Banking” is explained as the conduct of the banking operation system in consonance with Islamic teachings (Haque et al, 2007). Compared to conventional regulation, Islamic banking emphasises prohibiting usury, collection and payment of *Riba*; instead, it promotes profit and loss sharing, giving zakat working for the benefit of society and the development of all Halal aspects of business are highly implemented in this system (Tara et al, 2014). Therefore, in this study, investigating the several aspects of marketing perspective which influences the choice of Islamic banking service in non-majority Muslim nation would provide valuable insight to the regulators, regarding non-Muslim clients’ perception of the Islamic banking system. Moreover, it is imperative for the business sector must assess the efficiency of the service to make valuable developments to their service and also to maintain existing non-Muslim clients, as well as to attract new customer, to improve their customer base in the UK, especially for young generation.

Antecedents Variables of Research

Customer Perceptions of Islamic Banking

Ali and Syed (2010) conducted the impact of the perceptions and attitudes of professionals towards Islamic finance on the events of 9/11. They found that the event in the US created false impressions and misconceptions regarding Muslims. However, as a result of the study has shown that it significantly contributed to the growth in and awareness of Islamic banking. According to Gait and Worthington (2008) clients of Islamic banking are considered the most religious factor. However, other aspects also are considered by customers, for instance, cost of finance, bank reputation and service quality. Customers’ perception of service, especially may also be affected by corporation cues and ideas regarding its reputation conveyed formally and informally (Kim and Prabhakar, 2004). A good reputation might impact on assurance of an organisation’s ability, integrity and goodwill. Therefore, supporting to raise trust occurs when clients do not have first-hand knowledge of the service industry (Lohse and Spiller, 1998). In addition, it could also impact the confidence in the corporations’ reputation from the customers’ perspective (Anderson and Weitz, 1989). Thus, it is believed that reputation is one of the significant effects on the customers’ perception, especially in the Islamic banking industry.

Furthermore, Haque et al (2009) conducted a study on consumers’ perceptions regarding Islamic banking in Malaysia. They investigated the perception of clients as a dependent variable and service quality, availability,

confidence in finance corporations and social and religious perspectives as independent variables by implementing the Logit regression concept. The study found a significant positive association between independent and dependent variables. In addition, the availability of services along with social and religious perspectives might make Islamic finance institutions familiar and easy. Furthermore, Muniurrun et al (2010) analysed fundamental factors of acceptance of the Islamic banking system in Malaysia in a descriptive method. They found that ethnic and religious aspects had no massive important effect on the selection of Islamic finance institutions. In addition, the study recommended that people's awareness level regarding Islamic finance was limited. So, the Islamic corporation should emphasise the promotion concept to obtain significant impact in the near future.

There are several studies conducting customer perceptions of Islamic banking. Khattak (2011) analysed the perception of Pakistani corporate clients towards Islamic banking products and services in Pakistan. As a result, he found that knowledge, cost and service factors were the main aspects for corporate clients towards Islamic finance institution goods and services. Chhapra and Bhutto (2013) explored the perception of postgraduate students towards Islamic banking in Pakistan, implementing perceptions as dependent variables and religion, knowledge and service quality as independent variables. As a result of the study indicates that all independent variables had a significant positive relationship with the dependent variable, and religion and level of knowledge regarding Islamic goods and services were equally crucial in Islamic finance.

To conclude, several studies have emphasised the relevance of customers perception of Islamic banking to this study.

- Bank Reputation

There are some scholars who investigated the relevance of reputation variable in selecting Islamic banking (Erol et al, 1990; Haron et al, 1994; Gerrard and Cunningham, 1997; Metawa and Almosawi, 1998; Naser et al, 1999; Ahmad and Haron, 2002; Gait and Worthington, 2008; Bisharat, 2014).

- Awareness of Islamic banking

Several studies which emphasised the customers perception of awareness of Islamic banking highlighted several different contexts (Haron et al, 1994; Metawa and Almosawi: Naser et al, 1999; Rammal and Zurburrig, 2007; Khattak and Rehman, 2010; Keong et al, 2012; Thambiah et al, 2012). In addition, there is a positive relation between client awareness and variables, for instance attitude (Wahyuni, 2012; Echchabi and Aziz, 2012; Faisal et al, 2014).

- Relative Advantage

Several studies have found the relevance of relative advantage in Islamic banking through functional, ethical and social benefits, as well as service quality (Thambiah et al, 2011; Echchabi and Aziz, 2012; Aziz et al, 2015).

- Perceived Combability

Several studies investigated the positive effect of perceived combability in Islamic banking (Thambiah et al, 2011; Ayinde and Echchabi, 2012; Echchabi and Aziz, 2012; Amin et al, 2013; Aziz et al, 2015).

Corporate Social Responsibility Perception

Corporate social responsibility or CSR is defined as an organisational green strategy that proposes to preserve the cultural, economic and social factors of the environment in which a corporation system (Raimi, 2017). This concept received valuable attention during the last decade in the community or society field, especially in the business sector, because it significantly impacts the corporate sector to increase on a continual basis (Hou, 2019). Moreover, this activity depends on a number of factors for example economic conditions, regulations and laws, organisational culture and behaviour also, including the market competition level (Campbell, 2018). According to Gorski (2017) CSR practices significantly contribute to organisational capabilities to take competitive advantage of other communities and achieve sustainable growth objectives. In addition, CSR initiatives not only impact corporations' reputations but also increase clients' loyalty and staff satisfaction (Asrar-Ul-Haq et al, 2017).

The implication of CSR toward corporations has several impacts on the environment which not only increase market share, but also minimise reduction of emissions, pollution and waste, and energy-saving (Awan et al, 2017). According to Turker (2009) implementing the CSR framework by considering stakeholders and categorising CSR activities into four groups, first, namely CSR to stakeholders, CSR to employees, CSR to a client, and CSR to government. Furthermore, Maignan and Ferrel (2000) argued that CSR activity has four aspects which are economic, legal, ethical and discretionary citizenship. The current research considers two dimensions of CSR which are focused on the community or society and customer issues from the Generation Z perspective toward Islamic banking in the UK.

- CSR to the community, it refers to Islamic bank (Al Rayan bank) initiatives for the development community, it includes several factors such as sharing best practices on social responsibility with other communities or society, involving the collaboration issue with educational institutions and also related activities for the well-being of the community.
- CSR to clients, it considers the Islamic banking responsibilities toward the customers, it includes designing products or services offered by Al Rayan Bank, giving the correct information to the clients, ensuring clients' satisfaction through quality goods and services, and respecting clients' complaints and ensuring prompt solution.

CSR is a crucial issue in building and maintaining a favourable corporate reputation which is regarded as an essential strategic resource factoring into a corporation's competitive advantage (Keh and Xie, 2009). Implementing this system into a company is considerably needed to meet better the legitimate, environmental,

economic and social demands of the community. In fact, in the current year, companies not only accept CSR systems to implement but also apply CSR initiatives as management tools (Bielak et al, 2007). Moreover, in terms of the company, it could make proper strategic resource-allocation decisions for various CSR initiatives, it is considerably required to envisage the effect of each CSR initiative on reputation and impact on client trust might be influenced by distinct CSR initiatives and how the consequences affect the corporate reputation (Park et al, 2013). Therefore, CSR initiatives for a corporation are significantly required to build a good reputation not only for customers but also for society and the community in the market and it also impacts the long-term strategy of sustainability.

Corporate Social Responsibility in Islamic Finance

The Islamic finance system is a traditional financial system which emphasises *Shariah* laws or religious values directed at creating the conditions for a social aspect to distribute wealth, and the system is highly considered social responsibility. The system includes the implementation of medium to long-term sustainability in the CSR aspect.

Bowen (1953) stated that CSR is a corporate decision to extend goodwill to society or the community. There are several studies have been conducted on the CSR aspect in the context of Islamic finance that has analysed the fundamental of Islamic laws (Shariah), the objectives, the determinants and disclosure with the purpose of highlighting the religious main aspect of the concept of social responsibility in the Islamic finance sector (Dusuki, 2006; Mohammed, 2007; Yusuf and Bahari, 2011). Moreover, the latest studies on CSR involved by Islamic banking corporations enhanced the research on customer perception regarding the CSR aspect (Hamdan, 2014; Goby and Nickerson, 2016; Aribi and Arun, 2015) and its principles in terms of practicability, measuring its outcomes (Samina, 2012; Sairally, 2013). The issue of CSR in Islamic banking could make an impact on the interest of the International Accounting and Auditing Organisation for Islamic Finance Institutions (AAOIFI) also included other governance standards which in 2010 developed one on CSR for example standard No. 7 'CSR conduct and discloser for Islamic corporations' (AAOIFI, 2010). This standard is argued that CSR involves several activities from IFI (Islamic Financial Institutions) to fulfil each factor. First, religion, it emphasises the overarching obligation of IFIs to follow Shariah regulations for dealings and operations. Second, legal, it includes respecting and obeying the laws and regulations of the nation of operation. Third, ethics, it relates to respecting the mass of societal, religious and customary regulations that are not codified in law. Fourth, economic, it refers to Islamic financial institutions being financially viable, efficient and profitable. Fifth, discretionary, it relates to the expectation from stakeholders which IFIs will perform a social role in adopting the Islamic system over and above the religious, legal, economic and ethical responsibilities. Therefore, these factors are responsibilities as financial intermediaries

for persons and society or community (AAOIFI, 2010). Furthermore, the guidelines regarding CSR indicated in Standard 7 of the AAOIFI are subdivided into two categories.

Mandatory Conduct	Recommended Conduct
Policy for screening clients	Policy for qard hasan
Policy for responsible dealing with clients	Policy for reduction of adverse impact on environment
Policy for earnings and expenditure prohibited by sharia	Policy for social-, development- and environment-based investment quotas
Policy for employee welfare	Policy for par excellence customer service
Policy for <i>zakāh</i>	Policy for micro and small business and social savings and investments
	Policy for charitable activities
	Policy for <i>waqf</i> management

Table 2. 2: Structure of CSR according to Auditing Organisation for Islamic Financial Institution (AAOIFI) standard No.7 (AAOIFI, 2010).

The table above shows that there are two aspects of conducting CSR in Islamic banking. Firstly, the mandatory factor, this structure is mainly concerned with the implementation of a set of internal Islamic institution procedures, which includes several aspects such as respect for CSR principles; the safeguarding of the interest issue in the drafting of the contract; supervision of Islamic laws compliance of earnings and investment; the safeguarding of the individual’s welfare and policies explaining the condition for the stabilisation of *Zakah* which is mandatory for Islamic people. Secondly, the recommended issue, it includes some factors, for instance, the purpose of the condition for benefiting from a loan without interest granted for social reasons. The adoption of investment, instrument and operating stage of selection procedures purposed at safeguarding and protecting the environment, customers, micro and small businesses. Policies purposed at setting up charity-oriented social activities and the regulation of endowment management purposed to reinforce the corporation’s commitment to integrating CSR principles into the management system.

Service Quality

Wong and Zhou (2006) stated that service quality is an evaluation of service that is reflected in consumer perceptions and service degree is being maintained through reliability, responsiveness, assurance and customer needs. In terms of the business field, service quality has played a significant role in contributing to the corporation’s competitiveness worldwide. Moreover, it is also related to the feeling of customers to compare the service expected to what is actually received after they purchase a product or service (Lovelock and Wright, 2002). They could feel how satisfied they were with service delivery and outcomes, also related to the quality. Nevertheless, service quality and customer satisfaction are different concepts in the marketing field. In addition, service is living labour, which is provided to understand a customer’s particular needs. It has higher added value than a simple goods sales market, especially in terms of the banking sector. According

to Xu (2011) Service is defined as intangible, but customers can feel the service. Customers do not see service, but they can see the tools, equipment, employees, data, other customers, and the place where services are provided and the voice of service delivered (Karatepe, 2011). Moreover, all these tangibles have a direct impact on clients' purchases and use of the banking service industry. If the intangible service is displayed in a tangible way and conveys the connotation of the company and its products, it could stimulate clients' desire to re-buy and use it.

Quality of services is the degree of features that match the target group of customers. Service is defined as the action or activity which can be offered from one party to another for fulfilling specific needs or demands (Bruhn et al, 2008). Services are intangible in nature and management has to make more efforts to satisfy customers. According to Wong and Zhou (2006), Service quality is an evaluation of services that reflect in consumer perceptions and services degree is being maintained through reliability, responsiveness, assurance, and customer needs.

Service quality is an area which concerns the way to deliver the services in such a way that matches customer expectations. High-quality service is efficient enough to delight customers and achieve a higher level of satisfaction (Zaibaf et al, 2012). Based on the assessment of service quality using gap analysis, the market can quickly get an idea to develop effective marketing strategies that meet customers' demands and improve the chances of customer satisfaction.

Figure 2. 4: SERVQUAL Model (Sharma and Jhamb, 2017).

In the user-based approach, the quality factor relates to related satisfaction issues: the best quality defines the best satisfaction of clients' preferences (Yarimoglu, 2014). Corporations have realised that service quality affects sustainable and competitive benefits. Rauch et al (2015) stated that to implement a comprehensive corporation evaluation, and the management system has to analyse the performance factor with the customers' expectations and with the performance of other corporations in the same industry. In figure 2.1, it indicates in the organisation process service quality is clearly explained as to how the corporation meets or exceeds customer expectations and it leads to word-of-mouth communications between clients to other people. In addition, Mauri et al (2013) explained that service quality is "a multidimensional concept, assessed and perceived by clients. There are five main instruments of service quality concept: tangibility, reliability, responsiveness, empathy and assurance. Moreover, Siddiqi (2011) argues that the service quality concept is an appropriate assessment tool to measure service quality perception.

- Empathy

Clients are required to feel that they are made a priority by the corporation providing service. Empathy is defined as caring, paying personal attention, and providing the best service to clients (Parasuaraman et al, 1994). The fundamental factor of empathy is conveying the feeling that the consumer is special and unique.

Furthermore, the research of quantitative has identified SERVEQUAL concept dimensions that have used security, credibility and access to measure empathy.

- Responsive

According to Parasuraman et al (1994) the responsive aspect is defined as willing staff who involves telling clients exactly when things will be done, giving the customers undivided attention, promoting service, and responding in accordance with the requested customers' need. Moreover, Zeithaml and Berry (1988) highlighted that responsiveness defines the willingness to support the client and provide prompt service. Keeping clients waiting, particularly for no apparent reason, builds unnecessary negative perceptions of quality. This factor enhances recovery quickly and cares for professionalism to build a great perception of quality.

- Reliable

According to Parasuraman et al (1994) reliability in service quality defines a corporation performing a service correctly the first time. Furthermore, it indicates that corporations strive to fulfil promises and pay attention to the results. This factor also is the first concept of the SERVEQUAL model. In addition, Lam (29) indicated this factor as first in the dimension of the service quality aspect. This factor is related to the company providing prompt service to the clients and providing accurate information to the customers.

- Assurance

Assurance is defined as the staff 'courtesy knowledge and capacity to transfer confidence and trust to clients (1994). This factor is defined as keeping clients informed in the customers' native language and listening to them, regardless of customers' education level, age and nationality (Pakurar et al, 2019). Moreover, Parasuraman et al (1994) argued that assurance defines the attitude of the staff and their behaviour and the employees' ability to provide confidential, friendly, courteous and competent service to the customers.

- Tangible

Parasuraman et al (1994) explained that tangibles are physical facilities which offered to the customers to enjoy the service such as personnel, equipment and communications materials. It is the physical image of a corporation toward the service for clients to assess quality. Tangibles are associated with physical facilities, tools, and machines applied in order to support the service from the company, it also includes offering the service, for example, statements, cards (debit and credit), the efficiency of transactions and speed. There are some privileges of tangible for instance, external appearance, counters in the bank, opening hours, overdraft facilities and transaction efficiency. Moreover, Parasuraman et al (1988) argued that this factor has a crucial issue as empathy.

Furthermore, in the banking industry, service quality is considered the utmost crucial aspect and is a vital competitive weapon for high competition in the marketplace with typically undifferentiated goods

(Choudhury, 2013; Karatepe, 2011; Hossain and Leo, 2009). Portela and Thanassolis (2005) state that the strategy for long-term survival of bank branches mostly depends on the service quality levels they provide to customers. Thus, financial institutions should consider more service quality aspect as a vital competitive strategy (Hossain and Leo, 2009) and imperatively work on this area.

Customer Satisfaction

Customer satisfaction is a key driving factor in consumer loyalty. What consumers expect and what they gain are more important to increase consumer satisfaction. It is a fact that satisfied consumer is more likely to be loyal towards company services. However, Bougoure and Lee (2009) stated that satisfied consumers may not be guaranteed to make them loyal to a specific brand. Hence, it is observed in many organizations that customers are being loyal and satisfied with company services due to their engagement with the consumer loyalty program.

Customer satisfaction also has a close link with customer loyalty. According to Setiowati and Putri (2012), the only satisfied customer can be considered loyal to a business because their experiences and tastes force them to engage with products and services. Satisfied customers give more opportunities for businesses to serve for a more extended time period. A branded product or service ensures customers feel satisfied and being loyal (Novikov and Novikov, 2013). Hence it can be said that there is close integration with corporate image, customer satisfaction, and customer loyalty. In the case of banking services, customers can be satisfied only when they receive quality uninterrupted service, and they have that it will meet their satisfaction level because it incorporates better quality, prices stability and easy availability of the goods.

Schiffman and Kanuk (2007) defined satisfaction as a degree of expectation fulfilment of an individual. It is also defined as an expression of pleasure which results in service outcomes in relation to the expectations and consumer perception. If service performance falls from the expectation, it becomes unsatisfactory for consumers and adversely perceived by consumers. Customer loyalty is the deep help commitment of a consumer towards a specific product or service, or brand to use it for a longer time by repetition of purchase. Consumer buying behaviour is one of the crucial factors for managing loyalty. The brand image of products or services is also essential to promote customers towards specific kinds of products or services. Positive behaviour is also helpful to increase referral of the product to others and associates, which improves the market share of the products or services. The banking services are used after subscription, whereas the consumer has yet to have any prior intention to subscribe to the brand image. According to Stewart, (2017) loyal customers are always ready to re-buy a product or service until they face any major problem with its functional experience.

Figure 2. 5: Customer Satisfaction Framework (Mohammed et al, 2014).

Figure 2.5 shows that there are several processes to obtain customer satisfaction and, in the end, it might lead to a long-term relationship between a corporation and customers also increase the market share (Mohammed et al, 2014). In addition, according to (Zeithaml and Bitner, 2003) there is a significant factor influencing customer satisfaction, it is determined by several factors, including perceptions of service and goods quality and price. Other components, such as personal and situational issues, might influence customer satisfaction from the customers. However, perceived service quality is a crucial factor in customer satisfaction (Zeithaml et al, 2006). Furthermore, some studies (Szymanski and Henard, 2001) have highlighted that customer satisfaction is also measured by other components, for instance, customer-specific and situational aspects. The literature on customer satisfaction, especially in the service industry, in general, and the banking industry, in particular, is divided into different factors interpreting this variable. The factors, it could gain from various external and internal aspects for reaching the level of customer satisfaction. It is defined as a number of clients whose experiences (ratings) exceed the explicit goals of service satisfaction (Rajagopal and Velmurugan, 2016). In order to gain high customer satisfaction in the bank service, a company requires to adopt the most suitable strategy for their clients rather than implementing an approach which is less costly (Dayang and Francine, 2009).

Customers Outcomes Variables

Brand Experience

It is crucial for customers to have brand experience in marketing practice. This brand experience aspect leads to positive consumer-brand relationships, especially for long-term relationships. The brand experience model was driven by the cognitive science, philosophy and management fields and is being defined as “sensations, feelings, cognitions, and behavioural response evoked by brand-related stimuli which is part of a brand’s design and identity, packaging, communications and environments (Brakus et al, 2009). Moreover, there are several researchers who understood the brand experience concept relating to the combination of consumption, goods, service, and shopping experience sourced from the client-brand interaction (Brakus et al, 2009; Khan and Rahman, 2015). It is also related to, but different from the affective, evaluative, and associative brand constructs, including brand involvement, brand attachment, brand personality and brand attitudes (Brakus et al, 2009). Nysveen et al (2013) highlighted that this has two different perspectives which are from the clients’ and non-clients’ experiences and is realised as a broad experiential construct. In addition, Alloza (2008) argues that it defines the clients’ perception of the brand formed during interaction with a specific brand. Therefore, some studies have shown that brand experiences are evoked during the entirety of the client buying decision process, involving the information search, buying, receiving and consumption of goods and services (Arnould et al, 2002; Schmitt, 1999; Schmitt and Rogers, 2008). In addition, brand experience has a long-lasting impression on consumer sense as compared to traditional goods’ features or benefits (Chase and Dasu, 2014).

Brand experience is related to the sensory dimension. It refers to the excitement and aesthetic pleasure that occurs when a client perceives a brand through the five senses such as hear, vision, smell, taste and touch (Khan and Rahman, 2016). Furthermore, these sensory factors arise in response to mechanical clues. According to Berry and Carbone (2007) the mechanic clue contains several factors toward the brand experience from the customers’ perspective for example building design, furnishing, equipment, colour, textures, sounds, smell, displays, etc. They also argued that the affective dimension focuses on client’s inner feeling and emotion generated through humanistic clues, humanistic clues turn up in response to behaviour and appearance of the service provider. The behavioural dimension defines the prior experience generated through humanistic and functional clues of the brand, and functional clues denote the technical quality of an offering (Berry and Carbone, 2007). The cognitive dimension is all regarding the problem-solving (or creative usage) thought that a brand puts forward through the goods or services (Khan and Rahman, 2016).

According to Rowley (2004) branding in a digital age could be defined by two factors such as organisational strategy and brand experience. Brakus et al 2008 and Holbrook (2000) argued that the experience occurred in two settings: directly which is shopping, purchasing, and consuming the goods, and indirectly, in the case

of clients exposed to advertising and marketing communication. The brand experience could enhance a top-of-mind awareness, recall and attitudes. This is because the experience actively engages the customers and prompts them to interact with the specific brand. In addition, integrating the more traditional marketing tool of having better service quality and customer satisfaction with an interactive brand experience is expected to result in the combined advantages of both marketing communication strategies, especially for long-term relationships. Therefore, brand experience is one of the crucial factors of marketing in the business to maintain or remember the customers for having an excellent experience regarding the specific brand.

Word of Mouth

Word of mouth is one of the vital factors in the marketing aspect especially for businesses because it could lead to gaining more customers. The clients might have their expectations shaped, in part by WOM communications regarding the service industry. According to Mekonnen (2015) this factor could be implemented effectively, it relates to communication from other sources than the service provider itself. Relatives, colleagues and family are the fundamental sources of information in the communication of service. Moreover, the media factor also might be a source of such communication as many other corporations such as inspection and audit agencies also the central government. Communication is one of the crucial factors in the marketing aspect. It is the process of conveying a message from someone to another individual or group to advise or to change feelings, mentalities, conduct and both legitimately or in a roundabout way (media) (Nurhadi and Kurniawan, 2017). In addition, Melewar et al (2017) argued that it considers an assortment of messages from official and informal sources through a decent variety of media, where corporations could move the personalities to different crowds.

Word of Mouth is one of the parts of communication, which is an informal aspect between clients regarding suppliers or the characteristics of the goods or services. WOM has defined two different factors, it could be positive or negative perspectives by expected customers prior to their experience toward the goods or service (Shi et al, 2016). The clients have various motives in terms of WOM. Villanueva et al (2008) highlighted that through the WOM concept, a corporation's client lifetime value could impact on increasing nearly twice more as a company which is implementing other concepts of the marketing communication systems. Moreover, WOM provides a 'two-way information exchange,' which allows a more significant effect on personals at the stage of persuasion. In the customer behaviour field, WOM has been indicated to influence the clients' buying decision-making process and increase the profitability of sales in the firms (Augusto and Torres, 2018; Godes and Mayzlin, 2004). Therefore, WOM has played a crucial factor in the communication system and also impacts the firm's income.

WOM is also defined as a social process which encourages customers to obtain motivation in terms of a sense of obligation, a desire to assist other people, and the pleasure of communicating with other customers

regarding the goods or services (Purwanto et al, 2020). Furthermore, from the customers' perspective, it could be affected for a recommendation system to persuade other customers regarding new goods which leads to building trust in future transactions (Hajli et al, 2014). There are several studies indicated in their research that have obtained a positive impact on the WOM factor (Shankar et al, 2020; Van Tonder et al, 2018). The vital of WOM is excellently impacted in the service context because of its inherent intangibility and experiential nature (De Matos and Rossi, 2008). In addition, the studies have been shown on the impact (Jan et al, 2013; Velazquez and Molina, 2015) and eventually on the changes which arise from interpersonal communication on attitude or behavioural intention (Gilly et al, 1998).

Service Quality and Brand Experience

The conceptualisation of service quality and brand experience are of high scientific and practical relevance, enhancing two critical aspects determinants for the clients' evaluation process and in the long-term perspective for the success of corporation in the current era of the business market to emphasise brand-dominated and experience-seeking business market (Meis, 2018).

Figure 2. 6: The Relationship between Brand Experience and Customer Perceived Service Quality (Meis, 2018).

It is believed that the past experience of customers with a specific brand has the ability to persuade customers' expectations of service or offering provided by the brand (Zeithaml et al, 1990). It is compulsory to draw the attention of customers to the possible interrelationship between customer perceived service quality and the prior brand experience aspect. The picture above illustrates that "contemporary service quality is considerably focused on favourable customer experiences" (Enquist et al, 2007). Thus, highlighting the topicality of the interconnectedness of these two meaningful systems. Moreover, enhancing "a focus on customer experience

instead of service alone will encourage brand managers to understand the value which clients derive from their offer more profound and substantial manner and in this sense, reinforce the traditional role of brands as fundamental to value creation in competitive markets (Klaus and Maklan, 2007).

Conceptual Framework

Theory in any piece of study has played a significant role by shaping the understanding of the relationship which exists between concepts such as practice and the reason why it exists in the research aspect (Downing, 1996; Blaikie, 2010). Bryaman and Bell (2015) stated that theory assists in understanding of the most appropriate framework and the reason for the existence of the research. The framework of the study, which includes certain philosophies is a needed input in the study because it opens up theories for understanding how to appropriate the research to the social field, this aspect mainly if the research paradigm is that of pragmatism (positivism), that is based on deductive reasoning. Moreover, the theory in the research, it supports descriptions of a phenomenon happening and why it occurs. Inkeles (1964) argued that the theory of the research is defined as “a heuristic device for organising what we know, or think we know, at a specific time regarding some more or less explicitly posed questions or issues”. Nevertheless, Ibrahim (2014) and Kathri (2003) highlighted that there might be several instances when doing study work where one established theory might not be appropriate or adequate well to explain the phenomena of the research. It could be triggered by a phenomenon that includes or involves two or more theories implemented in the study.

There are several steps to consider for setting up or implementing the relevant concept for the study which is mainly assisting the model of the theory of research (Velde et al, 2004). According to Creswell (2014) it is required that in the beginning, theories are collected to explore the questions in research in order to answer the main research questions, which involves testing theory that provides an explanation adopted to answer the questions of research. The theory is concluded with a general assertion implemented which is structured with a focus on a concept of reality (Velde et al, 2004). Moreover, theories appear in quantitative research as arguments, justifications or a diagram, and discussions with the sole aim of supporting predicting or explaining variations in aspects of reality in the study that exists in the real world. In addition, Creswell (2014) explains that in quantitative research, some historical precedent exists for viewing a theory as a scientific prediction or explanation for what the researcher expects to find. In this particular research, there are several fundamental concepts of the theory which have been implemented empirically to underpin project marketing research which includes Islamic banking adoption, Corporate Social Responsibility, Service Quality, Customer Satisfaction, Brand Experience and Word-of-Mouth aspects

Figure 2. 7: The Conceptual Framework.

Hypotheses Development

Customers Perception

According to Dusuki and Abdullah (2007) client perception regarding a bank's conformance with Islamic banking laws system serves as one of the crucial aspects in patronising Islamic banking. However, conforming to Islamic banking is not the only reason identified for patronising an Islamic financial institution. There have been studies investigating the factors which can possibly contribute toward clients patronising the Islamic financial system. There are several factors included, such as relative price, convenience, efficient service, cost or benefit, confidentiality, bank's reputation and image, and these factors contribute to customer patronising behaviour (Erol and El-Bdour, 1989; Gait and Worthington, 2008). Nevertheless, the possibility of a causal relationship between religious attitudes and other aspects contributing to patronising an Islamic financial is yet to be investigated. Casual relations are probably the fundamental factor which affects customers in terms of service quality and overall satisfaction factor with the service from an Islamic bank (Mohsin and Aftab, 2013). In addition, there are several studies found that a general attitude toward a salient object could generate a similar attitude toward broader, related objects, in fact, it referred to as the "halo

effect” (Beckhvit and Lehman, 1975; Holbrook, 1983; Kardes et al, 2004). Therefore, it is believed that more clients positively evaluate a bank’s commitment to conform to the Islamic Financial institution, which is supported by the trait issue influencing other related traits, attitudes and or beliefs relevant to patronising the Islamic bank.

Several existing studies found that customer satisfaction is majorly influenced the convenience, awareness, relative advantages, reputation and responsiveness (Abdul and Moydheen,2015; Elavarasi, 2014; Prema, 2013; Safeenaet et al, 2012; Haris, 2007; Sayar and Wolfe, 2007; Black et al, 2011). In addition, in the banking sector, Dhurup et al (2014) found that different aspects of customers’ perception have a positive significant effect on the satisfaction factor in this industry. Customers’ perception of Islamic banking in Jordan directly link to customer satisfaction (Anouze et al, 2019). Moreover, there is a significant effect between clients’ perception and customer satisfaction with the banking industry in a recent study (Mahajan, 2021).

H1: Customers Perception of Islamic Banking has a significant positive effect on Customer Satisfaction.

Several scholars mentioned experiential concepts in marketing literature known as customer experience (Gentile et al, 2007), brand experience (Brakus et al, 2009; Beckman, 2013) and destination brand experience (Barnes et al, 2014). All these scholars indicate an association between experience and customer behaviour. It is believed that customers consider the most to have an excellent experience with the banking service that they use for the daily life of transactions in the finance system. Therefore, this current study highlights the impact on customers overall, especially Generation Z client perception of Islamic banking satisfaction factor, Brand Experience and WoM.

H2: Customers Perception of Islamic Banking has a significant positive effect on Brand Experience.

The importance of the WoM factor in shaping customers’ attitudes and buying decisions led many studies to investigate within various industries. Several researchers found that have a stronger relationship between customers perception (Silverman, 2001; Aghadie et al, 201; Lim and Beatty, 2005; Mir, 2011; Chen et al, 2011). Previous scholars have investigated the significant effect of customers attitudes on WoM (Soderlund and Rosengren, 2007; Bone, 2005). However, some studies also found that dissatisfaction results in negative WoM (Richins, 1983). Matos and Rossi (2008) argued that the situation is from a different perspective. Moreover, corporations should spend time-consuming, and much money to get rid of negative WoM due to its ability to reduce the business reputation of the products and services (Hart et al, 1990) and its effect is stronger than positive WoM (Chevalier and Mazlin, 2006; Charlett et al, 1995).

H3: Customers Perception has a significant positive effect on WoM.

Corporate Social Responsibility

Corporate social responsibility (CSR) is one of the vital strategies in the business industry and a source of competitive benefits. Studies have found a link between CSR initiatives and customer satisfaction. Several studies found that CSR activities enhance the corporation's effectiveness on clients-related the customers' perspective for instance customer satisfaction factor (Carvalho et al, 2010; He and Li, 2011; Luo and Bhattacharya, 2006). Furthermore, the relationship between the CSR system and customer satisfaction factor is explained based on different streams. CSR aspect is not only considered the economic value of consumption but also taken into account perceived value and customer knowledge is acknowledged as a possible antecedent of the customer satisfaction aspect (Fornell et al, 1996; Jayachandran et al, 2005). CSR has played an excellent role in the firm because it impacts adding value and improving customer knowledge, promoting customer satisfaction.

H4: CSR has a significant positive effect on Customer Satisfaction with Islamic Banking.

CSR context as a brand value is desirable in order to gain a positive brand experience with clients (Nieto, 2009). CSR aspect in a brand perspective conducts several activities in terms of environmental initiatives, social welfare activities, sustainable supply and opening a new school. Several scholars involving CSR on brand experience, for example, Kumar and Chrisrodoulopoulu (2014) highlighted that a crucial factor of CSR is the branded aspect which aids the corporation's branding. It also affects the competitive advantage of the business. In addition, according to Nieto (2009) the impact of CSR on business clients has given a positive experience with the specific firm or brand.

H5: CSR has a significant positive effect on Brand Experience.

CSR also has a positive effect on WoM which guides the customer's willingness to discuss a corporation (Bhattacharya and Sen, 2004; Walsh and Bartikowaski, 2013). Clients' response regarding CSR initiatives reveals corporation effects on cognition and behaviour (identification, attitudes and belief) and behavioural outcomes such as WoM, patronage and loyalty (Karem Kolkalah et al, 2013; Martinez and del Bosque, 2013). Moreover, Mandhachitara and Poolthong (2011) found out that CSR has a vital association with the attitudinal loyalty of bank clients by implementing positive WoM, recommending the service to other people and defending the service provider's virtues.

H6: CSR has a significant positive effect on WoM.

Service Quality

Parasuraman et al (1988) identified service quality and customer satisfaction as "service quality is a global judgment or attitude, relating to the superiority of the service, whereas satisfaction is related to a specific transaction". There is a positive relationship between the two variables (Beerli et al, 2004). Numerous scholars highlighted that service quality is the antecedent of customer satisfaction (Bedi, 2010; Kasim and

Abdullah, 2010; Naeem and Saif, 2009; Balaji, 2009). Moreover, A set of service quality determinants are predominated by “satisfiers” for example attentiveness, responsiveness, care and friendliness. However, several factors are predominated by “dissatisfiers” for instance integrity, responsiveness, reliability, availability and functionality (Johnston, 1995). In subsequence, He argued that it is more crucial to ensure the dissatisfiers issue is dealt with before the satisfiers factor. Moreover, Johnson et al (2008) highlighted the importance of ascertaining the criteria implemented by clients to evaluate banking services toward maintaining and expanding their customer base.

H7: Service Quality has a significant positive effect on Customer Satisfaction with Islamic Banking.

An understanding of the relationship between service quality and brand experience is a crucial issue for a manager in a firm because it assists the level of appeal which will influence target clients’ perception of brand personality and also the brand experience aspect (Keng et al, 2013). The marketplace has consistently improved over the years, especially in a new era which encourages corporations to have high competition from selling and promoting goods and services to selling and enticing customers through experiences (Joy and Sherry, 2003). Moreover, Brakus et al (2009) point out that the brand experience is conceptualisation as a subjective, internal consumer response (sensation, feeling and cognition) and a behavioural response evoked by brand-related stimuli for example colour, shapes, design, slogan etc which are part of a brand’s design in terms of the identity, communication, packaging and environment.

Service quality is a crucial issue, especially in the banking sector. Focusing on Generation Z is lately considered in every banking sector because they are a vast market and the option for a long-term relationship. It could make potential leaders, consumers and users with excellent purchasing power which will shape the social, economic and political landscape in the near future. Therefore, regardless of numerous studies shown that affirm the positive relationship between service quality and brand experience, this research tries to prove that Generation Z of Al Rayan Bank has the power to change the market and the future of entrepreneurial companies.

H8: Service Quality has a significant positive effect on Brand Experience.

The relationship between service quality and WOM has been extensively researched in past studies. However there needs to be more study related to the effect which service quality dimension has on the WOM factor. In addition, in more specific research, Macintosh (2007) suggested that the relationship of business travellers with their travel agent indicated that relationship quality affects overall clients’ satisfaction with the corporation and having positive word-of-mouth. He also explained relationship quality as the client’s assessment of the interpersonal relationship with the contact person. Furthermore, according to Arasli et al (2005) in their research, it shows the impact of service quality perception of Greek Cypriot bank customers, on overall satisfaction from their bank service and positive WOM.

In line with the above discussion, it becomes clear the relationship between service quality to customer satisfaction, brand experience and WOM. Therefore, based on the above theoretical arguments, the present research infers that service quality influences customer satisfaction, brand experience and the WOM aspect.

H9: Service Quality has a significant positive effect on WoM.

Customer Satisfaction

The literature on customer satisfaction could be divided into two varieties: research on the relative importance of the experience aspect (Andersson and Mossberg, 2004) and research on the effect of customer satisfaction and behavioural intentions (Liu and Jang, 2009). Analysing customers' meal experience in luxury hotel restaurants, Wu and Liang (2009) found that the restaurant environment and customers' interaction with restaurant employees and other clients had a significant effect, either directly or indirectly on customer satisfaction. Brakus et al (2009) highlighted research to develop a scale to measure brand experience and to investigate the impact of brand experience on customer satisfaction as well as loyalty and found that the brand experience factor had a positive effect on customer satisfaction and loyalty either directly or indirectly through brand personality. Moreover, Nysveen et al (2013) found that brand experience had a significant influence on brand personality, brand satisfaction and brand loyalty.

Some related research on brand experience has pointed out the positive effect of this construct on client outcomes. Prentice et al (2019) found that in the airline sector examined the effect of clients-based factors, particularly in the brand experience and brand love factor, and corporations based on the factor of customer engagement and revealed that customer-based factors had a significant influence on customer engagement. In particular, brand experience had direct and indirect influences on customer engagement. Shanti et al (2019) examined the impact of the brand experience aspect, it had a significant effect on brand satisfaction and brand love but not on brand loyalty. In a general statement of the study, customer satisfaction exerts a significant effect on brand experience.

H10: Customer Satisfaction with Islamic Banking has a significant positive effect on Brand Experience.

Furthermore, there are several studies have shown the relationship between satisfaction factors and the desire to recommend (Parasuraman et al, 1988; File et al, 1994; Shemwell, 1998; Soderlund, 1998; Sivadas and Baker-Prewitt, 2000; Henning-Thurau et al, 2002). More specifically, as Ennew et al (2000) highlight, consideration of clients' motives for involving in the WOM concept has tended to examine the vital customer satisfaction factor as a determinant of the positive WOM aspect. In addition, the effect of clients' satisfaction on WOM has been playing a crucial aspect, as clients are hoping for better quality from services and products in the banking industry (Manyanga et al, 2022). According to Sidiqqi (2011) implied that satisfaction issues in the banking sector are a vital factor in the well-competitive sector. Due to the ability to keep a long-standing

connection with its clients worthwhile (Widana et al, 2015). In addition, the studies found that there is a positive link between customer satisfaction and WoM in the banking industry (Casalo et al, 2008; Manyanga et al, 2022; Siddiqi, 2011; Widana et al, 2015; Al-Msallam,2015).

H11: Customer Satisfaction has a significant positive effect on WoM towards Islamic banking services.

Mediating factors

Customer satisfaction enables companies to increase sales revenue and lead to achieving a competitive edge over other competitors (Lewin, 2009). Customer satisfaction originates from the recognition that companies have to interact with changing environments consistent with customer behaviour to maintain the longevity and stability of corporations in the market competition (Smith et al, 1996). Moreover, Parasuraman et al (1985) argued that the high quality of service is positively related to the customer satisfaction factor. Palmer et al (2005) highlighted that customer satisfaction is the primary key in the bank sector. The firms should know whether the customers are satisfied with the service or providing high-quality service. Consequently, service quality and customer satisfaction contribute to the success and continuity of the business (Sadowski, 2017). Furthermore, several studies found that customer satisfaction could correctly mediate the relationship between customer perception and branding factors. These findings confirm the research (Hamouda, 2019; Chen and Lin, 2019; Chuah et al, 2017; Hasan et al, 2020, Hew et al, 2016).

CSR affects behavioural outcomes through direct or mediated paths and customer satisfaction is considered an evaluative outcome of the CSR aspect (Brown and Dacin, 1997; Luo and Bhattacharaya, 2006). This aspect also may directly and indirectly affect the company's performance through various mediating sectors (Lee and Heo, 2009). Customer satisfaction could be linked to that mediating system between CSR and brand experience. The previous study has indicated that customer satisfaction partially mediates the relationship between CSR and company market value (Luo and Bhattacharaya, 2006). According to Hsu (2012) the variable of satisfaction is partially mediating between the CSR and the branding sector. Moreover, satisfaction is driven by the experience of the customer with the company and the information client has in the form of corporate associations regarding the corporation (Davies et al, 2012). In addition, Kim et al (2015) stated that positive brand experiences of clients will enhance their trust issues on the brand aspect. Moreover, the company's strong CSR record could lead to enhancement in the level of customer satisfaction which would translate into potential advances like clients-based brand experience.

He and Li (2011) highlighted that CSR is significantly associated with customer satisfaction. Martinez and del Bosque (2013) found that the customer satisfaction factor mediated the association between CSR and loyalty. In addition, marketing studies have implemented customer satisfaction as an assertive variable mediating customer behaviour (Chadha and Kapoor, 2009; Zulganef, 2009).

Al-Hawari and Ward (2006) found the role of customer satisfaction as the mediator in the relationship between service quality and financial performance. Numerous marketing scholars have incorporated satisfaction and behavioural intention as crucial aspects in the theoretical concept and illustrate which service quality leads to satisfaction factor (Bressolles et al, 2015; Chang et al, 2009; Dabholkar, 2000), which in turn, affects behavioural intention to adopt banking service (Chang et al, 2009; Chang and Polonsky, 2012). Moreover, it is believed that from previous scholars indicated that in the service field, especially in the banking sector, service quality has an indirect impact on the customer satisfaction aspect along with the branding factor (Prameka et al, 2016).

The comprehensive understanding of the relationship that links Customer's perception, CSR and service quality to brand experiences requires the modification of the concept to account for a second-order construct measuring the impact of one primary mediating factor, namely customer satisfaction to the dependent variables.

H12: The Role of Customer Satisfaction mediates the effect of Customers Perception on Brand Experience.

H13: The Role of Customer Satisfaction mediates the effect of CSR on Brand Experience.

H14: The Role of Customer Satisfaction mediates the effect of Service Quality on Brand Experience.

There are numerous researchers have found that a variable's a direct effect on satisfaction and an indirect effect on WoM. Customer satisfaction enables corporations to improve their sales and revenue and achieve a competitive edge over competitors which are recommended to other people (Lewin, 2009). Smith et al, (1996) stated that customer satisfaction originates from the recognition that companies have to interact with changing environments consistent with customer behaviour to sustain the longevity and stability of corporations in market competition. Customer's perception is a core aspect of customer gain satisfaction which might contribute to the WoM factor. Moreover, there are several scholars in the literature who analysed the mediating effect of customer satisfaction (Pereira et al, 2016; Wahab et al, 2016; Osman and Sentosa, 2013; Usta and Memis, 2009). Nevertheless, the number of researches regarding whether the mediating effect of customer satisfaction on the customer perception of Islamic banking and WoM is very limited.

Luo and Bhattacharya (2006) investigated the crucial of considering customer satisfaction as an evaluated consequence of CSR which assists in explaining the equivocal link between CSR and corporation's market value. Customer satisfaction is one of the consideration factors for the psychological mechanism through which CSR relates to customer behaviour aspect. In addition, the link between these variables resonates with the notion of customer-corporation identification. (Bhattacharya and Sen; 2003; Lichtenstein et al, 2004). Moreover, Luo and Bhattacharya (2006) argued that clients should be more satisfied when they hold positive CSR associations because it might impact a sense of connection with the corporation. Furthermore, some

studies highlighted there is a link states CSR influences behavioural outcomes and customer-specific knowledge such as WoM through multiple paths, whether directly or mediated by customer satisfaction (Sen and Bhattacharya, 2001; Gardberg and Formbrun, 2006; Dutton et al, 1994).

Several scholars found that corporate ability which includes the service quality aspect, may affect WoM behaviour directly and indirectly via satisfaction (Bloemer et al, 1999; Gupta and Pirsch, 2008; Reimann et al, 2008; Rust et al, 1995), it indicated that customer satisfaction partially mediates the relationship between corporate ability and behavioural outcomes. Moreover, partial mediation exists when an exogenous variable such as service quality, relates both effects directly and indirectly through the satisfaction of customers to an endogenous variable like WoM (Baron and Kenny, 1986). It is believed that a convincing quality perception of a service provider should prompt recommendations from customers to other people when they feel satisfied with the service. Therefore, the effect of service quality on the outcomes obtains amplified by a high level of customer satisfaction.

H15: The Role of Customer Satisfaction mediates the effect of Customers Perception on WoM.

H16: The Role of Customer Satisfaction mediates the effect of CSR on WoM.

H17: The Role of Customer Satisfaction mediates the effect of Service Quality on WoM.

The Summary of Literature Review

This chapter captured the literature review of the fundamental theory of the research which included basic information on marketing, customer behaviour, Islamic banking, Islamic banking customers' perception of Islamic Banking, CSR, service quality, customer satisfaction, brand experience and WOM. In the process, numerous underlying casual relationships are extracted and integrated with a conceptual model framework. This chapter is postulated in an attempt to advance a scholarly understanding of how the consumer of Generation Z perspectives toward Islamic banking started adopting and becoming satisfied with the service of AL Rayan Bank in the UK. Moreover, this chapter also included a synthesis of the literature review, proposing a series of testable hypotheses extracted from these insights. The conceptual framework, providing an integrated view of contracts the relationship detail. In addition, the research model was introduced and the various variables were defined.

The following chapter focuses attention on the research methodology aspect for the empirical phases of the research. In this respect, the focal point of the implemented research will be demarcated and the procedures for data collection and the tools for data analysis will be profiled.

CHAPTER III

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Introduction

This chapter includes a detailed account of methods and techniques applied to contribute to collecting data and answering the research questions and objectives. In addition, explain why various strategic decisions are taken in the development of the research. This chapter also includes how the data analysis is conducted.

The first section of this chapter considers the macro-level research design and philosophy, incorporating aspects relating to the time horizon, research approach and orientation of the research. It also, explains the sequential phases in compiling this study, namely the pilot, main and validation research. This study is followed by consideration of the target population, taking demographic. Furthermore, the construction of the research instrument and specific data collection procedures are explained. At the last, the technique for analysing the data and generating constructive results is profiled.

A research methodology is a system implemented for evaluating information and answering accurate data information. According to Ghauri and Gronhaug (2005), there are two kinds of methods of analysing quantitative and qualitative in the tool of research methodology. Also, it is a guideline on how the data to put together. Furthermore, Cohen et al (2010) stated that quantitative data refers to primary information which collected and analysed in the numerical system to answer the research. On the other hand, qualitative is based on valid journals, books, websites and magazines that are relevant to the study in which the researcher is conducted.

According to Wilson (2014) A research methodology diagram design called the honeycomb (mesh), it helps the central aspect of the research and sets out a logical pathway to creating a proper research methodology. Moreover, the pathway represented in the honeycomb contains six main aspects: 1. Research Philosophy; 2. Research Approach; 3. Research Strategy; 4. Research Design; 5. Data Collection, and 6. Data Analysis and Interpretation Technique.

Wilson (2014) states that not combining the main aspects of research methodology together such as research philosophy, strategy and design. These are clearly indicated in the honeycomb and at each point, there is a specific stage of the study. The honeycomb leads to a logical pattern of research and it could make a good structure for research.

Figure 3. 1: The Research Honeycomb (Wilson, 2014).

The figure above explains the method which is implemented in this research, and the researcher applies the system to assist the honeycomb model. This method is the guideline for this research study, which will be conducted in the process of collecting data until answering the research objectives of the study. Having remarkable planning is one of the strategies to achieve the main objectives. According to Baker and Edwards (2012), conducting research should be a predefined better plan which could minimise any difficulty during the study. In fact, any research sector should be well prepared to obtain the best result to answer the objective study.

Research Philosophy

According to Collis and Hussey (2003), research philosophy is related to the researcher's strategy to guide the study of how to conduct and it also helps to derive from philosophy and assumptions to develop knowledge. Saunders et al (2012) state that it relates to the "overarching development of knowledge and the nature of that knowledge". In addition, it also points to a number of epistemological positions in this respect, including positivism, phenomenology and realism. The importance of having a clear philosophy cannot be underplayed; among the reasons for this are that it assists in clarifying research design, and dealing with the types of data required (primary or secondary), and choosing the collection strategy and methods of interpretation or analyses. Moreover, having a proper philosophical background supports the researcher to

understand that the research design is well structured; however, if it does not work correctly, it means that these underlying assumptions work in such a way that determines the research strategy and methods (Wilson, 2014). Therefore, the research methodology helps a researcher's inherent knowledge to build a design outside the researcher's own experience that assists in shaping the frontiers of the research being conducted.

Figure 3. 2: Developing Research Philosophy: A Reflective Process (Saunders, 2009).

It is crucial to guide the process that is appropriate for the research to have a better plan, especially in the business and management discipline. According to Saunders et al (2016), there are some big philosophical methods in the study such as positivism, postmodernism, critical realism, pragmatism and interpretivism. Choosing research philosophy, in addition to other aspects of research methodology or paradigms, will be implemented to realistically situate the appropriate contributions of this study in the area of business and social science (Bryman and Bell, 2011). Furthermore, it explains the use of research building blocks, involving five different systems, namely, epistemology, methodology, ontology, methods and sources (Grix, 2002). This section sheds light on the distinct theories which assist in answering the aim of the study in the proper research of social science and the components required to create this are discussed below.

1. Epistemology

According to Blaikie (2004) and Scotland (2012) Epistemology relates to the “theory of knowledge” in the aspects of social entities or social reality or the acquisition of knowledge that is valid. In other words, it refers to how the researcher states to know, the nature of knowledge and how the researcher explains the same to

contribute to knowledge in a specific aspect of research. According to Kivunja and Kuyini (2017) there are several ways the researcher comes to know: empirically, logically, authoritatively, and intuitively. In addition, the natural sources of knowledge are belief, intuition and faith. Moreover, epistemological positions focus on the relationship between the researcher and the study. Bryman and Bell (2011) also explain that epistemology is the best way of inquiring into the required state of knowledge and what is an appropriate assumption generally of study as the nature of knowledge. Therefore, there are three central systems of epistemological perspectives which is generally considered in research, as explained below.

- Positivism

Positivism refers to the objective of nature research. According to Saunders (2009) it relates to the philosophical stance of the natural scientist and entails working with an observable social reality to make a result law-like generalisation. The science and rational assumption involving the researchers' application of accurate and value-free knowledge is generated in the process of the research. It assists in building universal rules from the sample and it leads to implementation for the whole population for example, predicting behaviour or explaining relationships. In addition, positivism is more related to the facts of research rather than opinion. Bryman and Bell (2011) state that involving a similar process to which of a natural science, it could tend to be positivism in the research epistemology. Moreover, positivism is a methodology that requires a highly structured implementation of hypothesis testing and statistical tools- a quantitative approach.

- Interpretivism

Fard (2012) states that interpretivism could be called the constructivism paradigm, which is a paradigm for social phenomenon and understanding of people. It purposes to explore and understand phenomena inductively and it is believed the social event is understood from the individual perspective who is doing an action to be investigated. Moreover, this particular aspect has been considered by the "feeling" researcher to analyse human emotions. According to Rowlands (2005) a qualitative method is implemented to interact with people in order to build a meaningful reality collaboratively. In addition, the aim of interpretivism is to create a new, proper understanding and interpretation of social worlds and contexts (Saunders, 2009).

- Pragmatism

Pragmatism emphasises utilising both methods of interpretivism and positivism. It implements qualitative and quantitative approaches which both methods cannot accommodate individually (Wilson, 2014). This is also a third strand of the epistemology triad. Pragmatism avoids going into an argument on the concept of truth and reality, which focuses on the issue and interest and value and uses different concepts to bring out positive consequences. Furthermore, in the process of the study using this approach, qualitative and quantitative data are collected also it could be in sequence or simultaneously, and analysed or interpreted that

produce the final output of research (Creswell and Clark, 2011). As a result, this system produces single research or at a different stage of the study.

Based on the above considerations, a positivism paradigm was implemented in this study, opting in favour of a casual conceptual framework to guide the adopted concept of the research. In this respect, several hypothesised relationships were statistically tested to obtain specific conclusions in the scientific context of the marketing and business field. Moreover, the presence and intensity of the embedded were explored in an attempt to expand the theory in this specific subject of enquiry.

This research obviously clarifies into the orientation A typology for several reasons, which describes as follows:

- Several hypotheses generated, linked to the embedded relationship between variables in the research framework were developed and empirically tested.
- The aforementioned hypotheses were subjected to statistical procedures, with a reliance on quantitative data methods.
- A considerable sample of participants was generated through a customer survey, with results being extrapolated to the population under consideration.

Figure 3. 3: Research Orientations Framework (Roberts et al, 2011).

2. Ontology

Ontology is defined as “a concept concerned with the existence of and relationship between a different aspect of society for example, social actors, cultural norms and social structures. Ontology issues are concerned with a question pertaining to the aspects of within society” (Jupp, 2006). According to Bryman (2008) it is defined as a philosophical consideration in the study of social ontology that concerns the nature of social entities, it could be objective entities that exist independently from social actors or rather social constructions to build up from the action, perception and interpretation of the individual in society. Moreover, in the concept of ontology, there are two concepts which are subjectivism and objectivism.

Subjectivism emphasises that social phenomena are built from the perceptions and consequent actions of the social researcher which is similar to interpretivism in that the interdependency between the researcher and the respondent has the same purpose. The interpretivism method could be implemented in developing a psychological strategy to lure customers (Chetty, 2016). This system works as social actors interpret a phenomenon to rely on the perception of the world and lead to interaction with the environment. Therefore, it is based on qualitative methodology.

Moreover, objectivism defines the belief that social phenomena are reality external in the social world and out of the reach or monitor of the values held by the researcher (Velde, 2004). In addition, it focuses more on the social world as a set of tangible objects (Kumar, 2014). In this case method, the quantitative or mixed methodology is addressed to apply in a study.

3. Research Values (Axiology)

Axiology is the branch of philosophy that studies judgments regarding value, including both ethics and aesthetics (Chopra, 2005). It is also concerned with the nature of the value of the study being conducted (Wilson, 2014). Moreover, Bidenbach and Jacobsson (2016) state that axiology addressed questions related to what is valuable and considered to be desirable or “good” for humans and society. There are several aspects to approach and understand the value. However, given the limitation of the article, it could explore only a few of them. Implementing axiology skills is the ability to help the researcher articulate facts, a guide to make a decision while conducting a study and collecting data and lead to the findings of research (Kumar, 2014).

Positivism is arguably more objective in the nature field. According to Bryman and Bell (2011) This epistemological system could be explained as the “application of the methods of the natural science to the study of social reality and beyond”. In addition, contend that positivism is taken to entail the following aspects:

1. Only phenomena and hence knowledge confirmed by the senses could genuinely be warranted as knowledge.

2. The aim of theory is to generate hypotheses that could be examined and that will thereby allow explanations of law to be assessed.
3. Knowledge is arrived at through the gathering of facts that provide a basis for laws.
4. Science must be conducted in a way that is objective and value-free.
5. There is a clear difference between science statements and normative statements and a belief that the former is the valid domain of the scientist.

Positivism is often implemented in the instance that consumer research requires to be conducted based on a sample of research subjects and inferences made to a larger group of individuals (Malhotra, 2010). Moreover, this research is firmly grounded in the scholarly literature. Based on the existing conceptual framework, this study augments and implements it in a new context. In doing so, this research considers a strict number of constructs (variables) and the relationship between them. In order to answer the research questions of the research, the researcher implements the positivism model. In this model, understanding phenomena in reality, it must be determined and supported by evidence (Hammersley, 2013). It is clear that the relationship between variables is designed and entirely determined in a way that emphasises the influence of the independent on the dependent variables and events through this process (Cohen et al, 2010).

Research Approach

The research approach is a crucial method to select the appropriate approach to influence the overall findings of the research because it sets the way how the researcher conducts and analyses the specific research. In this process, the researcher has selected the analysis of whether to apply an inductive or deductive in the research discipline. Bryman (2012) argues this process refers to the research to analyse for collecting data, describing and predicting problems in the research method. The deductive approach is a pre-existing theory which is tested based on collecting information. However, an inductive is implemented to develop a concept or theory. In order to achieve the main objectives, implement the inductive method in this research. The relationship between variables will be developed to use data information from the sample. (Davis, 2015). In addition, this approach also leads to the research for describing the connection between methods, data and theories (Ghauri and Gronhaug, 2005).

Figure 3. 4: Approaches of Research (Denzin and Lincoln, 2013).

The figure above shows the inductive method analyses in-depth analysis of phenomena which could assist through the process of a deep literature review to improve the concept of phenomena. Moreover, this method is constructive and supports the discovery of new findings. There are two kinds of central approaches to implement when conducting research: inductive and deductive (Bryman and Bell, 2011). According to Ghauri and Gronhaug (2005) these approaches assist in establishing what is true or false and building a conclusion in the study. In addition, the inductive aspect is predicated on empirical evidence, while the deductive aspect is predicated on logic. Both approaches have different characteristics which classify the field of application in research. The deductive approach is considered best suited to explain the variation and predict social phenomena based on theory triangulation or specific theory (Creswell, 2014). Saunders et al (2009) state the deductive to be an approach where the theory is being tested. According to Bryman and Bell (2011) the process of the deductive approach starts with testing theory, which is defining a hypothesis based up on the theory, whether the theory is confirmed or rejected is determined by the collected empirical data. Furthermore, a hypothesis is implemented in this process as a specific type of research question. It is applied as informed speculation that is being set up to be tested regarding the relationship between two variables or more (Bryman and Bell, 2011).

On the other hand, the Inductive side is where the theory is built (Saunders et al, 2009). This process is the opposite system with a deductive approach which starts with the data collected and is broken down into codes, and later developed into categories and concepts, which leads to generating new theories (Bryman and Bell,

2011). Moreover, it is believed that the theory of a deductive system is the foundation while the outcome of an inductive process is the theory. Bryman and Bell (2011) state that a common strategy within inductivism is; iterative. It defines the data collection and analysis are made constantly and continuously repeated back to each other. In addition, the researcher could always collect further data in order to establish the situation in which the theory is or is not sustained (Bryman and Bell, 2011). Therefore, this approach is observable specific in grounded theory. “the systematic process of establishing a general proposition on the basis or specific facts” (Ghauri and Gronhaug, 2005).

The above approach is necessary in order to fulfil the methodological system in research properly, as espoused by Edmonson and MacNamus (2007). In this particular study, the formulation of the research questions, hypothesis, and relationship among the selected variables to analyse is built on the fundamentals of the theoretical framework which assisted the study.

Research Strategy

Saunders et al (2016) mentioned that research strategy is a core guideline for conducting proper research to achieve the objective of the specific study. This process is choosing the strategy which leads to answering the research question and achieving the study purposes and its assisting objectives. There are two main methods of research strategies implemented in social science research or business fields (Quantitative and Qualitative). The primary distinct both systems is the orientation of quantitative research in terms of theory is deductive in nature, though the testing of theory that deals with experimental examination through the collecting information which is measured and carrying out analysis on the specific data and the resulting impact on understanding the causal relationship between selected variables (Bryman and Bell, 2011). In addition, this method emphasises a value-free environment (no interference), while the qualitative study is oriented in terms of the theory which is inductive in nature with basically theory generation (Bryman and Bell, 2011).

Quantitative Strategy

The quantitative strategy purposes to measure features, count them and use a statistical approach in an attempt to answer what has been conducted in research (McCusker and Gunaydin, 2014). It also generates a commonly implemented result of a study by using numbers rather than words to answer the questions of objectives. Moreover, this strategy intends to collect information which can be generalised and implemented to an expanse population (Ghauri and Grounhaug, 2005). It is believed that the quantitative approach commonly applies tools for example surveys or questionnaires to collect numerical data which leads to applying statistical models such as SPSS, SEM, SAS and others. This strategy is seen as more efficient than qualitative since the data collection and gathering of information is quick and the researcher tends to remain objective to the subject in the matter (McCusker and Gunayadin, 2014). Thus, this strategy has mainly contained the answer of research with numerical information.

This particular study is conducted with the aim to examine and analyse the Generation Z who are using Al Rayan banking in the UK with the process of customers' perception of Islamic banking to enjoy the service, CSR perspective and service quality, which generates becoming satisfied with the service, also from brand experience perspective and share to other people regarding the product and services of Al Rayan Bank in the UK. Since work value is existed widely explored, a quantitative approach is more appropriate consumed to this research and it might be implemented to either accept or reject the existing theory in the business and management sector.

Research Purpose and Design

Research Purpose

In this chapter, the researcher has featured the crucial purposes of the study and should consider the reason for the purposes of the research. According to Saunders et al (2009) a research purpose is divided into three distinct study forms: explanatory, descriptive and exploratory. Those aspects are the fundamental system purposes within business field-related research (Saunders et al, 2009). Firstly, the exploratory aspect of purpose defines implementation in a study where the problem lies under the actual investigation and where the purpose has a qualitative nature (Aaker et al, 2010). Moreover, this method examines a field which previously unknown (Stebbins, 2001). It also explains the research empathise flexibility that could be described as a brief preliminary stage of the study process in regards to the subject (Stebbins, 2001). Therefore, the exploratory purpose constrains to an exploratory purpose conducted with a quantitative approach (Saunders et al, 2009). In addition, this aspect investigates typically the relationship between distinct variables with the purpose of analysing the cause and effect between them.

Secondly, Descriptive research aims are relevant when the purpose of the study is well-defined and clear (Bryman and Bell, 2011). Saunders et al (2009) explain that this method has a purpose as conducted through a quantitative method and uses the numerical system in the research to answer the main objectives. Moreover, this system commonly uses a questionnaire to enquire about the respondent such as when, what, how, who and where (Aaker et al, 2010). Thus, Ghauri and Gronhaug (2005) explain that this method concerns how questionnaires and interviews should be implemented to obtain the study to be successful in the end to answer the purpose of the research. Lastly, explanatory research, it is directed to comprehend the effect of a particular change in existing standard strategies. This approach could be considered as the research that forms a casual association among variables (Singh, 2019). In terms of this study, it is mainly applied explanatory research because the researcher seeks to show the cause of the problem and how a problem or solution leads to another with the primary purpose of explaining the relationship between changing entities (Saunders et al, 2009). Therefore, this study's purpose is to explain how Generation Z customers of Al Rayan Bank in the UK have adopted this bank service.

Research Design

Research design relates to how the researcher examines approach inquiry, explicit research method and underpinning philosophy in the well-prepared study (Creswell, 2009). It is essential to select an appropriate method to guide the research better. Ghauri and Gronhaug (2005) explain this approach assists in building an answer to the investigated research problem. The research design is commonly applied in business subject research with several methods such as case studies, comparative studies, cross-sectional studies, experiments and longitudinal studies (Bryman and Bell, 2011). Firstly, a case study aspect is defined as an in-depth interest in one particular case where the science or researcher investigates new theoretical subjects (Saunders et al, 2009). Secondly, the comparative method is defined as an approach which is applied when a study is conducted on multiple occasions, which makes it possible to compare the different results of research (Bryman and Bell, 2009). In addition, this approach involves along with longitudinal and experimental, it is also the most time-consuming approach when the researcher is conducting the research (Saunders et al, 2009 and Bryman and Bell, 2011). Thirdly, a longitudinal approach is designed to analyse the distinct from one sample over a long period of time, whereas an experiment compares a control group to an experimental group with the purpose of exposing the experimental group (Saunders et al, 2009).

Lastly, cross-sectional relates with a questionnaire is implemented to be able to gather as much as information of study. The researcher applies this system to support examining the relationship between different variables. Furthermore, the information on the variables could be collected more or less at the same time while the researcher is conducting research (Bryman and Bell, 2011). Furthermore, Wilson (2014) explains there are two prominent roles in research design, involving the identification and development of logistical arrangements which support to obtain conducting research. This aspect assists through the process, valid, reliable, accurate and objective in the specific research. Moreover, the research design comprises the methodological paradigm, research method, data collection and analysis (Fisher, 2004).

Data Collection

Data collection is a crucial aspect because it assists to analyse and answer the main objectives of the research. There are two main sources implemented when gathering data to apply as material empirical material: primary and secondary data (Bryman and Bell, 2011). The primary approach is collected by researchers and is applied with the purpose of clarifying a particular problem in the study which is unknown (Bryman and Bell, 2011). It is also implemented when the concerned information does not exist and need to be retrieved directly from clients or organisation in the subject (Currie et al, 2005). Moreover, according to Bryman and Bell (2011), there are several ways to obtain primary data in a study such as a case study, survey, interview and focus group discussion. This system leads to one particular aim which contribute proper information to the study topic (Saunders et al, 2009).

Furthermore, secondary data defines opposite sites rather than primary data that information statistics existed collected for another purpose (Saunders et al, 2009). It is beneficial when the researcher tries to create comparable research because it could make it easier to collect information from both cases and make it easy to understand more depth in research (Ghauri and Gronhaug, 2005). Bryman and Bell (2011) state secondary data could be obtained from both sides external and internal aspects. The external sources include newspapers or websites, whereas the internal information is collected within the organisation itself. It is believed that the secondary data has several benefits rather than primary data which is less time consuming and less expensive, however, the information that existed has been conducted for another aim, and the information collected may not be applicable to a particular study.

In terms of data collection, there are several ways to obtain information that could support the research system such as observation, and this method commonly assists in obtaining qualitative and quantitative information which is mostly from primary data. This approach emphasises the researcher to be more active and observe the particular issue in a purpose-oriented manner, implementing a systematic method identified by recording, watching the object or event also concerning the action taking place or listening attentively to verbal expression in the environment (Kumar, 2014).

This study implements primary data for data collection. It assists the researcher in taking action with the direct customers of Generation Z of Al Rayan banking in the UK with a questionnaire, and it leads to support for fulfilling the purpose and hypothesis of this study. The questionnaire was in English. WhatsApp application on a smartphone was used to approach the respondents. Moreover, the web-based survey information and questionnaire link were shared by the researcher to the participants.

Research Questionnaire Data Collection

This section provides further detailed information regarding the data collection approach which is adopted in this study. The section below explains the primary data collection.

Questionnaire Development

There are several ways to adopt for conducting research to obtain the primary data collection, a questionnaire is one of them. This approach is a crucial strategy of study and it has a strong data collection method of the research with the main function of measurement (Saunders, 2009). This measurement of the study is involved when specifying the questions or designing the questionnaire to generate information which is appropriate to answer the research questions or achieve the research aim and objectives (Wilson, 2014). Moreover, this approach is defined as data collection which is implemented when conducting enquiry, factual or analytical research. This strategy is related to the quantitative approach and it is one of the main strategies of the primary method which is commonly attempting to get first-hand data from the participants of research in a specific field or community (Bell, 2004).

This research adopted the questionnaire method to obtain the main data collection from the participants. It purposes to examine and analyse the Generation Z customers who are using Al Rayan banking system in the UK. It assists this generation in how they adopted the Islamic banking system and their knowledge regarding the corporate social responsibility system of Islamic finance. It also analyses how they are using Al Rayan banking service in terms of service quality that they received and the feeling to obtain satisfaction factor for them. Additionally, the researcher attempts to explore more regarding brand experience from this bank and how this generation speaks up to the public through word of mouth regarding the service in the UK market.

Sampling Technique

When the researcher examines the research problem, there will be two factors that could be implemented: a sample study and a census study (Aaker et al, 2010). Bryman and Bell (2011) argue in a sample research one segment of the population is analysed, whereas the entire population is analysed in a census study. In fact, the practical of adopting the whole population could be not efficient and effective because it impacts many factors such as cost-wide, time-consuming and it might not be ethical. Nevertheless, if the population is small, it is required to have adequate representation which is possible to apply the whole population as a sample of the research (Awodele, 2012). In addition, Creswell (2015) argues the crucial of objective sampling, whilst to make sure which the sample involved provides a remarkable representation of the population.

The method of sampling (selecting part of the population) cannot be understood during the research (Bryman and Bell, 2011). Sample selection (a subset of the whole population) might be based on either probability or non-probability sampling. Sekaran and Bougie (2013) explain that the non-probability sampling is a purposive sampling that has two factors, namely judgement and quota sampling. Dealing with a limited population that could supply the data collected, it could be the best sampling method when using quota sampling and judgment sampling, it also significantly impacts considering the time and cost of collecting information for the study, additionally, obtaining proper representation of a minority aspect in the population (Sekaran and Bougie, 2013).

Due to the impossibility of targeting everyone in the Generation Z population, the researcher of this research has decided to limit the population, which is focusing on Al Rayan customers in the UK which is why this research would focus on the specific sample population of the research. Implementing non-probability sampling is adopted in this research. It is generated by people within the population which have the highest probability of being chosen (Bryman and Bell, 2011). Moreover, there several kinds of non-probability methods which is existed: convenience sample, purposive, expert, case study and quota sample (Vehovar et al, 2016). The researcher was adopted the purposive (judgmental) approach to obtain the main data sampling of the study, the targeting group is Al Rayan banking customers of Generation Z.

There are several techniques in data collection of a study which in general, sampling methods could be divided into two types.

- Probability or random sampling
- Non – probability or non – random sampling

This particular study has emphasised non-random sampling to collect data from participants. To measure the respondents' criteria of the research, the researcher implemented a purposive technique to analyse and examine data collection. Moreover, several characteristics of participants are appropriate to this research, as follows:

1. Participants must come from Generation Z, who was born between 1997-2002.
2. Respondents should be located in the United Kingdom
3. Active customers of Al Rayan Bank in the UK

To conclude, survey participants were drawn from customers of Al Rayan Bank in the UK which focused on Generation Z customers. An online survey is provided by respondents in the study geographical areas of the United Kingdom.

Furthermore, non-probability sampling is a sampling technique which does not provide equal opportunity for each member of the population sample. The snowball technique was also implemented in this research. The method is where the participants recruit future subjects from among their acquaintances. Due to time limitations and less than 100 respondents who participated to fulfil the questionnaire in the first stage while using the purposive technique, the researcher applied the snowball technique to reach the main objective of the research. The researcher visited the young Muslim community in one of the mosques in London, UK, to obtain more participants.

Data Analysis Technique

There are two main aspects that need to be considered when the researcher is collecting data (Bryman and Bell, 2011). Firstly, the approach requires to be consistent with the particular study and secondly, the study is dependent on whether the research is applying a qualitative or quantitative method. In the respect, this research is implemented a quantitative method rather than a qualitative approach because this research is qualified to apply either structured observation, experiment, interview or questionnaire. This study fully adopted the questionnaire method to measure and answer the study's objective. Moreover, this research primarily used this method to examine and analyse the causal relationships and therefore test the sequence of events which drive the Z generation who are using Al Rayan Bank in UK behaviour regarding the Islamic bank service. DeVault (2013) states this is common practice in developing and testing a conceptual model reflecting consumers' notions and latent motives.

Furthermore, in order to understand the properties of primary and secondary data collection analysed in this study, there are several aspects are conducted. Nevertheless, this research fully adopted descriptive statistics and inferential statistics because it is more related to this research. The descriptive method, according to Hair et al, 2007 and Kumar, 2014 explain that this method provides statistical features or characteristics of data existing in research in a systematic approach for example, describing or explaining mean, median, minimum, maximum, mode, skewness, kurtosis etc, these information assist more data on specific set of data of interest. Moreover, Kumar (2014) explains that this method does not involve explaining variations or examining the relationship between variables for instance, between dependent and independent variables. In terms of this research, characteristic median, mode, mean, minimum and maximum values implementing primary and secondary information are an example of the descriptive statistics shown in this research.

Another method is an inferential statistic. This system adopts testing a sample taken from a population to explain the relationship, predicts or estimates the characteristic of a population from a knowledge of the characteristics of only a sample of the population (Tawfik, 2019). This research adopts a sample collected to obtain information from secondary data to explain the specific characteristic which is Generation Z who are using Al Rayan Bank in the UK. Moreover, other approaches such as visual, discourse analysis, grounded theory and content analysis are not implemented in this research because the researcher is not used visual material or recorded interviews. Thus, this is related to the narrative approach. In addition, this method is only appropriate for observations and interview systems.

Ethical Consideration

Ethical consideration is one of the crucial factors of research design for every researcher when conducting the study. Bryman and Bell (2011) argue the importance of considering ethical principles when doing a study. According to Neuman (2013) this aspect assists in a better understanding of what is right and wrong the study. In addition, the information gathered for the study required to be implemented in the way it originally was supposed to (Aaker et al, 2010). Furthermore, Parveen and Showkat (2017) argue that it relates to the moral principle of someone's behaviour and legal right in the research or study. Therefore, in the research, it cannot mentally or physically harm the respondents and also it cannot invade the respondents' privacy (Bryman and Bell, 2011).

This ethical principle is taken into consideration when conducting the questionnaire because it involves human participants to answer the main objective of this study. The ethical factors have been taken into consideration throughout the span of this study which protects participants from harm and any risk and also conducted according to ethical guidelines and rules. In addition, this study follows the research ethics guidelines as stated the UWS (2020) system, the guideline states there are several important ethical principles when involving a human participant. Firstly, autonomy, veracity and informed consent, these principles

autonomies acknowledge the right of all individuals to determine their own course of action and to respect for rights of self-determination. Secondly, privacy and confidentiality, all respondents must entitle to privacy and confidentially and the application for ethical review should demonstrate which these aspects are upheld. Thirdly, justice and inclusiveness, it means every respondent should be fair and equity. Lastly, benefits and harm, it is central in the review of applications and it relates to potential harm, discomfort or stress generated by the study. Therefore, these ethical principles are crucial to support the study in proper ways.

Accessing and ethics are crucial aspects of research design as such numerous institutions and universities require every researcher to obtain ethical approval such as informed consent before embarking upon fieldwork that should guide the study. Moreover, the university perspective is responsible for reviewing and making a decision on all applications for ethical approval (UWS, 2020). In this study, before sending the questionnaire to participants who are Generation Z of Al Rayan bank customers in the UK, it must be obtained in writing which is followed by a comprehensive review of the UWS guideline.

Questionnaire Design

Having an attractive design is necessarily needed when the researcher creates a questionnaire because it makes it easier to follow and understandable from the respondent's perspective (Bryman and Bell, 2011). There are several methods to prevent receiving a low response rate or feedback from the participant (Saunders et al, 2009). According to Bryman and Bell (2011) there are five vital strategies that require to be considered when creating a questionnaire in the research. First, operationalisation, this is the main issue and crucial factor and it is believed the questionnaire relies on the operationalisation method. Second, the measurement scale, it includes some important factors of the statistical study which is nominal, ordinal, interval and ratio scale. Third, the question format, it must be clear because it impacts on supporting easy analysis from the participant's perspective. Fourth, question-wording, this factor regarding how easy participants to read and understand the questionnaire. In the last factor, question sequence, this method's function is to lead the respondent easily to the guide and it makes it easy to complete all the questions. In addition, this method would be affected the result, it is suggested to use a funnel method when creating the questionnaire. It should start off with involving and interesting questions, then continue with sensitive and qualification questions, which are relevant to all the participant criteria and it should be specific to eligible participants and at the end, the participant's personal information is placed in the end of the questionnaire of the research (Bryman and Bell, 2011).

Furthermore, Bryman and Bell (2011) state that the format of the question refers to how the questionnaire would be answered by the research participant, whether it has open-ended/ unstructured questions or partially closed questions in the research context. Moreover, according to Saunders et al (2009) it is beneficial to adopt a closed question in the research, since it could be numerically and analysed and encoded. In addition, the

question wording relates to how the researcher chooses to formulate the questions. Additionally, it should be formulated shortly and concisely, it should not involve two questions in one question questionnaire and it should not be formulated as an indication that a certain question is correct (Patel and Davidson, 2011).

No	Name of Variables	Constructs	Items Survey	Name of Source
1.	Customers Perception	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Bank Reputation • Awareness of Islamic Banking • Relative Advantage • Compatibility 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • I believe Al Rayan bank has a good reputation • I Trust this bank is known to be concerned about customers • I am aware of the instruments used in financing products Islamic bank offer such as <i>Mudaraba</i> • I am aware about the differences between the conventional banking system and the Islamic banking system • Investments are more secure in Islamic banks • Islamic banks are more profitable comparing with the interest in 	<p>Jarvenpaa et al, 2000</p> <p>Bashir, 2012</p> <p>Alam, et al, 2012</p> <p>Faisal et al, 2014</p> <p>Gounaris and Kritos, 2008</p>

			<p>traditional bank (better returns)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Islamic banking is in line with my values • Islamic banking is well suited to my lifestyle 	
2.	CSR	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The Syariah compliance • Charity for preservation of virtue • Guarantee of Environmental sustainability • Guarantee of welfare 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • I trust Al Rayan bank is socially responsible • I am aware this bank does donation to charities • I believe this contributes to the welfare of society • I believe this bank sharing best practise on social responsibility with other organisations • I am aware Islamic financial collaborating with local schools, colleges, universities • I am aware this bank does sponsorship of community events 	<p>Sairally, 2007 He and Li, 2011 Zhang, 2021</p>

			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • I trust Islamic banks do supporting employee's involvement with society or community • Al Rayan bank does investment in research and development in society • This bank does scholarship to students 	
3.	Service Quality	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Emphaty • Responsive • Reliable • Assurance • Tangible 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • AL Rayan staff give individual attention to customer • I am aware this bank service's do deal customer with care • The staff understand the specific needs of customer • I believe all staff having problem solving attitude in this bank • This bank provides prompt services and 	<p>Sata, 2013 Yavas et al, 1997 Chen, S 2009</p>

			<p>quick service to customers</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Willing to help our customers • Always keep customer informed • This bank provides service as promised • When I have problem, the bank shows a sincere interest in solving it • The bank performs the service right the first time • Providing correct /accurate information to our customers • Customers' behaviour in still confidence • All Rayan employees' give confidence to customers • This bank employees are knowledgeable and efficient • Feeling safe in transaction 	
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			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Keep confidentially of client information • Modern equipment are used in Al Rayan bank • Employees have professional appearance • Employees are dress well in this bank 	
4.	Customer Satisfaction	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Overall satisfaction 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Al Rayan bank is exactly what I need • The bank gives the service very well • Overall, I am satisfied with the services of the Al Rayan bank • This Bank meets my expectations 	Chu et al, 2012 Afthanorhan et al, 2018
5.	Brand Experience	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Affective • Behavioural • Sensory 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The brand of Al Rayan bank induces feeling and sentiments • I have strong emotion for the brand of this bank • I feel special experience when I 	Yasin et al, 2019

			<p>see the brand of this bank</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The brand of this bank is an action oriented • The brand of this bank appeals to my sense 	
6.	WoM	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Opinion • Willingness to recommend 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • I will talk about the strengths of the Al Rayan bank with people I know • When I talk about bank to other people, I will tell positive story for this bank • If people ask me about Islamic bank, I will definitely recommend this bank • I would recommend this bank to others on social media • I would recommend and encourage people to use this bank based on the bank reputation 	<p>Mehrad and Mohammadi, 2017 Zhang, 2021 Mahadin and Akroush, 2019</p>

Table 3. 1: Components Segments of Measurement Items.

The questionnaire design of this study started with a cover letter in order to inform the participant regarding the purpose of the questionnaire and the crucial concept which is required to understand in order to complete all the questions. Moreover, it contains the consent form information to ensure the participant a description of involvement and rights as a respondent of this research. Then, there are two some basic questions to make sure the participants are eligible to proceed with this study by asking whether they are customers of Al Rayan Bank in the UK and to make sure they are Generation Z customers. After these sections, it continues to the main questions of the research with total 50 questions which are asked in the questionnaire. In the end of the survey, it contains several demographic background questions which ask about gender, educational background and the occupation of the participant. Furthermore, A Likert scale is implemented in order to for the participant to answer the questionnaire. The scale has answering options from 1-7, where 1 strongly disagrees to 7 strongly agrees. The questionnaire which is sent out to the specific criteria who are using Al Rayan Bank in the UK and also, they are Generation Z (16-24 years old).

Development of Questionnaire Design

A questionnaire protocol that involves the main themes and questions to be completed by the participant is developed. This protocol takes the form of a guide for the questions to be asked from the customers of Al Rayan Bank in the UK who are Generation Z criteria. The guide is based on the issues identified during the literature review analysis (both narrative and systematic) in the business and management field, especially in the marketing perspective of this research and the objectives of the study. Moreover, flexibility is the main guiding principle in this research. Therefore, the questionnaire guide includes a framework that is flexible in nature for the purpose of capturing the participants' perspectives and understanding of the issue at hand which are not thought of initially but might be of value to the study. This structured guide is implemented to include a focus for the study to answer the main research questions and achieve the goal objectives of this study. In addition, this research involves further strengthened analysis by adopting a questionnaire and applying the acceptability, validity and reliability, including integrity (Bell, 2012).

Reliability and Validity of Questionnaire

Implementing the validity and reliability of a quantitative study is a basic method because these points refer to the physiological system or concept to measure (Khadka and Maharjan, 2017). These approaches help to solve comprehensive evaluation. Berzonsly and Adam (2002) state that the comprehensive evaluation can lead to gathering evidence that provides theoretical information through silent questions.

The validity instrument is a fundamental measurement in the research, and it generates the study to be valid if the collecting data and the questions of the questionnaire are in a systematic process. In addition, Golafshani (2003) explain the validity aspect can determine whether the researcher can measure the result of the research is truthful. According to Ekinci (2015) emphasising the need for reliability and validity of a questionnaire

and the questionnaire adopted in this study is subject to appropriate the test of reliability and validity. Moreover, Sekaran and Bougie (2013) explain that reliability and validity could be likened to the goodness of measure. Ekinici (2015) states that a reliability system is commonly considered with the issue of measure consistency, whereas “validity method with whether scale-response questions measure what they are meant to”. Additionally, the Alpha-Cronbach test is tested to confirm the reliability of the questionnaire. This aspect is normally measuring the score.

Sampling Frame

Paten and Davidson (2011) explain sampling frame is a framework of distinct criteria which a participant is required to be able to participate in the sample of the study. It requires to be both general and exact for the sample to be considered representative (Bryman and Bell, 2011). Selecting a sample of the study is significantly required to obtain the best result study and it should be appropriate for a specific study to answer the main research objectives, in the beginning, the question requires to be asked whether the respondents are relevant to this research.

Furthermore, since this study targets respondents within Generation Z customers, it is also vital to ensure that only this generation is generated in this research. Representatives of this generation were born in 1995 and raised in 2012 (Deloitte, 2020). Thus, the questionnaire target is only delivered to customers of Al Rayan Bank in the UK and they are Generation Z criteria as well, it is necessary to obtain a specific sample because it impacts the credibility of the research increased. Moreover, the questionnaire is published on the participating link or website which might be shared by the e-platform system where they have access to the questionnaire or the questionnaire is sent to the customer via social media of WhatsApp and also it is sent by a created link from the researcher to the participants. In order to obtain an estimation of how many participants are required in this research sampling size, the researcher gets involved only 100 respondents because of the limited population who are using AL Rayan Bank in the UK, especially Generation Z characteristics.

Bryman and Bell (2011) stated that a precise number of the total sampling participants does not exist. It is based on various variables for example, time consumption, cost and precision. This research is implemented to describe the relationship between two or more variables and explain a justifiable sample size of around 50 participants (Van Voorhis and Morgan, 2007). Therefore, this research collects a sample size larger than 50 respondents to assist in answering the main objectives of this study. In addition, Fraenkel et al (2012) stated that recommended sampling with a minimum of 100 individuals of subjects needed in descriptive research is essential.

To conclude the sampling size, there are several main reasons to use only 100 participants. Firstly, due to time-consuming to find the particular respondents, especially the young generation. Secondly, in the UK, Islamic banking is not the main bank compared to the conventional system which has fewer customers.

Thirdly, it is believed that 100 respondents are the minimum sample for meaningful results in the research (Gorsuch, 1983; Kline, 1994)

Questionnaire Pilot Study

The literature emphasises the require for a pilot study and pre-testing of a prototype questionnaire before the main research to prevent the incidence of respondents having difficulties completing the questionnaire and to test the validity and reliability of the data collection (Kumar, 2014). It is significantly believed that before sending the questionnaire to all participants is produced, numerous iterative procedures are included between the researcher and supervisor to obtain the proper study. This process gathered the generation of the questionnaire from the literature. All the questions are made based on the relevant theories to support an in-depth analysis of the research. It is usually required times-consuming to generate the actual questionnaire which is sent to the participants.

In regards to the prototype test questionnaire, 116 copies of the prototype questionnaire are provided to the customers' Al Rayan bank with criteria Generation Z in the UK. Moreover, these are applied for the pilot research and pre-testing of the prototype questionnaire prior to conducting the main study and the researcher attempts to prevent any incidence of respondents having difficulties with the questionnaire. Additionally, the data collection is also examined for validity and reliability to produce better research (Wilson, 2014).

Data Analysis and Interpretation (Primary Data)

There are several analysis approaches implemented in this research. A descriptive statistic is one of them. Adopting this method is to analyse some statistical factors for example, frequencies (bar/pie charts) measure the centrality of tendencies (mean, median and mode), and also dispersion (range, variance and standard deviation). These elements are implemented as part of the data analysis and interpretation. In terms of the quantitative approach, with reference to the responses from the closed (structured) questionnaires, this research involved statistical software packages such as SPSS. According to Ekinici (2015) the software of statistical packages is considered to be among the most appropriate to analyse such data. Furthermore, secondary data is collected purposely for the econometric method. In contrast, primary data is collected with the intent to establish the opinions/responses of the participants who are relevant to answering the research. There are numerous distinct characteristics that play a role in determining the most appropriate technique for a study. One of the primary aspects to consider is the number of variables, independent and dependent which are examined in the study, and the scale applied to measure these variables (Sekaran and Bougie, 2010). In this study, there are several independent variables such as customers' perception, corporate social responsibility (CSR), service quality and customer satisfaction, and some dependent variables are service quality, customer satisfaction, brand experience and word of mouth (WoM).

Furthermore, it is crucial to build a special characteristic of this proposed conceptual model. The variables provided in the model are not purely independent and dependent, since, as it is possible to observe in the model, customers' perception, CSR, service quality and customer satisfaction, and then service quality and customer satisfaction lead to brand experience and WOM. As a result, customer satisfaction is a dependent and independent variable at the same time and also a mediating variable. Thus, it is significant to choose a proper technique that permits testing this series of dependence relationships simultaneously since most of the statistical approaches for example, exploratory factor analysis, multiple regression analysis, multiple discriminants, logistic regression, ANOVA analysis, etc., do not allow assessing the measurement properties and examine the main theoretical relationship in one technique approach (Jr et al, 2010).

Based on the study characteristics explained, Factor Analysis and Structural Equations Modelling (SEM) are adopted to be implemented in the customer data in order to examine and analyse the proposed conceptual model. This research adopted the SEM analysis, which could study the structural properties of the proposed conceptual framework, hence this method includes gathering some aspects of multiple regression and factor analysis. Consequently, this research provides examining the overall relationship between theoretical methods and measurable variables (Moon-Koo Kima, 2004). In addition, SEM analysis includes the examination of a series of dependence relationships simultaneously for example in this research there is one variable dependent and independent at the same (customer satisfaction) (Jr et al, 2010). In fact, an approach is divided into two aspects: firstly, implementing factor analysis and secondly, SEM analysis, these methods tend to be the most adequate technique for this study.

Quality Criteria

According to Bryman and Bell (2011) the crucial factor of quality criterion when executing measurement elements of a study is pursuant reliability and validity testing. They also stated that the reliability system maintains the stability of the measurement element. On the other hand, validity maintains that the measurement element measures what it is intended to measure.

Validity Test

The validity is one of the main factors part of the study process which is not only applied to confirm the appropriateness or otherwise of the study processes' constituent factors but also includes the measurement of the study element for instance, this method is implemented to ensure that the instrument measure what it is mainly meant to measure in the specific research with an accurate manner or right way (Kumar, 2014). Moreover, the validity instrument for this study is established through the operationalisation and studied category. By implementing an operationalisation, the researcher could ensure that the information collected is measured in an accurate manner.

Reliability Test

Bryman and Bell (2011) state that reliability measures a specific concept. The main purpose of adopting this instrument is to ensure that the data collection part of the research could be replicable and obtain the same result, with following the guidelines of the pilot study a questionnaire is one of the priority factors in examining the reliability of the research element (Awodele, 2012). Awodele (2012) argues that one of the best reliability coefficients is Cronbach's Alpha (α). This research implemented a SPSS instrument to test the reliability aspect. Malhotra (2005) argues it will appear the value should be from 0 to 1 but the reliable result should be more than 0.6 on the scale of the research. The inter-observer consistency denotes the topic where multiple observations in a study exists or where there is a change of subjective judgment. Nevertheless, to prevent subjective judgments, the researcher has selected only adopted questions in the questionnaire. Moreover, the variable with a value over 0.7 is considered reliable research.

Ensuring validity and reliability methods is significantly crucial for scientific research such as a DBA thesis. The reliability of the validation research was enhanced through the development of a structured research instrument comprising particular questions and the validity method was maintained by including selected academic approaches and industry experts in the field of business and management subject, especially in the marketing aspect. In terms of transferability, the result of this research is argued to be representative of the geographic scope of the research.

Categories	Indexes	Assumptions	References
Internal Consistency Reliability	Composite Reliability (CR)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - CR < 0.6 (Low) - CR: 0.7-0.9 (Satisfied) - CR: 0.6-0.7 (Acceptable for Exploratory Research) - CR > 0.9 (The Probability of Multicollinearity Issues) 	(Hair et al, 2014; Nunnally and Bernstein, 1994)
Indicator Reliability	Outer Loading	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Outer Loadings > 0.7 (Suggested) - $0.4 \leq$ Outer Loading < 0.7 (Acceptable with Certain Condition) 	(Hair et al, 2010; Hulland, 1999; Byrne, 2016; Bagozzi et al, 1991; Hair et al, 2011)

		- Outer Loading < 0.4 (Should be Eliminated)	
Convergent Reliability	Average Variance Extracted	- AVE > 0.50	(Kline, 2015; Gold et al, 2001; Henseler et al, 2015)

Table 3. 2: Acceptance Criteria of Reliability and Validity for Reflective Measurement Model Assessments in PLS-SEM.

Structural Equation Modelling (SEM)

SEM Partial Least Square (PLS) analysis is an extension of multiple linear regression, with a proven track record in exploring such relationships (Henseler and Chin, 2010). Furthermore, they argued that PLS is based on SEM concepts, whereas pure covariance-based SEM still remains the gold standard for theory confirmation and comparisons between alternative methods. However, the demanded places by SEM on data are more onerous and emerging markets, which exhibit degrees of heterogeneity, are commonly appropriated to more flexible concepts for instance, the PLS model. According to Hair et al (2010) PLS technique is one of the examples less affected by data that does not adhere to a high degree of normality.

Several marketing scholars implemented the SEM-PLS model as analysis data for research. Hair et al (2012) argued that the authors found 204 PLS model-based articles published in the top 30 marketing journals over the few last decades, with 51 such research appearing in 2010 alone. In fact, there are numerous studies applying this method for master data analysis in current years, especially in the marketing field. Therefore, the PLS concept has a strong implemented focus and its predictive algorithm is optimised for model building and adaptation. These are characteristics highly compatible with the stated aim and objectives of this study. This study adopted Structural Equation Modelling (SEM) for data analysis through the PLS to analyse the influence between variables. The conceptual modelling in SEM PLS is based on the previous study and rationale since it must be developed and constructed estimation. The data used does not have to meet the requirements of data normality assumption. Therefore, PLS analysis appears as an alternative procedure other than SEM-based covariance because in reality commonly find that the data might not normally be distributed. This analysis can be implemented in a small participant size and does not require randomisation of the sample, thus selecting a sample with non-probability concepts. Garson (2016) argued that the PLS method could handle numerous independent variables, even when predictors display multicollinearity on the predictor side. Moreover, this model applies path analysis handling casual paths relating to the predictor as well as paths relating to the predictors to the response variable, while PLS is an alternative concept of estimating the model managing SEM based on theory and previous research.

The Summary of Research Methodology

This chapter has discussed the research methodology which underpins this research. The most appropriate analysis should be adopted to obtain the proper study at the end. The research process has applied the research honeycomb method rather than the often-applied research onion. The review expanded on the various components of the honeycomb model which provided several analyses such as research philosophy, research approach, research strategy, research purpose, research design, data collection and data analysis or technique. Enhancing attention on the research data analysis technique to obtain the main answer to the research objective, the researcher implemented multiple approaches to analyse the research data which was discussed extensively. Adopting the primary and secondary data to collect information is required significantly to find the answer to the purpose of the study. It also used some statistical tools such as SPSS and SEM-PLS analysis to achieve the main objectives.

CHAPTER IV

DATA ANALYSIS AND SURVEY RESULTS

Introduction

The previous chapters discussed the background of the research, the primary relevant literature and the methods implemented in the research. In addition, chapter III provided the research methodology aspect such as philosophy, design, strategy, scope, quantitative procedures and measured applied etc. This chapter provides the results or findings of the analyses and hypothesis testing. Moreover, the research discussed in this chapter includes an initial understanding of the relationship between customer perception, CSR, service quality and brand experience and Word of Mouth aspect toward Generation Z customers of Al Rayan bank in the UK.

This chapter addressed the research questions and is organised as follows. Firstly, a general description of survey participants and how the dataset compares to the sample Generation Z who are using Al Rayan Bank in the UK. This is followed by an explanation of how the scales were checked for validity and reliability. Next, regression analysis results for each research question are presented, along with the result of the test. Finally, the limitations of the findings are considered in this research.

The four research questions are:

Research Question 1: What is the main factor of Generation Z customers of Al Rayan Bank in the UK which influence the brand experience and Word of Mouth factor?

Research Question 2: Does customers perception, CSR and Service quality affect customer satisfaction?

Research Question 3: Does customers perception, CSR and Service quality affect brand experience and WoM?

Research Question 4: Does customer satisfaction mediate variable of the effectiveness of customers perception, CSR and service quality on brand experience and WoM?

Aligned with this, and as specified in chapter one, the research aim for the main research is:

The main aim of the research is to analyse and evaluate the effectiveness process of the Generation Z customers of Al Rayan Bank in the UK market by customers' perceptions, analysing the service quality, becoming satisfied with the service, measuring the experience with this brand and sharing to other people regarding this bank service.

Consequently, the following several research objectives are designated for exploration in the main research. This is heavily based on the conceptual framework provided in the previous chapter, except with the original first objective now sub-divided into objectives which are explained as follows:

1. To consider the effect of customers perception of Islamic banking, CRM and service quality factors of Al Rayan bank for Generation Z in the UK on customer satisfaction.
2. To consider the effect of customer's perception towards Islamic banking, CRM and service quality aspect of Al Rayan bank for Generation Z in the UK on brand experience and WoM.
3. To examine the relationship between customers perception of Islamic banking, CRM and service quality of Al Rayan bank for Generation Z in the UK on customer satisfaction, brand experience and WoM.
4. To analyse whether customer satisfaction mediates effect the relationship between customers perception towards Islamic banking, CRM and service quality of Al Rayan bank for Generation Z in the UK on customer satisfaction, brand experience and WoM.
5. To assess the impact of brand experience and Word of Mouth factors from Generation Z customers of Al Rayan Bank in the UK (Research objectives 1 to 4).

Response Collection

The survey included 50 survey variables implemented to measure Generation Z customers' perspectives in Al Rayan bank in the UK (Table 3.1, Chapter III, Methodology). The variables are grouped into six sections including:

Section 1. Customer Perception (8 questions),

Section 2. Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) (9 questions),

Section 3. Service Quality (19 questions)

Section 4. Customer Satisfaction (4 questions)

Section 5. Brand Experience (5 questions)

Section 6. Word of Mouth (WoM) (5 questions)

Survey Summary

There were 100 participants who filled the questionnaire correctly. Regarding the remaining 16 questionnaires, some of them were incomplete and removed from the data results. However, the response rate of the questionnaire was almost all the participants completed which are about 90% of the total respondents.

Focusing customers of Al Rayan bank who are Generation Z were invited to participate in this research. The survey is shared from an online system via social media such as WhatsApp.

There result of this analysis is presented:

Table 4. 1:
Survey Summary

No of Participants	of Not Correctly Filled	Collected Questionnaire	Response Rate (%)
116	16	100	86.21%

Descriptive Statistics

Sample Characteristics

The present research, it provides some demographic aspects of the participants such as age, gender, education background and occupation. In fact, all these variables have their own impact on making a decision on Al Rayan bank. In general. Surveys were Generation Z customers of Al Rayan bank in the UK. Key statistics relevant to the survey sample and hypotheses are presented:

- Gender and age

Table 4. 2:
Respondent Characteristic Gender

No	Gender	Frequency	Percentage
1	Male	59	59%
2	Female	31	31%
3	Prefer Not to Say	10	10%
Total		100	100%

Source: Own Survey, 2022

The current study only focuses on the Generation Z customers of Al Rayan bank in the UK, so the participants' ages were from 16 to 24 years old.

- Level Education

No.	Education	Frequency	Percentage
1	PMR/LCE or Below	3	3%
2	SPM/STPM/MCE/HSC/GCSE	8	8%
3	Certificate/Diploma	17	17%
4	Degree/Professional Certificate	44	44%
5	Postgraduate (MBA, Masters & PhD)	25	25%
6	Others....	3	3%
Total		100	100%

Source: Own Survey, 2022

- Occupation

Table 4. 3:
Demographic Characteristic

No.	Occupation	Frequency	Percentage
1	Student	2	2%
2	Health and Social Care	11	11%
3	Business & Public service	31	31%
4	Science & Engineering	12	12%
5	Service Occupations	20	20%
6	Sales	16	16%
7	Construction & Building Trades	8	8%
Total		100	100%

Source: Own Survey, 2022

Validity and Reliability Test

The reliability aspect is a vital instrument in the research to further analysis for measuring consistent and accurate what it ought to measure. The reliability test is assessed during the first phase of data analysis. Babbie (2010) stated that one of the main functions of a reliability check of collected data is to assert that the data would not be subject to significant variation if it is collected from the same participants at a different time. Testing the reliability by implementing Cronbach's Alpha to measure the variables which the current study presents. The Cronbach Alpha should be higher than 0.7 to have adequate reliability.

The validity of research variables and constructs is a crucial consideration in the research when evaluating both the appropriateness of research methodology and the quality of research results. Validity is related to the measurement variables implemented to model and test theory and expresses the "extent to which an empirical measure adequately reflects the real meaning of the concept under consideration (Babbie, 2010).

Quantitative Analysis

After an evaluation of different multivariate data analysis methods, Structural Equation Modelling was taken into account as the best fitting multivariate research technique. In addition, the main reason is that this study is not exploratory nature in that the techniques implemented and tested have already been established. Implementing SEM-PLS for measurement model (outer model) and structural model (inner model). The measurement model builds on the knowledge gained in new products and new service development studies

and introduces a new model in order to evaluate the moderating impact of service complexity. Moreover, the outer model was applied to test the validity and reliability aspects. However, the inner model was applied to test the significance of the parameters formulated in the hypothesis.

Evaluation of the Inner Structural Model

Structural model testing (Inner Model) after the estimated model meets the criteria for the outer model, a structural model test (inner model) is conducted. The inner model test was conducted to see the relationship between the construct, the significance value and the R-square of the research model. The value indicates that An R² Value of 0.75 is considered substantial, an R² value of 50 is regarded as moderate, and an R² value of 0.26 is considered as weak (Henseler et al, 2009; Hair et al, 2013). Here are the R-square values in the construct:

Table 4. 4:
Value of R-Square

R-Square	
Customer Perception (X1)	
CSR (X2)	
Service Quality (X3)	
Brand Experience (Y1)	0.653
Word of Mouth (Y2)	0.116
Customer Satisfaction (Z1)	0.362

Source: Output Smart PLS, 2022

Table 4.1 shows the R-square value for Customer Satisfaction (Z1) obtained by 0.362 which means that Customer Perception (X1), CSR (X2), and Service Quality (X3) are able to explain Customer Satisfaction (Z1) by 36.2%, while the R-square value of the Brand Experience (Y1) variable was obtained at 0.653, which means that Customer Perception (X1), CSR (X2), and Service Quality (X3) were able to explain the Brand Experience (Y1) of 65.3%. The R-square value is also found in the Word of Mouth (Y2) variable, which is obtained at 0.116, which means that Customer Perception (X1), CSR (X2), Service Quality (X3), and Customer Satisfaction (Z1) are able to explain Word of Mouth (Y2) by 11.6%.

Evaluation of Outer Measurement Model

According to Ho (2013) the outer measurement concept is aimed to calculate the reliability, internal consistency, and validity of the observed variables (measured through the questionnaire) together with unobserved variables. Consistency evaluations are based on single observed and construct reliability tests whereas convergent and discriminant validity is applied for the assessment of validity (Hair et al, 2012).

A single observed variable reliability has described the variance of an individual observed comparatively to an unobserved variable by evaluating the standardised outer loading outer loadings of the observed variables (Gotz et al, 2010). Observed variables with an outer loading of 0.7 greater are believed to be sufficiently acceptable (Hair et al, 2012), whereas the outer loadings with a value less than 0.7 should be discarded (Chin, 1998). Moreover, Cronbach’s alpha and composite reliability were applied for internal consistency evaluation in the construct reliability. According to Fornell and Lacker (1981) the level of composite reliability and Cronbach alpha should be greater than 0.7 to verify the convergent validity of the variables, and each latent construct’s Average Variance Extracted (AVE) was calculated. The lowest 50% of the variance constructs from the observed should be taken by the latent construct in the model. Thus, this indicates that all of the AVE for all constructs should be above 0.5 (38,71). From the table of the outer model after removal 4.3, it is indicated that all of the AVE values were more than 0.5, therefore, convergent validity was confirmed for this research. In addition, these results confirmed the convergent validity and good internal consistency of the measurement model.

The measurement of the outer model uses three criteria, namely discriminant validity, convergent validity, and composite reliability. The measurement results show that all variable indicators are valid and reliable as presented in Table 4.2.

Table 4. 5:
Outer Models

Item Indicators	Outer Loadings	AVE	Composite Reliability	Cronbach Alpha
Customer Perception (X1)				
X1.1	0.858	0.522	0.895	0.867
X1.2	0.642			
X1.3	0.743			
X1.4	0.620			
X1.5	0.765			
X1.6	0.838			
X1.7	0.736			
X1.8	0.515			
CSR (X2)				
X2.1	0.243	0.359	0.799	0.717
X2.2	0.094			

X2.3	0.251			
X2.4	0.403			
X2.5	0.548			
X2.6	0.849			
X2.7	0.823			
X2.8	0.756			
X2.9	0.816			
Service Quality (X3)				
X3.1	-0.060	0.353	0.900	0.878
X3.2	0.079			
X3.3	0.708			
X3.4	0.411			
X3.5	0.782			
X3.6	0.557			
X3.7	0.728			
X3.8	0.698			
X3.9	0.389			
X3.10	0.464			
X3.11	0.730			
X3.12	0.690			
X3.13	0.497			
X3.14	0.704			
X3.15	0.694			
X3.16	0.714			
X3.17	0.587			
X3.18	0.515			
X3.19	0.607			
Customer Satisfaction (Z1)				
Z1.1	0.863	0.547	0.821	0.708
Z1.2	0.885			
Z1.3	0.482			
Z1.4	0.654			

Brand Experience (Y1)				
Y1.1	0.121	0.357	0.662	0.505
Y1.2	0.097			
Y1.3	0.682			
Y1.4	0.803			
Y1.5	0.809			
Word of Mouth (Y2)				
Y2.1	0.785	0.550	0.858	0.795
Y2.2	0.780			
Y2.3	0.614			
Y2.4	0.857			
Y2.5	0.645			

Source: Output Smart PLS, 2022

Note: *) indicator is valid if outer loadings > 0.70

**) reliable indicator if composite reliability and Cronbach alpha > 0.70

Table 4.2 indicated that the value of outer loadings which mark red < 0.60 does not meet convergent validity, therefore it is necessary to remove outliers.

Table 4. 6:

Outer Models After Removal

Item Indicators	Outer Loadings	AVE	Composite Reliability	Cronbach Alpha
Customer Perception (X1)				
X1.1	0.857	0.652	0.903	0.866
X1.3	0.748			
X1.5	0.804			
X1.6	0.873			
X1.7	0.747			
CSR (X2)				
X2.6	0.872	0.693	0.900	0.852
X2.7	0.849			

X2.8	0.771			
X2.9	0.833			
Service Quality (X3)				
X3.3	0.719	0.576	0.890	0.855
X3.5	0.810			
X3.7	0.710			
X3.11	0.772			
X3.14	0.790			
X3.16	0.747			
Customer Satisfaction (Z1)				
Z1.1	0.946	0.887	0.940	0.873
Z1.2	0.938			
Brand Experience (Y1)				
Y1.4	0.840	0.706	0.828	0.784
Y1.5	0.841			
Word of Mouth (Y2)				
Y2.1	0.813	0.728	0.889	0.816
Y2.2	0.830			
Y2.4	0.914			

Source: Output Smart PLS, 2022

Note: *) indicator is valid if outer loadings > 0.70

*****) reliable indicator if composite reliability and Cronbach alpha > 0.70**

Table 4.3, it shows that the AVE value > 0.50, Cronbach Alpha and Composite Reliability > 0.70 and the outer loading is all > 0.70 so it could sufficient to meet convergent validity.

Figure 4. 1: Original Outer Models

Figure 4. 2: Model After Outlier

Discriminant Validity

Discriminant validity is defined as the manifest variable in any cost concept which is distinct from other constructs in the path model of research, where its cross-loading value in the latent variable is greater than that it any other constructs (Sarstedt et al, 2014). Fornell and Larcker (1981) stated that the Fornell and Larcker criterion and cross-loadings were applied to evaluate the discriminant validity. Moreover, (Sarstedt et al, 2014) argued that the standard is that a construct should not indicate the same variance as any other construct which is more than the AVE value. Table 4.4 indicates the Fornell and Larcker criterion test of

construct where the squared correlations were compared with the correlations from other latent variables. In addition, table 4.4 shows that all variables of the correlations were small relative to the squared root of average variance exerted along the diagonals, implying satisfactory discriminant validity. Therefore, it proved that the observed variables in every construct showed the given latent variable confirming the discriminant validity of the model.

Table 4. 7: Discriminant Validity

	X1	X2	X3	Y1	Y2	Z1
X1	0.807					
X2	0.783	0.832				
X3	0.065	-0.008	0.759			
Y1	0.760	0.769	0.117	0.840		
Y2	0.248	0.240	0.074	0.142	0.853	
Z1	0.031	0.060	0.588	0.085	0.228	0.942

Source: Output Smart PLS, 2022

Table 4.4, it shows that all variables are sufficient for the criteria of discriminant validity, in which the constructs all variables are > 0.50.

Composite Reliability

The next attempt was tested the construct reliability test which can be seen from composite reliability and Cronbach alpha > 0.70. Table 4.3, it indicates that the value of composite reliability and Cronbach's alpha is > 0.70, so that all variables are greatly acceptable of composite reliability and Cronbach's alpha.

Hypothesis Testing

Path analysis was implemented to test linkages' causal relationship within the conceptual model. PLS analysis is an extension of multiple linear regression, with a proven track record in exploring such relationships. The path coefficients in the PLS and the standardised β coefficient in the regression analysis were similar. Through the correlation coefficient value, the significance of the hypothesis was tested and analysed. The correlation coefficient denoted the expected variation in the dependent construct for a unit variation in the independent construct.

Table 4. 8:
Path Coefficients

Hypothesised Path	Correlation Coefficient	t statistics	p values	Result
CP -> Customer Satisfaction	-0.171	1.369	0.172	Not Significant
CP -> Brand Experience	0.389	4.904	0.000	Significant
CP -> Word of Mouth	0.155	0.903	0.367	Not Significant
CSR -> Customer Satisfaction	0.197	1.718	0.086	Not Significant
CSR -> Brand Experience	0.469	5.993	0.000	Significant
CSR -> Word of Mouth	0.102	0.714	0.475	Not Significant
ServQual -> Customer Satisfaction	0.602	7.413	0.000	Significant
ServQual -> Brand Experience	0.100	1.536	0.125	Not Significant
ServQual -> Word of Mouth	-0.099	0.730	0.466	Not Significant
Customer Satisfaction -> Brand Experience	-0.011	0.176	0.861	Not Significant
Customer Satisfaction -> Word of Mouth	0.276	2.038	0.042	Significant

Source: Output Smart PLS. 2022

Assessment of Hypothesis

Hypothesis 1

The above PLS output shows that Customer Perception has no significant effect on Customer Satisfaction with a negative correlation coefficient of -0.171. This is indicated by the value of t statistic ($1.369 < 1.661$) and p-value ($0.172 > 0.05$). Therefore, the variable of Customer Perception has no effect on customer satisfaction. So, hypothesis 1, namely that the Customer Perception has a significant positive effect on Customer Satisfaction can be rejected.

Hypothesis 2

Customer Perception variable has a positive and significant effect on Brand Experience with a positive correlation coefficient of 0.389. This is indicated by the value of t statistics ($4.904 > 1.666$) and p values ($0.000 < 0.05$). Therefore, the Customer Perception variable has a significant effect on Brand Experience. It can be concluded that hypothesis 2, namely Customer Perception has a positive and significant impact on Brand Experience (Accepted).

Hypothesis 3

Customer Perception has no significant effect on Word of Mouth with a positive correlation coefficient of 0.155. This is indicated by the value of t statistics ($0.903 < 1.661$) and p values ($0.367 > 0.05$). Therefore, The Customer Perception variable has no effect on WoM. It can be concluded that Hypothesis 3, namely Customer Perception, has a significant positive effect on Word of Mouth and can be rejected

Hypothesis 4

Corporate Social Responsibility has no significant effect on Customer Satisfaction with a positive correlation coefficient of 0.197. This is indicated by the value of t statistics ($1.718 > 1.661$) and p values ($0.086 > 0.05$). Therefore, the CSR variable has no effect on customer satisfaction. It can be concluded that Hypothesis 4, namely Corporate Social Responsibility, has a significant positive effect on Customer Satisfaction, which is rejected.

Hypothesis 5

Corporate Social Responsibility has a positive and significant effect on Brand Experience with a positive correlation coefficient of 0.469. This is indicated by the value of t statistics ($5.993 > 1.661$) and p values ($0.000 < 0.05$). Therefore, the Corporate Social Responsibility variable has a significant effect on Brand Experience. It can be concluded that Hypothesis 5, namely Corporate Social Responsibility, has a significant positive effect on Brand Experience (accepted).

Hypothesis 6

Corporate Social Responsibility has no significant effect on Word of Mouth with a positive correlation coefficient of 0.102. This is indicated by the value of t statistics ($0.714 < 1.661$) and p values ($0.475 > 0.05$). Therefore, the Corporate Social Responsibility variable has no effect on WoM. It can be concluded that Hypothesis 6, namely Corporate Social Responsibility, has a significant positive effect on Word of Mouth, which is rejected.

Hypothesis 7

Service Quality has a positive and significant effect on Customer Satisfaction with a positive correlation coefficient of 0.602. This is indicated by the value of t statistics ($7.413 > 1.661$) and p values ($0.000 < 0.05$). Therefore, the Service Quality variable has a significant effect on Customer Satisfaction. It can be concluded that Hypothesis 7, namely Service Quality, has a significant positive effect on Customer Satisfaction (accepted).

Hypothesis 8

Service Quality has no significant effect on Brand Experience with a positive correlation coefficient of 0.100. This is indicated by the value of t statistics ($1.536 < 1.661$) and p values ($0.125 > 0.05$). Therefore, the Service Quality variable has no effect on Brand Experience. It can be concluded that Hypothesis 8, namely Service Quality, has a significant positive effect on Brand Experience, which is rejected.

Hypothesis 9

Service Quality has no significant effect on Word of Mouth with a negative correlation coefficient of -0.099. This is indicated by the value of t statistics ($0.176 < 1.661$) and p values ($0.861 > 0.05$). Therefore, the Service Quality variable has no effect on WoM. It can be concluded that Hypothesis 9, namely Service Quality, has a significant positive effect on WoM can be rejected.

Hypothesis 10

Customer Satisfaction has no significant effect on Brand Experience with a negative correlation coefficient of -0.011. This is indicated by the value of t statistics ($0.176 < 1.661$) and p values ($0.861 > 0.05$). Therefore, the Customer Satisfaction variable has no effect on Brand Experience. It can be concluded that Hypothesis 10, namely Customer Satisfaction has a significant positive effect on Brand Experience, is rejected.

Hypothesis 11

Customer Satisfaction has no significant effect on Word of Mouth with a positive correlation coefficient of 0.276. This is indicated by the value of t statistics ($2.038 > 1.661$) and p values ($0.042 > 0.05$). Therefore, the Customer Satisfaction variable has a significant effect on WoM. It can be concluded that Hypothesis 11, namely Customer Satisfaction, has a significant positive effect on the Word of Mouth accepted.

Mediation Effect testing

The mediation variable has been described as the third variable. Moderator variables impact the strength and/or direction of a relationship between independent predictor variables and dependent variables. Mediation is often also referred to as interaction. The two terms are implemented interchangeably in this research. In addition, the mediating effect shows the relationship between independent and dependent variables through mediating variables.

Table 4. 9: Indirect Effects

	Original Sample (O)	Sample Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values
X1 -> Y1	0.002	0.003	0.013	0.139	0.890
X1 -> Y2	-0.047	-0.046	0.047	1.018	0.309
X1 -> Z1					
X2 -> Y1	-0.002	-0.003	0.014	0.150	0.881
X2 -> Y2	0.055	0.054	0.046	1.184	0.237
X2 -> Z1					
X3 -> Y1	-0.006	-0.009	0.038	0.172	0.863
X3 -> Y2	0.166	0.157	0.082	2.018	0.044
X3 -> Z1					
Z1 -> Y1					
Z1 -> Y2					

Source: Appendix 3. Output Smart PLS, 2022

Hypothesis 12

The calculation of the correlation coefficient of the indirect influence of the Customer Perception variable on Brand Experience mediated by Customer Satisfaction which shows in table 4.6, is based on the correlation coefficient of the indirect influence of the Customer Perception variable on Brand Experience, which is 0.002 with a t statistic value ($0.139 < 1.661$) and p values ($0.890 > 0.05$) which means it is not significant. Therefore, Customer Perception has no effect on Brand Experience mediated by Customer Satisfaction. It can be concluded that Hypothesis 12, namely Islamic Banking Adoption of Brand Experience mediated by Customer Satisfaction is rejected

Hypothesis 13

The calculation of the correlation coefficient of the indirect influence of the CSR variable on Brand Experience mediated by Customer Satisfaction is presented in Table 4.6 based on the correlation coefficient of the indirect influence of the CSR variable on Brand Experience, which is 0.002 with a t statistic value ($0.150 < 1.661$) and p values ($0.881 > 0.05$) which means it is not significant. Therefore, CSR has no effect on Brand Experience mediated by Customer Satisfaction. It can be concluded that Hypothesis 13, namely CSR of Brand Experience mediated by Customer Satisfaction is rejected

Hypothesis 14

The calculation of the correlation coefficient of the indirect influence of the Service Quality variable on Brand Experience mediated by Customer Satisfaction is presented in Table 4.6 based on the correlation coefficient of the indirect influence of the Service Quality variable on Brand Experience, namely -0.006 with t statistics ($0.172 < 1.661$) and p values ($0.863 > 0.05$) which means it is not significant. Therefore, Service Quality has no effect on Brand Experience mediated by Customer Satisfaction. It can be concluded that Hypothesis 14, namely Service Quality on Brand Experience mediated by Customer Satisfaction, is rejected.

Hypothesis 15

The calculation of the correlation coefficient of the indirect influence of the Customer Perception variable on Word of mouth mediated by Customer Satisfaction is presented in Table 4.6 based on the correlation coefficient of the indirect influence of the Customer Perception variable on Word of mouth, namely -0.047 with a value of t statistics ($1.018 < 1.661$) and p values ($0.309 > 0.05$) which means not significant. Therefore, Customer Perception has no effect on Word of mouth mediated by Customer Satisfaction. It can be concluded that Hypothesis 15, namely Customer Perception of Word of mouth mediated by Customer Satisfaction is rejected.

Hypothesis 16

The calculation of the correlation coefficient of the indirect effect of the Corporate Social Responsibility variable on Word of mouth mediated by Customer Satisfaction is presented in Table 4.6 based on the correlation coefficient of the indirect influence of the Corporate Social Responsibility variable on Word of mouth, which is 0.055 with a value of t statistics ($1.184 < 1.661$) and p values ($0.237 > 0.05$) which means it is not significant. Therefore, Corporate Social Responsibility has no effect on Word of mouth mediated by Customer Satisfaction. It can be concluded that Hypothesis 16, namely Corporate Social Responsibility for Word of mouth mediated by Customer Satisfaction is rejected.

Hypothesis 17

The calculation of the correlation coefficient of the indirect effect of the Service Quality variable on Word of mouth mediated by Customer Satisfaction is presented in Table 4.6 based on the correlation coefficient of the indirect effect of the Service Quality variable on Word of mouth, namely 0.166 with a value of t statistics ($2.018 > 1.661$) and p values ($0.044 < 0.05$) which means that it has a significant effect. Therefore, Service Quality has a significant effect on Word of mouth mediated by Customer Satisfaction. It can be concluded that Hypothesis 17, namely Service Quality on Word of mouth mediated by Customer Satisfaction is accepted.

Conclusion

This chapter provides a detailed discussion of the quantitative data analysis. Starting the pre-test of survey instruments refined items by assessing validity and reliability test with implementing Cronbach's alpha and item to total correlation. The primary data of the main survey is collected applying a self-administrated questionnaire which delivered to Generation Z customers of Al Rayan bank in the UK. Moreover, testing evaluation of inner structural model and evaluation of outer measurement model. In addition, examining the hypotheses with path analysis (PLS)- SEM model and mediation effect testing is also used in this research.

CHAPTER V

DISCUSSION OF ANALYSIS

Introduction

In the previous chapter, the theoretical model proposed in this research to provide an understanding of Generation Z customers of Al Rayan Bank perspectives was empirically tested. The result from empirical analysis defines the set of significant predictors for young customers perspective of Islamic banking in terms of brand experience and WoM factor. By implementing SEM analysis, a final revised framework is provided, showing the significant links between variables (independents, dependents and mediating). Moreover, this chapter aims to give a synthesis of the quantitative analysis, by discussing the significant and insignificant relationship in the proposed theoretical framework through which research hypotheses were accepted or rejected.

Discussion of Hypotheses Testing

The primary purpose of this research is to examine and analyse the Generation Z customers of Al Rayan Bank in the UK market by measuring their brand experiences regarding the service of the bank and how their reaction to sharing the information about this bank with other people, implementing the independent variables such as from the customer perception of Islamic banking, CSR aspect and service quality of Al Rayan bank in the UK. In addition, it also tests the mediating effect of the customer satisfaction factor.

The main contribution of this research was to empirically reveal the constructs that affected brand experiences and WoM aspects of Generation Z customers of Al Rayan Bank in the UK using the PLS-SEM model. One hundred questionnaires were collected from Generation Z clients. It is believed that the PLS-SEM technique is highly an appropriate model for developing and analysing complex concepts, and it also validates the complex model, and social science investigators should improve the latest concepts to manage the more complex model relationship of their current and future research. Moreover, this study applied the paths model to test implementing SEM based on the PLS technique. It also used the SPSS to assist with the descriptive statistical analysis. As in the previous chapter detailed, several significant findings are discussed as follows.

Implications

The effect of Customer Perception on Customer Satisfaction, Brand Experience and Word of Mouth.

The results indicated that customer perception had an insignificant effect on customer satisfaction. Generation Z customers need to be more satisfied enough with the service. The bank's reputation is also not one of the significant aspects for the customers to adopt the Islamic bank (Chebab and Zribi, 2012). This bank still needs to do more to fulfil the expectations of these customers regarding customer perception towards Islamic banking factors such as the reputation of the bank. These results contradict the existing literature; for instance,

Ahmad and Haron (2002), Dusuki and Abdullah (2007), Gait and Worthington (2008), Lateh et al (2009) and Othman and Owen (2001) these scholars argue that from the customer perspective regarding the bank, reputation is one of the significant aspects in adopting the banking service and lead to the satisfaction factor of the service. Moreover, the customers also still need to gain knowledge regarding the benefits of service Islamic banks which leads to them are not satisfied enough to enjoy the service. Furthermore, another dimension of customer perception, such as awareness of Islamic banking also should be considered. Due to the majority of young generation clients need more knowledge of Islamic system products and services. A marketing strategy is significantly required to improve this value. It requires educating young customers on their system to obtain a better understanding of Islamic finance. In addition, Hassan et al (2008) argue that since customer satisfaction is a crucial element of the total package, Islamic financial institutions might implement satisfied clients in their promotional efforts to attract new ones. Thus, the company should consider perceiving customer's perceptions to get a better value for the customer satisfaction aspect.

The results showed that customer perception had a positive and significant on brand experience. It indicated that Z generation of customers AL Rayan bank in the UK has an excellent brand experience to adopt this bank and they have a special feeling in terms of experience to this bank and able to appeal their sense. The awareness of customers aspect evokes an emotional experience. Customers experience a brand not only with a single touch point, though it is a whole journey of all touch points which really counts, therefore it increases customers feeling of happiness when they actually are (Rawson et al, 2013). Moreover, the customers have an impressive brand experience regarding customer perception of Islamic banking in the UK. It is confirmed several studies which found that customer perception regarding bank reputation is one of the most crucial aspects of choosing a banking system and having an excellent experience with the firm (Ahmad and Haron, 2002; Dusuki and Abdullah, 2007; Gait and Worthington, 2008; Lateh et al, 2009; Othman and Owen, 2001). Therefore, the role of customers' perception of brand experience from young customers has positive feedback. However, it is considerably required from the company to improve and maintain the service from the young generation customers for long-term strategy and better brand experience perspective.

Another result of this study showed that customer perception in Islamic banking had an insignificant effect on the WoM factor. Boksberger and Melsen (2011) argue that a customer's perception is an individual interaction with the company or of the eventual consequence of this interaction which creates a perceived value from the customers. Zeithalm (1988) indicated that it refers to how the client values the usefulness of a goods or service, considering the benefits received and the sacrifice made to obtain the product or service. In addition, customers' attitude is seen as an overall effect towards an act, and it reflects the overall evaluation of the goodness and badness of performing the action after assessing the outcome of behavioural beliefs. This study found that customers expressed feelings about Islamic banking and tended to share information with

other people. It is believed that customers' perception regarding Islamic banking still less received value from Islamic financial institutions which leads to the customers being less motivated to share information regarding Al Rayan bank corporation. These results contradict the previous study such as (Hansen et al 2008; Brodie et al, 2009; Mosavi and Ghaedi, 2012).

The effect of Corporate Social Responsibility on Customer Satisfaction, Brand Experience and Word of Mouth.

It is believed that CSR initiatives are considerably required in the banking sector to enhance the productivity of a business. Nowadays, numerous companies in this industry implement this activity, especially in the banking sector. In terms of achieving the main objectives, this study analyses the CSR aspect of Islamic banking. The result of this research found that CSR had an insignificant effect on customer satisfaction. Whilst several studies found a positive and direct correlation between CSR and customer satisfaction (Ashraf et al, 2017; Chung et al, 2015; Qamar, 2016). They stated that by adopting and improving CSR initiatives, corporations could have a more satisfied and long-term customer base. Nevertheless, this study showed that the customers still have less satisfaction regarding the CSR aspect of Islamic banking, it could probably the clients are still not really familiar with the CSR perception of Islamic banking. Therefore, several existing scholars which mentioned before contradict this study. It is considerably required that the firm considers a better understanding of how CSR activities to increase the value from the customers' perspective to obtain satisfaction aspect from young generation clients.

Another result of the research showed that CSR had a positive and significant effect on brand experience. The customers have a great feeling of brand experience and appeal to their sense regarding the CSR perception of Al Rayan Bank. The existing literature also found that CSR influences the brand experience directly and indirectly, an aspect which leads to the brand loyalty factor (Crespo and del Bosque, 2005). In addition, it is confirmed from a prior study that since clients are aware of the firm's CSR activities and its brands, it is most likely to form an attitudinal response to both the corporation's CSR and brand (Wong et al, 2015). Therefore, in this study, the customers of Generation Z had a positive effect on the brand experience factor. They have an excellent perception regarding CSR activities of Al Rayan Bank in the UK toward their brand experience in this company.

Another result of this study indicated that CSR had an insignificant effect on WoM. The customers are less likely to use marketing tools such as WoM to persuade or share with other people regarding the Al Rayan bank service, which the CSR activities of the bank are not priorities in sharing with others, as they have other more important factors. It contradicted the previous study which concluded that CSR initiatives had a positive and significant effect on WoM and it showed that CSR leads to positive WoM (Hong and Rim, 2010; Ningrum and Nurcahaya, 2014). In addition, it contradicts from prior scholars (Maden et al, 2012) who investigated

that CSR had a positive effect on WoM in Turkish companies, which CSR activities could improve their reputation by persuading the clients to change their attitude in positive ways to customers. Moreover, the banking industry is able to improve the firms' image through a similar process. However, this study found refuted by Generation Z customers and it necessarily needed to improve their perspective in terms of CSR activities from the company because a remarkable adoption of CSR by a financial institution will lead to positive information and experience for their clients which could impact on WoM strategy. Consequently, the clients feel the positive experience could tell other people, share their experience and recommend the company as a banking service provider to other people.

The effect of Service Quality on Customer Satisfaction, Brand Experience and Word of Mouth.

Several studies consider that service quality aspects are valid instruments for measuring service quality, which is a core determinant of customer satisfaction factor (Abu et al, 2016). In fact, modern banking success nowadays is taken into account that bank clients' satisfaction is one of the indicators to measure (Amin and Isa, 2008). The findings of this research confirmed that the generic service quality dimensions are the most important factors to contribute to customer satisfaction alongside customer perception and CSR aspects. More specifically, understanding the specific needs of the customer, the bank provides prompt service and quick service, always keeping customer informed and providing accurate information to clients are confirmed in this study.

The results of this study found that service quality had a strong positive and significant effect on customer satisfaction. Service quality was positively correlated with customer satisfaction, indicating the quality of Al Rayan Bank to Generation Z clients as a prerequisite for establishing and having satisfaction with the products and service. The previous existing studies indicated that service quality is the antecedent of the customer satisfaction variable (Cronin Jr et al, 2000; Yee et al, 2010). In addition, the results confirmed or supported the current literature that investigated service quality as crucial to improving the probability of customer satisfaction (Bloemer et al, 1998; Lai et al, 2008; Dahiyat et al, 2011). Therefore, the results indicated that service quality had a positive effect on customer satisfaction, supporting existing previous studies.

The role of service quality on brand experiences in this study indicated that there was an insignificant effect between them. It has been refuted by several scholars existing in this field such as, Serafimovikj et al (2017) the company should improve and enhance the service quality aspect to lead the customers to gain brand experience in this modern market of business (Serafimovikj et al, 2017). Meis (2018) found clients tend to assign higher importance to dimension service quality comparatively to brand experience and that especially the indicators responsiveness, assurance and reliability appear to be of main relevance. Moreover, the service staff 's willingness to assist clients and to aid prompt service accounts are the most crucial factors. However,

this study found that it contradicted the existing literature. Therefore, it has significantly improved the service quality aspect of brand experience aspect on Generation Z customers of Al Rayan Bank in the UK.

Furthermore, the results of this study indicated that service quality had an insignificant effect on the WoM variable. The customers are less likely to recommend or share regarding the service quality of AL Rayan bank. This result needs to be more consistent and refuted by several studies which stated that the more satisfied customers the more willing they are to use positive WoM in the service industry (Parasuraman et al, 1998; Shemwell, 1998; Soderlund, 1998). Moreover, (Kwun et, 2013; Purwandari, 2015) argued that service quality has a significant effect on WoM. This statement is supported by Rezvani and Safahani (2016); Suryaatmaja et al (2016); Rambe et al (2017). The previous studies are contradicted in this study, it is believed that service quality is a crucial factor in WoM in the service industry to enhance great value from customers which could lead to a positive reputation from customers to share with other people. Thus, it is significantly required for the firm to consider this issue to increase the value of the young generation of customer's view.

The Effect of Customer Satisfaction on Brand Experience and Word of Mouth.

The results indicated that customer satisfaction had an insignificant effect on brand experience. The clients who are satisfied with the products and services of Al Rayan Bank have less value for brand experience. It contradicts the existing studies which stated that there is a positive relationship between brand experience and customer satisfaction variable (Brakus et al, 2009; Ha and Perks, 2005).

The results showed that customer satisfaction has a substantial impact on WoM. Several scholars also are in accordance with previous research studies (Shirsavar et al, 2012; Soderlund, 1998; Ennew et al, 2000). If the customers are satisfied with the products or services of Islamic bank, it could lead to influence the use of WoM marketing tools to other people and share a good positive review regarding the product or service. The clients of this bank are satisfied with the service and tend to share their opinions with others.

The Role of Customer Satisfaction in Mediating Effect of Customer Perception on Brand Experience and Word of Mouth.

The results indicated that customer satisfaction had an insignificant effect on the customer perception of brand experience and WoM in terms of mediating variables. It shows that role of the satisfaction factor is not a mediator factor for Generation Z customers of Al Rayan Bank on brand experience and WoM variables. The role of customer satisfaction in between customers perception and brand experience is crucial to enhance the productivity of the business field, especially in banking service because if the customers are satisfied, it could lead to an excellent brand experience from customers' perception. However, the results of this study found an insignificant effect from the indirect effect of analysis. It is confirmed by previous literature. For example, Ebrahimi et al found that the effect of brand advantages on customer satisfaction and clients' behavioural loyalty aspect towards the Pars Khazar brand by testing the mediating concepts of a range of variables

(Ebrahimi et al, 2014). It indicated a positive relationship between symbolic and brand-oriented advantages and behavioural customers towards the brand. Moreover, in terms of this study, it is considerably needed that the company should improve and educate more young generation customers to feel satisfied with the service to enhance a remarkable brand experience value from customers' perception.

Furthermore, another result also found that the role of customer satisfaction in mediating variables of customer perception had an insignificant effect on WoM. It is believed that the company should increase and build satisfaction factors to obtain a high recommendation from customers to other people. Several scholars investigated strong empirical studies on the relationship between satisfaction and recommendation (Athanassopoulos et al, 2001; Ranaweera and Prabhu, 2003; Wirtz and Chew, 2002)). Moreover, Alizadeh (2018) investigated the effects of customer perception and satisfaction on WoM variables, with the results having significant factors among these variables. In addition, Bontis and Booker (2007) found that it is concluded that reputation from the customer perception aspect serves as a partial mediator of two links: customer satisfaction and recommendation in the banking sector.

The Role of Customer Satisfaction in Mediating Effect of CSR on Brand Experience and Word of Mouth.

The results showed that customer satisfaction had an insignificant effect of CSR on brand experience and WoM in terms of mediating variables. It shows that the role of the satisfaction factor is not the mediator variable factor from Generation Z customers of Al Rayan Bank on brand experience and WoM variables. It contradicts existing studies that CSR affects behavioural outcomes through direct or mediated path analysis and customer satisfaction is taken into account as an evaluative outcome of CSR (Brown and Dacin, 1997; Luo and Bhattacharya, 2006). In addition, Lee and Ho (2009) investigated how CSR may directly and indirectly affect the company's performance through various mediating aspects. Moreover, customer satisfaction is driven by the experience of the customer with the corporation and the information clients have in the form of corporate associations regarding the company (Davies et al, 2002). In addition, the satisfaction issue not only includes a cognitive component but also an emotional response towards a brand (del Bosque and Martin, 2008; Nam et al, 2011). In this result, the company should consider more education to young generation customers regarding CSR activities to increase a positive brand experience through customer satisfaction factor.

The role of customer satisfaction and culture as a moderator of the relationship between CSR and WoM (Hofstede, 2001). Several existing studies also found that CSR initiatives experienced by various stakeholders may assist in reducing transaction costs and positively influence the company not only the income but also a good reputation which affect customer attitude toward the company, satisfaction and loyalty factor (Becker-Olsen et al, 2006; Bhattacharya and Sen, 2003; Gardberg and Fombrun, 2006; Lacey et al, 2010).

The Role of Customer Satisfaction in Mediating Effect of Service Quality on Brand Experience and Word of Mouth.

The results showed that customer satisfaction had an insignificant indirect effect on service quality and brand experience in terms of mediating variables. It indicated that the role of customer satisfaction had yet to play an essential aspect in the brand experience of Generation Z customers. It contradicts existing literature such as (Spiros et al, 2010; Butt and Aftab, 2013; Moreira and Silva, 2015). The result indicated that the role of customer satisfaction is less and weakens the relationship of young customers of Al Rayan Bank between service quality provided by the bank. Therefore, it is considerably required that the bank should focus on this issue to improve from the customers' perspective.

Furthermore, service quality had a direct significant effect on WoM and an indirect effect through customer satisfaction. Therefore, the role of customer satisfaction played an important role in keeping clients of Generation Z and reducing the rates of switching to other banking services. So, the company wishing to achieve a competitive advantage through the customer satisfaction variable must focus on the determinants of clients' satisfaction for instance the service quality factor, by narrowing the gap between expectation and perception. The finding of this research is confirmed by several studies which assist the results of (Aljumaa, 2014; Puspasari, 2014; Paswan and Ganesha, 2009). Moreover, this indicator is the only one which had a positive indirect effect. It is essential to keep maintaining this issue to obtain an excellent reputation and long-term strategy, also impact on making new customers.

Restatement of Research Questions

As indicated in chapter one – Introduction, the research problem is addressed by four main questions, which are:

1. What is the main factor of Generation Z customers of Al Rayan Bank in the UK which influence the brand experience and Word of Mouth factor?
2. Does customers perception, CSR and Service quality affect customer satisfaction?
3. Does customers perception, CSR and Service quality affect brand experience and WoM?
4. Does customer satisfaction mediate variable of the customers perception, CSR and service quality on the brand experience and WoM?

Approaching these research questions were addressed by developing a theoretical framework that describes the relationship between customers perception of Islamic banking, CSR and service quality and customer satisfaction with Islamic banking, and in turn, its impact on the brand experience and Word of mouth. The quantitative approach is implemented in this research through which the research hypotheses are examined. The results of hypotheses testing provide various insights into the young consumer perspective of Al Rayan

Bank in the UK, in which the research is conducted. These insights help in reaching optimal answers to the research questions. The hypotheses testing results can be summed up in the following points:

- I. Customer perception of Islamic banking in Al Rayan Bank UK to the customer satisfaction with Islamic banking and brand experience also WoM factor. The customers perception elements predict brand experience significantly and positively, except for the customer satisfaction and WoM, which have no direct significant impact. Moreover, CSR has a significant positive impact on brand experience and a significant negative impact on customer satisfaction and WoM. In addition, service quality has a significant impact on customer satisfaction but a negative impact on brand experience and WoM. Furthermore, customer satisfaction has a significant impact on WoM but not on brand experience.
- II. The impact of service quality on WoM is the only variable which is enhanced by the mediating role of customer satisfaction with Islamic banking.

First Research Question

The first question examines the main factor of Generation Z customers of Al Rayan Bank in the UK. Addressing this question requires the identification of a few aspects to consider in this study. Several factors were provided to analyse the study such as fundamental customers perspective of Islamic banking knowledge, involving knowledge of the social responsibility of the company and the service quality of the bank. This acts as a preliminary step to operationalise the construct and examine their impact on the brand experience of Islamic banking and word of mouth aspect.

The literature revealed that branding and spread of WoM aspects are crucial strategies in the highly competitive industry for instance, in the banking service, as it enables differentiation and value creation. There are several primary factors of customers, especially for the young generation to measure whether they have significant experience with Islamic banking. Firstly, involving customer perception factor which includes several factors such as bank reputation, awareness of the Islamic banking system, relative advantage and perceived combability, these factors are believed that the fundamental issue to adopting Islamic banking (Ahmad and Haron, 2002; Gait and Worthington, 2008; Bisharat, 2014; Khattak and Rehman, 2010Keong et al, 2012; Thambiah et al, 2012; Thambiah et al, 2011; Echchabi and Aziz, 2012; Aziz et al, 2015; Ayinde and Echchabi, 2012; Amin et al, 2013). Secondly, it is crucial to involve one of the strategic marketing aspects in the banking industry to measure the Generation Z customers of Al Rayan Bank which is the CSR factor, it because this generation are expected to have a more positive attitude toward the environment, community, spirituality, justice and friendship comparing previous generation (Jain, Reshma, & Jagani, 2014, p.19, Arman, 2013). This generation is also concerned about the CSR issues. In addition, In Islam, CSR is more

likely related and embedded in fundamental Islamic teachings and shariah is core to understanding CSR in Islam (Dusuki, 2008; Jusoh et al, 2015;).

Thirdly, another variable involved in this research is service quality. In terms of the banking sector, service quality is dominant mainly in considering every bank for concerning customers perspective (Allred and Addams, 2000). Generation Z is shown different financial needs and expectations compared to other generations. This generation of customer expects a more substantial banking experience and better quality of service, beyond other factors such as fee and rate considerations. In addition, this customer would have efficient transaction processing, better functionality, ease of access to relevant information and a more comprehensive range and personalisation of goods and services (Kaabchi et al, 2022). Therefore, the main research found all independent variables such as customer perception, CSR and service quality are able to explain the dependent variables (brand experience and WoM) with the R-square value 0.653 (65.3%) and 0.116 (11.6%) respectively. Moreover, all variables are also sufficient for the criteria of discriminant validity, in which the constructs all variables are > 0.50 and the composite reliability and Cronbach alpha, all variables are significantly acceptable of composite reliability and Cronbach's alpha.

To sum up, research question one, involving variables such as customer perception of Islamic banking, CSR and service quality is considered important to get a better understanding of perspectives from Generation Z customers Al Rayan to analyse the brand experience and WoM factor.

Second Research Question

The second research question indicates an answer regarding the testing between independent variables (customer perception, CSR and service quality) and mediating variables (customer satisfaction). The literature suggested numerous researchers found a relationship between customer perception of Islamic banking and customer satisfaction. Customer perception is an antecedent of customer satisfaction (El-Adly, 2019; Karjaluto et al, 2019; Itani et al, 2019; Chang and Wang, 2011; Eid and Gohary, 2015). According to Singh and Kaur (2011) customers consider the immense perceived value of service when they feel that facilities have provided more than they expected, which leads to be satisfied. In fact, Dhurup et al (2014) found that several aspects of customer perception of banking services have a positive impact on customer satisfaction. The main study of this research found that the relationship between customer perception of Islamic banking and customer satisfaction has an insignificant effect with a negative correlation coefficient of -0.171. This is indicated by the value of t statistic ($1.369 < 1.661$) and p-value ($0.172 > 0.05$).

The second independent variable (CSR). It is believed that in the current business era of banking, banks are taking into account the crucial of ethical standards through social responsibility (Lockett et al, 2006). It is composed of economic, social and environmental dimensions (Chocolakova et al, 2015). Thus, it is vital that the banking industry especially Islamic banks to consider two factors, financial and non-financial in the

banking industry and enhance the transparency of CSR activities (Yeung, 2011). The result of the study indicated that the contradiction from several existing literature which found there is a significant effect between CSR and customer satisfaction (Ashraf et al, 2017; Chung et al, 2015; Qamar, 2016). The results demonstrated that there is no significant effect on Customer Satisfaction with a positive correlation coefficient of 0.197. This is indicated by the value of t statistics ($1.718 > 1.661$) and p values ($0.086 > 0.05$).

Another variable which is service quality. In the modern era of business, numerous banking companies are significantly considered to improve service quality in strategic policy. Anand and Selvaraj (2012) enhancing the service quality aspect in the business could improve customer satisfaction in a certain period and there is a correlation between them. Awan et al (2011) highlighted that service quality in the Islamic banking industry can improve customer satisfaction because the clients tend to react something when they feel satisfied with the product and service. The results of the research are in line with existing studies (Keng et al, 2013; Brakus et al, 2009), confirming that this variable positively influenced the satisfaction of Generation Z customers of Al Rayan Bank in the UK. The main study found that Service Quality has a positive and significant effect on Customer Satisfaction with a positive correlation coefficient of 0.602. This is indicated by the value of t statistics ($7.413 > 1.661$) and p values ($0.000 < 0.05$). Therefore, the Service Quality variable is the only one from the independent variables which has a significant effect on Customer Satisfaction.

Third Research Question

The third research question finds an answer regarding the testing between independent variables (customer perception, CSR and service quality) and dependent variables (brand experience and word of mouth). Firstly, the previous literature indicated that the concept of engagement is understood as a motivational model which motivates an individual toward a brand (Sprott et al, 2009). Brakus et al (2009) highlight that brand experience is related to sensation, behaviour, cognition and feeling evoked by brand stimuli. According to Nysveen and Pedersen (2014) explaining customer perception of banking on brand experience is to create positive sensory brand experiences. Co-creation participation has to stimulate customer's senses in exciting and preferably appealing ways and engage clients in the brand. It is believed that customer perception of Islamic banking is an important factor to lead an excellent experience with the specific brand. The results of this study indicated that customer Perception variable has a positive and significant effect on Brand Experience with a positive correlation coefficient of 0.389. This is indicated by the value of t statistics ($4.904 > 1.666$) and p values ($0.000 < 0.05$). Therefore, the Customer Perception variable has a significant effect on Brand Experience.

Secondly, CSR has a crucial impact on brand experience especially in the banking industry. It is related to a branded model including numerous factors of a brand which might be reporting of CSR activities in the form of environmental initiatives, sustainable supply chain, new schools or universities in remote areas and social welfare activities. Several scholars have highlighted CSR communication on consumer responses and brand

evaluation (Brown and Dacin, 1997; Luo and Bhattacharaya, 2006; Melo and Galan, 2011). It is believed that CSR activities should exist in the business field, especially in the Islamic banking sector, because it also relates to ethic and provides the customers with a positive experience. Moreover, based on the results of this study which are in line with previous research, CSR has a positive and significant effect on Brand Experience with a positive correlation coefficient of 0.469. This is indicated by the value of t statistics ($5.993 > 1.661$) and p values ($0.000 < 0.05$). Therefore, the Corporate Social Responsibility variable has a significant effect on Brand Experience.

Thirdly, service quality factors on brand experience. The customers experience in the past with a particular brand has the ability to influence clients' expectations of a service or offering provided by the brand, especially in the banking sector. It is important to draw attention to the possible interrelationship between service quality and brand experience. According to Edvardsson (2005) contemporary service quality is focused on favourable customer experience. However, the study results found that service quality has no significant effect on Brand Experience with a positive correlation coefficient of 0.100. This is indicated by the value of t statistics ($1,536 < 1.661$) and p values ($0.125 > 0.05$). Therefore, the service quality variable does not affect brand experience.

Fourth, customer perception relates to how the customer values the usefulness of a goods or service, considering the benefits received and the sacrifice made to get the product or service (Zeithaml, 1988). The importance of the WoM factor in shaping customers' attitudes and buying decisions led many studies to investigate within various industries, especially in the banking sector. In fact, when the clients feel that they have received good value and experience, they commit to the corporation and spread positive information to other people in their reference group which leads to loyalty with the particular company (McKee et al, 2006). However, the results of the study found that customer perception has no significant effect on Word of Mouth with a positive correlation coefficient of 0.155. This is indicated by the value of t statistics ($0.903 < 1.661$) and p values ($0.367 > 0.05$). Therefore. The customer perception variable has no effect on WoM.

Fifth, the effect of CSR on WoM. Combining these two variables in banking is significantly crucial for the business. CSR activities increase the company's visibility and it encourages more communication with the clients. Thus, it is expected that a company's engagement in CSR initiatives is likely to induce positive WoM on the part of clients (Schaefer et al, 2019). In fact, CSR initiatives of a bank assist in inducing WoM for that bank from clients in the banking sector (Cheng et al, 2021). Moreover, clients expect that a responsible corporation will provide them with quality goods and services while paying attention to their social responsibility initiatives (Kuokkanen and Sun, 2020). Consequently, the customers have a remarkable impact on the particular banking industry to spread positive information when they engage in CSR activities especially for young customers. However, the results of the study found a contradiction from existing

literature which CSR has no significant effect on Word of Mouth with a positive correlation coefficient of 0.102. This is indicated by the value of t statistics ($0.714 < 1.661$) and p values ($0.475 > 0.05$). Therefore, the Corporate Social Responsibility variable has no effect on WoM.

The last variable is service quality on WoM. It is believed that the better a corporation's service quality performance, the higher the propensity to engage in positive WoM and also impact the loyalty customers toward the company. According to Saha and Theingi (2009) the clients' evaluation of service quality is based on whether the service quality they received was in line with consumer expectations before receiving the service. Moreover, the process of WoM occurs when the customers post-purchase with an impression, feeling or experience. As a result, positive opinions regarding the specific company could share with other people. Therefore, positive of service quality will increase the positive WoM. Furthermore, the results of this study found a contradiction from the previous study which service quality has no significant effect on Word of Mouth with a negative correlation coefficient of -0.099. This is indicated by the value of t statistics ($0.176 < 1.661$) and p values ($0.861 > 0.05$). Therefore, the service quality variable has no effect on WoM.

The main results of the study above highlight to answer research question three. The results show the examination between independent variables and dependent variables, and it found that only several variables have a positive relationship for Generation Z customers of Al Rayan Bank in the UK.

Fourth Research Question

The Last research question of the study is to examine the role of customer satisfaction is emphasised through its direct impact as an important variable to brand experience and WoM and mediating relationship of customer satisfaction, CSR and service quality and brand experience and WoM. It is believed that the factor of customer satisfaction in the banking industry is crucial to lead brand experience and WoM aspect. Firstly, customer satisfaction is the clients' behaviour grounded on global practice and that can be regarded in two behaviours "transaction-specific outcome or cumulative evaluation" (Wang et al, 2004). The satisfaction factor is considered to be closely related to customer perception in banking service, an overall service evaluation. It is believed that customer perception of banking service can significantly relate to brand experience through customer satisfaction. Customers who are satisfied with a particular brand can lead to have a positive experience with a firm. The results of the study highlighted that based on the correlation coefficient of the indirect influence of the Customer Perception variable on Brand Experience, which is 0.002 with a t statistic value ($0.139 < 1.661$) and p values ($0.890 > 0.05$) which means it is not significant. Therefore, Customer Perception has no effect on Brand Experience mediated by Customer Satisfaction.

Secondly, Davies et al (2002) highlight that customer satisfaction is driven by the experience with the specific company and the information client has in the form of corporate associations regarding the company. The satisfaction variable not only includes cognitive components but also emotional responses towards a brand

(del Bosque and Martin, 2008; Nam et al, 2011). It is indicated that relating to responsible behaviour, a company can obtain the support of its stakeholders which might contribute towards making a strong and unique brand affiliation (Keller, 1993). In addition, it impacts on positive brand experience of clients will enhance their trust in the brand (Kim et al, 2015). The results of this study found that based on the correlation coefficient of the indirect influence of the CSR variable on Brand Experience, which is 0.002 with a t statistic value ($0.150 < 1.661$) and p values ($0.881 > 0.05$) which means it is not significant. Therefore, CSR has no effect on Brand Experience mediated by Customer Satisfaction.

Thirdly, service quality is a crucial factor for the company, especially in the banking sector. It is based on the abilities of the company to continually meet the requirements and desires of the regulars (Parasuraman et al, 1988). If the company reaches that level of requirements, the customers are more likely to be satisfied. Zins (2001) in the branding perspective, clients have no substitutes or they have high-level personal characteristics with the specific brand. A brand can fulfil its customers need through customer satisfaction in regard to products or service which a company offers. This study indicated that the results were based on the correlation coefficient of the indirect influence of the Service Quality variable on Brand Experience, namely -0.006 with t statistics ($0.172 < 1.661$) and p values ($0.863 > 0.05$) which means it is not significant. Therefore, Service Quality has no effect on Brand Experience mediated by Customer Satisfaction.

Fourthly, Customer's perception is a fundamental aspect of customers gaining satisfaction which might contribute to the WoM factor in banking service. It is believed that customer satisfaction is deemed as one of the important concepts for justifying WoM based on customer perception. Moreover, customer perception is defined as the assessment of the overall consumer against the utilities of a product or service based on what they received or what is obtained (Lubis et al, 2021). It assists in providing a positive perception and appear a sense of customer satisfaction from the customers perspective. As a result, the customers tend to spread positive thoughts or opinions regarding the service to other people. In fact, the results of the study found a contradiction toward the Generation Z of Al Rayan Bank in the UK which indicated based on the correlation coefficient of the indirect influence of the Customer Perception variable on Word of mouth, namely -0.047 with a value of t statistics ($1.018 < 1.661$) and p values ($0.309 > 0.05$) which means not significant. Therefore, Customer Perception has no effect on Word of mouth mediated by Customer Satisfaction.

Fifthly, the satisfaction factor might account for the psychological mechanism through which CSR affects customer behaviour, however, this claim remains to be determined. Company identification, a form of psychological attachment, occurs when clients adopt the defining characteristics of the company as defining characteristics for themselves (Dutton et al, 1994). When clients perceive the company's implementation of social responsibility behaviour, they form positive images which increase business identification and positively affect related outcomes. Therefore, satisfaction in turn, translates into developed WoM behaviour,

suggesting that the customer satisfaction factor mediates between variables of CSR and WoM (Walsh and Bartikowski, 2013). The results of this study highlighted that the correlation coefficient of the indirect influence of the Corporate Social Responsibility variable on Word of mouth, which is 0.055 with a value of t statistics ($1.184 < 1.661$) and p values ($0.237 > 0.05$) which means it is not significant. Therefore, Corporate Social Responsibility does not affect Word of mouth mediated by Customer Satisfaction.

Lastly, service quality is argued to be an antecedent variable of satisfaction in the banking sector (Chu et al, 2012). Specifically, higher service quality tends to increase customer satisfaction (Baker and Crompton, 2000; Bigne et al, 2003). Service quality is defined as the gap between clients' expectations of service that the customers received from the company. As a result, it could impact positive experiences and share or recommend to other people regarding the specific company. The results of this study argued that based on the correlation coefficient of the indirect effect of the Service Quality variable on Word of mouth, namely 0.166 with a value of t statistics ($2.018 > 1.661$) and p values ($0.044 < 0.05$) which means that it has a significant effect. Therefore, Service Quality has a significant effect on Word of mouth mediated by Customer Satisfaction.

The most prominent finding to emerge from this study regarding the mediation variable is service quality on WoM, the only variable which has a positive indirect relationship with customer satisfaction.

CHAPTER VI

Conclusion

The Islamic finance sector in the UK has emerged as a crucial area of opportunity and importance within the financial service sector in current years. It could be seen that a financial hub in London provides an excellent starting point for growing Islamic financial institutions in a Western economic system and there is yet more room to develop this sector (TheCityUK, 2017). The main aim of the research is to analyse and examine factors that influence customers perception of Islamic banking service, corporate social responsibility and service quality on satisfaction, brand experience and WoM, which is influenced by customer satisfaction from Generation Z Al Rayan Bank in the UK perspective.

One hundred participants answered all the questions thoroughly to test the research hypothesis. The results indicated that a few variables had a positive and significant effect in this study such as (H2) customer perception on brand experience, CSR on brand experience (H5), service quality on customer satisfaction (H7) and customer satisfaction on WoM (H11). In addition, the customer satisfaction variable mediates the effect of service quality on WoM, whereas the rest hypothesis of this research had an insignificant effect between variables. Having an insignificant effect on other variables does not mean that variables have no relationship to customer satisfaction, brand experience and WoM at all. Instead, it means this dimension of the variable does not significantly affect this particular study from Generation Z customers of Al Rayan Bank in the UK. Furthermore, this could be due to several reasons that the corporate structure of the case bank does not support better implementation of adopting banking, CSR and service quality practices. For instance, the company should focus more on the satisfaction aspect and pay more attention to Generation Z customers of Al Rayan Bank in the UK.

In the modern era of business, it is believed that using the advantages of technology is one of the main crucial factors in enhancing the effectiveness of the business, especially in the banking sector and among young generation customers. WoM is one of the significant aspects of marketing tools, and the dynamic virtual environment has given much power to clients in spreading the customers' opinions. Consequently, alerting the corporation to focus more on taking care of the customers' satisfaction factor will appear to other perception regarding the product or service the company. Moreover, brand experience is one of the fundamental aspects of the marketing perspective in the business field. Having excellent satisfaction issues with the customers, it might lead to an excellent brand experience (Brakus et al, 2009; McAlexander et al, 2003).

CSR aspect is also one of the main considered by Islamic banking institutions. CSR activity contributed to a better understanding positively influence on brand experience but no other dependent variables. It is believed that CSR activities should build strong and lasting connections with clients, especially with the young

generation in the banking industry, because it might impact the long-term marketing strategy. An increasing level of customer satisfaction is significantly required for this generation of customers to attract and retain clients. While the customers are satisfied with the service, it could appear to be a remarkable brand experience, and the WoM strategy will be successfully implemented from the customers' perception. Therefore, it builds an excellent bank reputation from the customers' perspective into a long-term strategy. Moreover, in terms of improvement from the bank side, Chapra (2000) stated that Islamic finance institutions should improve further to show Islamic value which not only focuses on social issue but also on political, legal and economic institutions.

Furthermore, the service quality aspect is also one of the crucial issues which the company considers for the young generation customers. The results indicated that service quality had a less critical aspect to dependent variables such as brand experience and WoM except for customer satisfaction which had a positive effect on it. Schmitt (2003) argues that providing a powerful and compelling customer experience could set customers apart from competitors in a way that focusing on simple satisfaction never will. It is essential to improve the service personnel's willingness to assist clients and to offer prompt service for the most crucial consideration clients emphasise in banking service for this generation to achieve a great experience and implement WoM strategy to communicate with other people regarding the service of AL Rayan bank in the UK.

To sum up the research, it is highly recommended that Islamic banking corporations increase many sectors of marketing aspect to young generation customers such as improving the service to achieve great experience and excellent reputation. Creating an excellent relationship is one of the considered aspects of the company to attract, a great experience and retain young customers with economic value by increasing customer satisfaction aspect in a competitive advantage perspective to other financial institutions, especially conventional systems.

Implications

Theoretical Implications

Several theoretical implications have been raised based in findings reported in the previous chapter. The most important theoretical contribution of this research is in extending the body of service marketing literature with regard to the study of customer behaviour in Islamic bank service, especially in the UK context, where there is no such research conducted before. This research focused on the existing academy literature regarding marketing aspects, consumer behaviour, customer perception, CSR, service quality, satisfaction, branding, WoM and related these concepts with one of the Islamic banking systems in the UK (Al Rayan) sector. As suggested by previous studies (Abu, 2015; Ebrahimi et al, 2014; Alizadeh, 2018; Luo and Bhattacharya, 2006; Moreira and Silva, 2015) this study provides a more comprehensive and complex aspect of consumer behaviour. Moreover, it is indicated that the theoretical framework developed in this research is the first

methodology initiative in the banking sector which involves six crucial marketing models to examine in a single framework simultaneously. As a result, this research involves the main of consumer behaviour factors in the Islamic banking sector from the perspective of the Generation Z customers of Al Rayan Bank in the UK.

The second theoretical contribution of this research is identified to the role of customer satisfaction in mediating service quality on WoM in the Islamic banking sector. While no direct link between service quality and WoM is present, the results indicate that service quality has only an indirect influence on WoM, unlike several studies on different sectors that have indicated service quality influences WoM directly (Macintosh, 2007; Arasli et al, 2005; Kwun et, 2013; Purwandari, 2015; Rezvani and Safahani, 2016; Suryaatmaja et al, 2016; Rambe et al, 2017). The current result includes support for the notion that customer satisfaction indicates a mediating role in the relationship between service quality and WoM (Gupta and Pirsch, 2008; Reimann et al, 2008). This study suggests that young generation customers who perceive that their bank offers a high service quality may not automatically spread positive WoM opinions to other people. The Islamic bank may be required to include other incentives to increase satisfaction aspect. Moreover, this result implies that the link between service quality and WoM is not a straightforward one, it might provide customer satisfaction as a mediating aspect.

The third theoretical contribution of this research to indicate the relationship among all variables of this study. The empirical evidence in this research highlights that service quality is the only one with a direct positive relationship with customer satisfaction and service quality is the most vital driver of customer satisfaction. Followed by CSR on brand experience, Customer perception on brand experience and customer satisfaction on WoM in the Islamic banking sector. It is believed that customer satisfaction is a crucial aspect in the banking sector which could impact other factors such as excellent brand experience and spread positive WoM. According to Reichheld (1993) customer satisfaction is more likely to be the main focus of business with one specific bank. Moreover, the results indicate that service quality could be a source of competitive and sustainable advantage for an Islamic bank because it is difficult to imitate, unlike the service range or goods that could easily be replicated. It is believed that this variable has a crucial aspect to competitive advancement with commonly undifferentiated and homogenous goods being offered in the banking industry (Mandhacitara and Poolthong, 2011; Kumar et al, 2010). The current research also extends the evidence on the relationship between all variables frameworks in the Islamic banking sector, especially in the UK.

This research has also contributed to the knowledge in the field of Generation Z. it has identified to understand the way customers of Generation Z behave toward their Islamic bank and how their perspective and branding issues of their financial corporation. The research found out that despite this generation being stereotyped as iGeneration, Post-millennials, Gen Wii or NextGen (Raphelson, 2014; Turner,2015). Ernst and Young (2017)

stated that this generation emphasises digital natives and is significantly different from the previous generation. This is a generalisation and the behaviour of this generational cohort differs from nation to nation.

Managerial Implications

The empirical findings of this study hold strategic implications for managers and decision-makers in the Islamic banking industry in the UK, especially for Al Rayan Bank in the UK. Several dimensions of marketing variables are observed in this research such as measuring customer perception, CSR and service quality as antecedent variables on customer brand experience and WoM factor as outcomes. In addition, it examines the role of customer satisfaction as a mediating variable between independent variables and dependent variables. The results indicated there are several indicators that had an insignificant effect on the variables. Hence, the managerial implication is one of the best ways to provide for marketing practitioners and managers who design strategic plans and implement tools to improve the performance of the service of Islamic banks, especially Al Rayan Bank in the UK.

First and foremost, the knowledge of the antecedent of customer perception towards Islamic banking. The company should be more focused on concerning customers and the awareness aspect of the young generation because the results found that these points are less considered which made the clients less satisfied and less impacted on WoM aspect. As a result, the customers tend to less give the information regarding this bank service to other people. It is also required to share or give more knowledge to Generation Z regarding the difference between conventional banking and the Shariah banking system. Moreover, numerous development strategies and actions should be implemented to increase an excellent perception of these customers such as concerning and attracting more to this generation regarding the service, giving knowledge to this customer regarding Islamic finance. Consequently, the customers could increase positive brand experience to this bank and spread positive WoM aspects toward other people in the near future.

Secondly, the CSR aspect is also one of the crucial issues that the company will improve in the near future. This research considers three key performance outcomes in service marketing outcomes from CSR indicators such as customer satisfaction, brand experience and WoM. Among these outcomes, the customers had an insignificant effect on customer satisfaction and the WoM factor. Hence, several strategies should be taken into account from a managerial perspective. With respect to investing more in CSR initiatives, it should be determined by the company to achieve vital satisfaction aspect from young generation customers. It is believed that involving more CSR activities for the young generation is considerably required to gain best practices in their perspective such as Islamic banks should contribute more to the local communities, schools or universities and other organisations. Moreover, banks should bear in mind that young customers are more likely motivated by all CSR activities when evaluating corporate strategies. Based on the results, there is a need for managers to formulate business strategies which involve young customers' commitment to ethical

behaviour towards the environment and social inclusion initiatives as well as financing of Eco-sustainable projects. The strategy can assist in achieving competitive advantages as well as developing a corporate brand which helps the young customers the opportunity to choose based on bank's attributes. Moreover, the managers should consider paying attention more to Generation Z customers and invest more in CSR activities since the customers are concerned about the environment.

Thirdly, the results showed that service quality level had a positive effect on customer satisfaction. Generation Z customers are satisfied with the service quality of Al Rayan Bank in the UK. However, they had an insignificant effect on brand experience and WoM aspects. Hence, the company should take into account this issue to increase the best service to deliver to the young generation. Creating a great relationship with customers is significantly required for long-term strategy issues. To remain competitive in the market, Islamic finance requires paying more attention to the way the service is delivered to the clients, especially to the young generation. Improving well-trained staff is also one of the considerably required to obtain better service and to add value across the customer journey. The staff should be more attentive, take care and initiative to help customers. It is also simplifying organisational structures to enhance consistency with the staff. In addition, enhancing the service is most important to obtain a great experience from customers and Islamic banks should identify different clients' needs and work to fulfil such requirements. The company should consider beyond technical skills to possess soft skills, for instance, communication skills and interpersonal skills, to make sure better customer satisfaction level and brand experience. Furthermore, the company should also leverage appropriate modern technology to develop a new digitalised system that matches the client's level of expectation with the new system to obtain a better perspective from the young generation. Therefore, it is believed that the company should be more considerate of the service quality aspects to have a better brand experience from the customers and it could impact better WoM aspect to share great experience in terms of Islamic banking for other people.

Moreover, it is considerably required to improve the brand experience aspect for customers. Bank managers should induce better feelings among clients to maintain their preference towards the bank. More dedication is needed from Bank Prepositive to understand the clients' need and offer them a better feeling through a comfortable atmosphere and friendly dealing with the clients, especially the young generation. In addition, it is expected that the firm should have such an attitude towards clients which could assist in maintaining better customer relations. Consequently, for long-terms impact, it will receive a remarkable value from customers and in the end, the customers could share their opinions with positive feedback to others.

Furthermore, in the highly competitive banking industry, especially in the UK market. This research should benefit for all UK Islamic banking corporations because the model provides valuable information for understanding the process of building and maintaining relationships with bank clients, specifically for young

generation. In addition, in order to control the factor of clients' to promote and share to other people regarding the banking service. It is imperative that banks periodically measure their customers' behaviour. The challenge for banks is to carefully manage the drivers of behavioural aspects better than their competitors, especially for the young generation. This is because market perception and client expectations can change quickly from time to time. In the modern era, a transformation of the banking system has changed slightly from traditional to electronic, and it is believed that it can develop more shortly. For instance, in this research, the satisfaction factor was identified as a predictor of WoM as well as acting as a significant mediating in the link between service quality and WoM. Therefore, bank managers should monitor the progress of customer satisfaction levels among their young generation customers to reduce situations earlier that could generate dissatisfaction.

Limitation

It is believed that the research may give a better result if some limitations do not appear in the research field. For instance, the study implemented a questionnaire concept among numerous survey data collection techniques in a Cross-sectional time horizon, which is less time-consuming. One of the significant limitations of this research is the small data collection which is just focused on the Generation Z customers' perspective and analysed only one of the banks' Islamic financial institutions. Due to this shortcoming, there is a possibility of an undetected bias subtly to get a better result in a future study and hence, generalisation may not be applicable to other industries. The findings, whilst exciting and unique for the area of research, are not substantial as they do not represent the whole nation well in the Islamic banking market. Consequently, more time-consuming and also financial resources are considered for the ability to complete a more significant size of research.

Furthermore, the study was carried out in a single service industry, Al Rayan Bank in the UK, which indicated that findings are limited to this industry. However, this argument has remained consistent with recent calls within service marketing literature that argued for building contextual marketing knowledge in a specific industry because of particular industry characteristics. In addition, this study focuses on one of the banking systems and does not compare other financial systems to measure. It is considerably required to analyse from both perspectives to obtain a better understating of this industry. Another limitation is delivered to this study: this study only applied quantitative data collection from the customers perspectives. It is better to analyse qualitative data collection and also analyse from company's view, such as staff or manager of Islamic banking. In addition, it is considered that including the non-use of religious associations as part of the participants, which may be biased results and semi-structured interviews for Generation Z customers should be implemented to get a better understanding and verify some of the results.

Recommendations

There are several recommendations to address from this research. It is common that every study has its own problem and solutions appear accordingly to resolve for better understanding in future research. This research study permits a significant recommendation for the marketing field in the Islamic banking sector. As the same time, it would be desirable to see further research on the moderating impact on customer satisfaction in the Islamic banking sector in the UK. In order to achieve better quality of the research for future study, several recommendations are as follows:

First, this research only focuses on the Generation Z customers, which makes a narrow analysis from the customers' perspective. Further research suggests into the same areas as this study would be hugely beneficial as this research has only covered a small part of the UK market and cannot be considered entirely representative of the country. In addition, more samples should be implemented in future research.

Second, based on the results hypothesis of the study. it is identified that there is a gap in the Islamic banking system in the UK to Generation Z customers in supporting and enhancing marketing strategy. It showed that several variables had insignificant effects.

Third, it is recommended that the bank should emphasise providing and implementing customer relationship marketing to build better service and reputation. In addition, adding some other antecedent variables is also recommended, such as brand image, customer retention and customer loyalty. As this study is conducted in one country and specifically in the banking industry, perhaps other sectors should also be considered to make it more promising and generalisable.

Fourth, research in the future may explore the possibilities beyond the central mediating concept established in the present research by testing the existence of other variables and their potential effect on the relationships discussed and demonstrated here.

Fifth, this study just implemented quantitative methods, and it is recommended to conduct the relationship of these variables using qualitative or mixed research design methods to obtain a better analysis. In addition, implementing an interview method to customers could have more personal experience with the corporation to improve the credibility of the findings.

Sixth, it is suggested that for future analysis of another finance system such as, conventional to determine and analyse a better understanding to Generation Z customers.

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Appendices

Appendix I: Ethics Approval

01/04/2022

Dear Ahmad Zulfakar,

Your application 17078: The Impact of Islamic Banking on Generation Z: A Study of Al Rayan Bank in the United Kingdom, submission 15047, has been approved by the Business and Creative Industries SEC . You may now proceed with your study. If you wish to make any significant changes to the study you must seek the committee's approval before actioning them.

Good luck with your research.

Dr John Quinn

Appendix II: Questionnaire

Dear Participants,

I am Ahmad Zulfakar and I am conducting a research study as part of the partial fulfilment of my doctoral studies at the University of West of Scotland, under the supervision of Dr. Achilleas Boukis.

I am inviting you to participate in this research study by completing the attached survey. The primary purpose of the study is to “The Impact of Islamic Banking on Generation Z: A Study of Al Rayan Bank in the United Kingdom”.

The attached questionnaire shall not take more than around 10 minutes to complete. **Your participation is completely voluntary and you can choose not to participate in part or all of the project.**

You can withdraw at any stage of the project without being penalised or disadvantaged in any way. All the responses are anonymous.

All information collected about you will only be considered for the purpose of this study. It will be kept strictly confidential and your confidentiality, privacy and anonymity will be ensured in the collection, storage and publication of this research material and not shared with others.

This study has been analyzed by the UWS committee on research ethics and is affirmed to conform with the principles of research ethics and integrity.

Your participation and contribution is extremely valued. Please feel free to contact me for any further information regarding the study at [REDACTED] You can also contact my supervisor at [REDACTED]

Sincerely,

Ahmad Zulfakar
Doctoral Researcher
University of the West of Scotland

Consent Form

I, the undersigned, confirm that (Please tick the box as appropriate)

1	I have read and understood the information about the project as provided in the information sheet dated _____	<input type="checkbox"/>
2	I have been given the opportunity to ask questions about the project and my participation	<input type="checkbox"/>
3	I voluntarily agree to participate in the project	<input type="checkbox"/>
4	I understand that I can withdraw at any time without giving reasons and that I will not be penalised for withdrawing nor will I be questioned on why I have withdrawn	<input type="checkbox"/>
5	The procedures regarding confidentiality have been clearly explained (e.g. use of pseudonyms, anonymisation of data, use of surname etc.) to me	<input type="checkbox"/>
6	If applicable, separate terms of consent for interviews, audio, video, or other forms of data collection have been explained and provided to me	<input type="checkbox"/>
7	The use of data in research, publications, sharing and archiving has been explained to me	<input type="checkbox"/>
8	I understand that other researchers will have access to this data only if they agree to preserve the confidentiality of the data and if they agree to the terms I have specified in this form	<input type="checkbox"/>
9	I, along with the researcher, agree to sign and date this informed consent form	<input type="checkbox"/>

The Questionnaire

1. Do you have Al Rayan bank account in the UK?

Yes No

2. Are you Z generation (16-24 years old)?

Yes No

Note: (If your answer is YES to both 2 questions above, please complete the rest questions)

Please rate the extent to which you agree to disagree with the statements below about Islamic bank.

- Strongly disagree = 1 Disagree = 2 Somewhat disagree = 3 Neither
- agree or disagree = 4 Somewhat agree = 5 Agree = 6
- Strongly agree = 7

Section 1

Customer's Perception								
No		1	2	3	4	5	6	7
1	I believe Al Rayan bank has a good reputation							
2	I Trust this bank is known to be concerned about customers							
3	I am aware of the instruments used in financing products Islamic bank offer such as <i>Mudaraba</i>							
4	I am aware about the differences between the conventional banking system and Islamic banking system							
5	Investments are more secure in Islamic banks							
6	Islamic banks are more profitable comparing with the interest in traditional bank (better returns)							
7	Islamic banking is in line with my values							
8	Islamic banking is well suited to my lifestyle							

Section 2

Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR)								
No		1	2	3	4	5	6	7
9	I trust Al Rayan bank is socially responsible							
10	I am aware this bank does donation to charities							
11	I believe this contributes to the welfare of society							

12	I believe this bank sharing best practise on social responsibility with other organisations							
13	I am aware Islamic financial collaborating with local schools, colleges, universities							
14	I am aware this bank does sponsorship of community events							
15	I trust Islamic banks do supporting employee's involvement with society or community							
16	Al Rayan bank does investment in research and development in society							
17	This bank does scholarship to students							

Section 3

Service Quality								
	Empathy	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
18	AL Rayan staff give individual attention to customer							
19	I am aware this bank services's do deal customer with care							
20	The staff understand the specific needs of customer							
21	I believe all staff having problem solving attitude in this bank							
	Responsive							
22	This bank provides prompt services and quick service to customers							
23	Willing to help our customers							
24	Always keep customer informed							
	Reliable							

25	This bank provides service as promised								
26	When I have problem, the bank shows a sincere interest in solving it								
27	The bank performs the service right the first time								
28	Providing correct /accurate information to our customers								
	Assurance								
29	Customers' behaviour in still confidence								
30	Al Rayan employees' give confidence to customers								
31	This bank employees are knowledgeable and efficient								
32	Feeling safe in transaction								
33	Keep confidentially of client information								
	Tangible								
34	Modern equipment are used in Al Rayan bank								
35	Employees have professional appearance								
36	Employees are dress well in this bank								

Section 4

Customer Satisfaction									
		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	
37	Al Rayan bank is exactly what I need								
38	The bank gives the service very well								
39	Overall I am satisfied with the services of the Al Rayan bank								
40	This Bank meets my expectations								

Section 5

Brand Experience

		1	2	3	4	5	6	7
41	The brand of Al Rayan bank induces feeling and sentiments							
42	I have strong emotion for the brand of this bank							
43	I feel special experience when I see the brand of this bank							
44	The brand of this bank is an action oriented							
45	The brand of this bank appeals to my sense							

Section 6

Word of Mouth (WoM)								
		1	2	3	4	5	6	7
46	I will talk about the strengths of the Al Rayan bank with people I know							
47	When I talk about bank to other people, I will tell positive story for this bank							
48	If people ask me about Islamic bank, I will definitely recommend this bank							
49	I would recommend this bank to others on social media							
50	I would recommend and encourage people to use this bank based on the bank reputation							

Demographic background

1. What is your gender?
 - Male
 - Female
 - Prefer not to say
2. What is your education background?
 - PMR/LCE or below (Higher Scholl certificate)
 - SPM/STPM/MCE/HSC/GCSE O level
 - Certificate/Diploma (or A level)
 - Degree/Professional certificate
 - Postgraduate (MBA, Masters and PhD)

Others

3. What is your Occupation?

Student

Service Occupations

Health and Social care

Sales

Business and Public service

Construction and building trades

Science and engineering professional

Other

Appendix III: Smart PLS Report

SmartPLS Report

Please cite the use of SmartPLS: Ringle, C. M., Wende, S., and Becker, J.-M. 2015. "Sma

Complete

Final Results

Path Coefficients

[show](#)

Indirect Effects

[show](#)

Total Effects

[show](#)

Outer Loadings

[show](#)

Outer Weights

[show](#)

Latent Variable

[show](#)

Residuals

[show](#)

Quality Criteria

R Square

[show](#)

f Square

[show](#)

Construct Reliability and Validity

[show](#)

Discriminant Validity

[show](#)

Collinearity Statistics (VIF)

[show](#)

Model_Fit

[show](#)

Model Selection Criteria

[show](#)

Interim Results

Stop Criterion Changes

[show](#)

Base Data

Setting

[show](#)

Inner Model

[show](#)

Outer Model

[show](#)

Indicator Data (Original)

[show](#)

Indicator Data (Standardized)

[show](#)

Indicator Data (Correlations)

[show](#)

rtPLS 3." Boeningstedt: SmartPLS GmbH, <http://www.smartpls.com>.

SmartPLS Report

Please cite the use of SmartPLS: Ringle, C. M., Wende, S., and Becker, J.-M. 2011
[back to navigation](#)

Final Results

Path Coefficients

	X1	X2	X3	Y1
X1				0.388
X2				0.467
X3				0.106
Y1				
Y2				
Z1				-0.017

Indirect Effects

Total Indirect Effects

	X1	X2	X3	Y1
X1				0.003
X2				-0.003
X3				-0.010
Y1				
Y2				
Z1				

Specific Indirect Effects

	Specific Indirect Effects
X1 -> Z1 -> Y1	0.003
X2 -> Z1 -> Y1	-0.003
X3 -> Z1 -> Y1	-0.010
X1 -> Z1 -> Y2	-0.042
X2 -> Z1 -> Y2	0.051
X3 -> Z1 -> Y2	0.166

Total Effects

	X1	X2	X3	Y1
X1				0.390
X2				0.464
X3				0.096
Y1				
Y2				
Z1				-0.017

Outer Loadings

	X1	X2	X3	Y1
X1.1	0.857			
X1.3	0.748			
X1.5	0.804			
X1.6	0.873			
X1.7	0.747			
X2.6		0.872		
X2.7		0.849		
X2.8		0.771		
X2.9		0.833		
X3.11			0.772	
X3.14			0.790	
X3.16			0.747	
X3.3			0.719	
X3.5			0.810	
X3.7			0.710	
Y1.4				0.840
Y1.5				0.841
Y2.1				
Y2.2				
Y2.4				
Z1.1				
Z1.2				

Outer Weights

	X1	X2	X3	Y1
X1.1	0.285			
X1.3	0.215			
X1.5	0.224			
X1.6	0.257			
X1.7	0.256			
X2.6		0.344		
X2.7		0.292		
X2.8		0.267		
X2.9		0.296		
X3.11			0.254	
X3.14			0.279	
X3.16			0.206	
X3.3			0.184	
X3.5			0.224	
X3.7			0.163	
Y1.4				0.594
Y1.5				0.595
Y2.1				
Y2.2				
Y2.4				

Z1.1				
Z1.2				

Latent Variable

Latent Variable

Case ID	X1	X2	X3	Y1
1	-0.632	-0.581	-0.262	-0.277
2	-0.240	0.105	-0.819	0.087
3	0.896	-0.121	-0.262	0.087
4	-1.259	-1.579	-0.262	-0.787
5	0.502	-0.581	0.379	-0.277
6	-0.632	-0.581	1.050	-0.787
7	-0.240	-0.581	0.156	-0.787
8	-0.213	-1.264	-0.262	-0.787
9	-0.632	-0.352	-1.198	-0.787
10	-0.240	-0.121	-3.610	-0.277
11	-0.632	-0.126	-0.262	0.087
12	-0.429	-1.039	0.299	-0.787
13	-0.845	-0.387	-0.262	-1.443
14	-0.632	-0.352	0.633	-0.787
15	-0.632	-0.355	-1.417	-0.277
16	-0.632	-0.581	-0.438	-0.787
17	1.288	0.371	1.649	0.597
18	-0.632	-0.089	1.315	-0.787
19	-0.632	-0.581	-0.262	-0.787
20	-2.537	-1.797	0.220	-1.443
21	-0.632	-0.089	0.299	0.087
22	-0.997	-0.810	0.829	-0.787
23	-0.240	-0.579	-0.262	-0.787
24	-1.989	-2.029	1.050	-1.443
25	-0.632	-0.810	-1.195	-0.787
26	0.336	-0.812	-0.860	-0.787
27	1.288	-0.162	-0.822	0.597
28	-0.632	-0.352	-1.421	-0.787
29	-0.632	-0.581	0.295	-0.787
30	0.896	-0.584	-1.198	0.087
31	-1.970	-1.076	-0.599	-1.443
32	-0.813	-0.587	0.156	-2.317
33	-0.632	-0.581	1.055	-0.787
34	-1.206	-0.847	-0.262	-0.787
35	0.896	-0.126	-0.596	0.087
36	-0.632	-0.581	0.379	-0.787
37	-0.253	-0.581	-0.262	0.087
38	-0.632	-0.581	-0.262	-0.787
39	1.288	0.105	-0.857	0.597
40	-1.395	-1.076	-0.933	-0.787
41	-0.632	-0.810	0.379	-0.787
42	0.532	-0.126	-1.156	0.087

43	-0.632	-0.581	1.649	0.087
44	0.896	-0.355	-0.596	0.087
45	-0.253	-0.581	-1.018	0.087
46	0.114	-0.584	0.076	0.597
47	-2.355	-1.762	-0.596	-2.317
48	-1.186	-0.581	-0.262	-0.787
49	-1.362	-0.659	-0.860	-0.277
50	-1.591	0.371	-0.596	0.087
51	-0.632	-0.581	0.076	-0.787
52	-2.159	-1.343	-1.751	-2.317
53	-0.253	0.105	-0.600	0.087
54	-0.632	-0.810	0.076	0.087
55	-0.253	-0.581	1.315	0.087
56	-1.773	-2.258	0.894	-0.787
57	-0.632	-0.581	0.410	-0.787
58	-0.253	-1.076	-0.262	-0.787
59	-2.355	-1.762	1.649	-2.317
60	0.505	-0.355	-0.596	0.087
61	-0.632	-0.810	1.649	0.087
62	-0.036	-1.762	1.089	-0.787
63	0.134	-0.581	-0.335	0.087
64	0.330	0.379	0.829	0.597
65	0.721	0.409	1.315	0.597
66	0.738	0.901	1.649	0.597
67	0.563	1.361	-0.001	0.597
68	0.380	1.101	1.649	0.597
69	0.591	0.448	1.389	1.108
70	0.774	0.643	-0.262	1.108
71	0.407	0.415	1.649	1.108
72	1.322	0.420	1.649	1.982
73	1.274	0.612	0.417	0.597
74	0.951	0.608	1.315	0.597
75	1.127	1.057	1.312	0.597
76	1.133	1.582	-0.262	1.982
77	1.120	0.820	0.829	1.982
78	1.463	1.051	0.977	1.472
79	0.888	1.353	-1.044	0.597
80	1.254	1.087	0.828	1.982
81	0.890	2.276	-0.262	0.597
82	0.523	1.818	0.072	1.982
83	1.278	1.552	0.079	0.597
84	0.346	1.323	-0.262	0.597
85	1.491	1.552	0.490	1.472
86	1.491	1.283	0.410	-1.297
87	1.113	1.051	0.156	-0.423
88	1.138	1.318	-0.971	0.597
89	1.477	1.587	-0.262	0.087
90	1.490	1.359	0.076	1.472
91	1.106	1.092	-0.596	0.597
92	0.751	0.785	1.649	0.962

93	0.331	0.600	0.495	0.597
94	0.889	1.318	-0.262	1.982
95	0.535	1.016	-3.331	0.087
96	1.118	1.549	0.076	0.597
97	0.740	1.549	-0.822	1.472
98	0.355	1.283	-0.262	1.472
99	0.735	1.016	-2.015	1.472
100	0.191	1.819	-0.262	1.472

Latent Variable Correlations

	X1	X2	X3	Y1
X1	1.000	0.783	0.065	0.760
X2	0.783	1.000	-0.008	0.769
X3	0.065	-0.008	1.000	0.117
Y1	0.760	0.769	0.117	1.000
Y2	0.248	0.240	0.074	0.142
Z1	0.031	0.060	0.588	0.085

Latent Variable Covariances

	X1	X2	X3	Y1
X1	1.000	0.783	0.065	0.760
X2	0.783	1.000	-0.008	0.769
X3	0.065	-0.008	1.000	0.117
Y1	0.760	0.769	0.117	1.000
Y2	0.248	0.240	0.074	0.142
Z1	0.031	0.060	0.588	0.085

LV Descriptives

	Mean	Median	Min	Max
X1	0.000	0.114	-2.537	1.491
X2	0.000	-0.162	-2.258	2.276
X3	0.000	-0.262	-3.610	1.649
Y1	0.000	0.087	-2.317	1.982
Y2	0.000	0.391	-3.635	1.196
Z1	0.000	0.102	-3.948	1.114

Residuals

Outer Model Residual Scores

Case ID	X1.1	X1.3	X1.5	X1.6
1	0.005	0.286	0.123	-0.082
2	-0.330	-0.007	-0.192	-0.424
3	0.165	0.839	0.533	0.058
4	-1.659	0.756	0.627	0.465
5	-0.966	1.133	-0.789	0.402
6	0.005	0.286	0.123	-0.082

7	-0.330	-0.007	-0.192	-0.424
8	1.115	-0.027	-0.214	-0.448
9	0.005	0.286	0.123	-0.082
10	-0.330	-0.007	-0.192	-0.424
11	0.005	0.286	0.123	-0.082
12	-0.168	0.134	-0.040	-0.997
13	-0.546	-0.402	1.933	-0.634
14	0.005	0.286	0.123	-0.082
15	0.005	0.286	0.123	-0.082
16	0.005	0.286	0.123	-0.082
17	-0.171	0.546	0.218	-0.284
18	0.005	0.286	0.123	-0.082
19	0.005	0.286	0.123	-0.082
20	0.170	-0.832	0.016	0.107
21	0.005	0.286	0.123	-0.082
22	0.318	-0.288	-0.403	0.237
23	-0.330	-0.007	-0.192	-0.424
24	-0.299	0.454	0.395	-0.371
25	0.005	0.286	0.123	-0.082
26	0.644	-0.438	0.983	0.547
27	-0.171	0.546	0.218	-0.284
28	0.005	0.286	0.123	-0.082
29	0.005	0.286	0.123	-0.082
30	0.165	0.839	0.533	0.058
31	-0.316	-0.408	-0.440	0.349
32	0.161	-0.426	0.269	0.076
33	0.005	0.286	0.123	-0.082
34	-0.236	-0.132	-0.235	0.419
35	0.165	0.839	0.533	0.058
36	0.005	0.286	0.123	-0.082
37	-0.319	0.003	-0.181	1.062
38	0.005	0.286	0.123	-0.082
39	-0.171	0.546	0.218	-0.284
40	-0.074	0.010	-0.083	-0.153
41	0.005	0.286	0.123	-0.082
42	0.476	-0.585	0.826	0.376
43	0.005	0.286	0.123	-0.082
44	0.165	0.839	0.533	0.058
45	-0.319	0.003	-0.181	1.062
46	-0.633	-0.272	1.162	0.741
47	0.014	-0.120	-0.130	-0.052
48	0.480	-0.147	-0.251	-0.335
49	0.632	-0.862	-0.928	0.556
50	0.094	0.156	0.075	0.018
51	0.005	0.286	0.123	-0.082
52	-0.154	-0.267	-0.288	-0.223
53	-0.319	0.003	-0.181	1.062
54	0.005	0.286	0.123	-0.082
55	-0.319	0.003	-0.181	1.062
56	0.249	-0.555	0.221	0.177

57	0.005	0.286	0.123	-0.082
58	-0.319	0.003	-0.181	1.062
59	0.014	-0.120	-0.130	-0.052
60	-0.969	-0.565	0.847	0.399
61	0.005	0.286	0.123	-0.082
62	0.963	-0.159	0.464	0.135
63	0.083	-0.287	1.146	-0.014
64	-0.084	-0.433	0.989	-0.185
65	-0.420	-0.726	0.674	-0.527
66	0.300	0.957	-0.979	-1.278
67	0.449	-0.608	-0.838	-0.389
68	0.607	-0.471	-1.510	-0.228
69	1.160	-1.476	-0.860	-0.413
70	1.002	-1.613	-0.188	-0.573
71	1.317	-1.339	-1.532	-0.252
72	0.534	-0.328	0.191	-1.051
73	-0.893	0.556	0.229	-0.272
74	0.851	-1.746	0.489	0.010
75	-0.033	-1.877	0.348	0.594
76	0.695	-1.034	0.343	-0.149
77	-0.027	-1.024	0.353	-0.137
78	-1.055	0.414	0.077	0.300
79	-0.563	0.844	-0.280	0.802
80	-1.610	0.571	0.245	0.482
81	-0.564	-0.004	0.538	0.801
82	-0.250	0.270	-0.805	1.121
83	-0.897	1.400	-1.413	0.461
84	-0.098	0.402	-1.483	0.538
85	-0.345	-0.454	0.055	0.276
86	-0.345	-0.454	0.055	0.276
87	-0.021	-1.019	0.359	0.606
88	0.690	-1.038	-0.481	0.583
89	-0.333	0.404	0.066	0.288
90	0.389	0.394	0.056	0.276
91	-0.015	-0.166	0.365	-0.125
92	1.022	0.947	-0.989	-1.290
93	-0.086	2.109	-1.471	-0.923
94	-0.564	0.844	0.539	-0.673
95	0.473	1.108	-0.816	-0.364
96	-0.026	-0.175	-0.465	-0.136
97	0.298	-0.740	-0.161	0.194
98	0.628	-0.452	0.149	-0.207
99	0.303	-0.736	0.663	-0.538
100	0.769	-0.329	-1.358	-0.800

Outer Model Residual Correlation

	X1.1	X1.3	X1.5	X1.6
X1.1	1.000	-0.420	-0.252	-0.346
X1.3	-0.420	1.000	-0.140	-0.106

X1.5	-0.252	-0.140	1.000	0.090
X1.6	-0.346	-0.106	0.090	1.000
X1.7	-0.061	-0.286	-0.513	-0.418
X2.6	0.209	-0.066	-0.134	-0.109
X2.7	-0.232	0.140	0.099	0.251
X2.8	0.153	-0.174	-0.113	-0.164
X2.9	-0.156	0.116	0.163	0.046
X3.11	0.057	0.003	-0.103	0.145
X3.14	-0.057	0.088	0.018	0.033
X3.16	0.194	-0.111	0.049	-0.112
X3.3	-0.037	-0.093	0.001	-0.052
X3.5	-0.181	0.071	0.043	-0.104
X3.7	0.021	0.019	0.009	0.057
Y1.4	-0.068	-0.056	0.166	-0.008
Y1.5	0.068	0.056	-0.166	0.008
Y2.1	0.096	-0.222	-0.071	-0.038
Y2.2	-0.200	0.219	0.116	0.055
Y2.4	0.033	0.116	0.001	0.005
Z1.1	0.028	0.035	-0.076	0.119
Z1.2	-0.028	-0.035	0.076	-0.119

Outer Model Residual Descriptives

	Mean	Median	Min	Max
X1.1	0.000	0.005	-1.659	1.317
X1.3	0.000	0.003	-1.877	2.109
X1.5	0.000	0.123	-1.532	1.933
X1.6	0.000	-0.082	-1.290	1.121
X1.7	0.000	-0.135	-1.758	1.410
X2.6	0.000	0.112	-1.367	1.536
X2.7	0.000	0.015	-1.965	0.980
X2.8	0.000	-0.064	-1.939	1.754
X2.9	0.000	0.143	-1.651	1.750
X3.11	0.000	0.150	-2.524	1.299
X3.14	0.000	0.024	-3.571	1.410
X3.16	0.000	0.048	-2.166	1.222
X3.3	0.000	0.132	-3.556	2.538
X3.5	0.000	0.142	-1.856	2.894
X3.7	0.000	-0.033	-4.448	2.343
Y1.4	0.000	-0.149	-0.885	1.565
Y1.5	0.000	0.149	-1.563	0.884
Y2.1	0.000	0.007	-1.807	2.026
Y2.2	0.000	-0.070	-1.536	1.965
Y2.4	0.000	0.035	-1.464	1.080
Z1.1	0.000	0.026	-1.777	1.452
Z1.2	0.000	-0.028	-1.559	1.909

Inner Model Residual Scores

Case ID	Y1	Y2	Z1
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1	0.269	0.498	0.270
2	0.211	-2.025	0.020
3	-0.174	0.793	0.417
4	0.468	0.884	0.357
5	-0.239	0.658	0.058
6	-0.380	-2.782	-0.517
7	-0.437	-1.828	0.078
8	-0.101	0.754	-0.554
9	-0.249	-1.343	0.789
10	0.188	0.678	-1.798
11	0.421	0.463	0.186
12	-0.157	-0.390	0.544
13	-0.888	0.050	1.214
14	-0.443	0.762	-0.309
15	0.285	-0.441	0.920
16	-0.223	-0.325	0.375
17	-0.231	0.286	0.253
18	-0.638	0.811	-0.766
19	-0.241	1.303	0.270
20	0.376	0.713	0.927
21	0.353	1.178	0.359
22	-0.108	-2.527	-0.398
23	-0.394	0.426	0.329
24	0.175	-1.596	0.038
25	-0.078	1.321	-1.691
26	-0.446	0.277	0.818
27	0.262	-3.166	0.820
28	-0.234	0.998	0.426
29	-0.309	1.003	-0.581
30	0.141	0.313	1.064
31	-0.145	-2.702	-1.707
32	-1.726	0.294	1.004
33	-0.380	0.209	-0.520
34	0.106	-2.595	0.231
35	-0.153	0.619	-0.394
36	-0.309	0.255	-0.115
37	0.419	-1.094	-3.722
38	-0.224	0.218	1.282
39	0.133	-0.141	0.296
40	0.357	-1.110	0.647
41	-0.202	-0.224	-0.073
42	0.055	0.492	0.382
43	0.431	0.880	-0.876
44	-0.038	0.307	0.144
45	0.525	-1.251	-1.720
46	0.828	-0.356	0.677
47	-0.516	0.875	0.425
48	-0.026	-0.937	0.185
49	0.669	-0.198	1.544
50	0.613	0.288	1.161

51	-0.277	0.532	0.067
52	-0.683	0.971	0.057
53	0.202	0.838	0.404
54	0.687	0.831	-0.904
55	0.336	0.498	0.394
56	0.879	-0.545	0.724
57	-0.312	1.371	-0.133
58	-0.157	-0.219	0.418
59	-0.753	1.101	-0.921
60	0.088	0.188	-1.423
61	0.538	0.903	-0.834
62	-0.063	0.921	-0.233
63	0.344	0.654	0.430
64	0.207	0.852	-0.415
65	0.006	0.244	0.360
66	-0.274	-0.126	-0.424
67	-0.255	0.152	-0.062
68	-0.220	0.092	-0.019
69	0.541	0.386	0.289
70	0.503	-0.176	-1.766
71	0.600	0.257	0.111
72	1.109	-1.301	-0.267
73	-0.208	-0.159	0.946
74	-0.176	0.488	0.359
75	-0.470	-0.790	-0.707
76	0.850	-0.661	1.153
77	1.087	0.038	0.121
78	0.312	0.722	-0.454
79	-0.267	0.296	0.614
80	0.919	-0.456	0.609
81	-0.789	0.632	-0.520
82	0.924	-0.790	-0.196
83	-0.629	-0.414	-0.036
84	-0.125	0.478	0.068
85	0.136	-0.881	0.762
86	-2.516	-0.396	-0.153
87	-1.360	0.704	-0.016
88	-0.397	0.462	-1.906
89	-1.197	0.248	0.192
90	0.270	-0.483	1.045
91	-0.277	0.013	0.427
92	0.148	0.356	0.096
93	0.138	-0.004	-0.255
94	1.051	-0.236	0.152
95	-0.275	0.410	-0.031
96	-0.566	0.351	-0.059
97	0.541	-0.148	-0.073
98	0.764	-0.326	0.077
99	0.893	0.386	-0.790
100	0.578	0.163	-0.046

Inner Model Residual Correlation

	Y1	Y2	Z1
Y1	1.000	-0.130	0.000
Y2	-0.130	1.000	0.000
Z1	0.000	0.000	1.000

Inner Model Residual Descriptives

	Mean	Median	Min	Max
Y1	0.000	-0.038	-2.516	1.109
Y2	0.000	0.257	-3.166	1.371
Z1	0.000	0.096	-3.722	1.544

Quality Criteria

R Square

	R Square	R Square Adjusted
Y1	0.665	0.650
Y2	0.120	0.083
Z1	0.359	0.339

f Square

	X1	X2	X3	Y1
X1				0.169
X2				0.244
X3				0.021
Y1				
Y2				
Z1				0.001

Construct Reliability and Validity

	Cronbach's Alpha	rho_A	Composite Reliability	Average Variance Inflation
X1	0.866	0.873	0.903	0.652
X2	0.852	0.861	0.900	0.693
X3	0.855	0.868	0.890	0.576
Y1	0.784	0.784	0.828	0.706
Y2	0.816	0.852	0.889	0.728
Z1	0.873	0.876	0.940	0.887

Discriminant Validity

Fornell-Larcker Criterion

	X1	X2	X3	Y1
X1	0.807			

X2	0.783	0.832		
X3	0.065	-0.008	0.759	
Y1	0.760	0.769	0.117	0.840
Y2	0.248	0.240	0.074	0.142
Z1	0.031	0.060	0.588	0.085

Cross Loadings

	X1	X2	X3	Y1
X1.1	0.857	0.688	0.096	0.691
X1.3	0.748	0.533	-0.027	0.513
X1.5	0.804	0.478	0.000	0.528
X1.6	0.873	0.679	-0.007	0.638
X1.7	0.747	0.746	0.177	0.667
X2.6	0.702	0.872	0.185	0.715
X2.7	0.650	0.849	-0.152	0.624
X2.8	0.604	0.771	0.034	0.590
X2.9	0.645	0.833	-0.123	0.619
X3.11	0.033	0.025	0.772	0.096
X3.14	0.110	0.029	0.790	0.081
X3.16	0.069	-0.007	0.747	0.100
X3.3	0.019	-0.046	0.719	0.081
X3.5	0.020	-0.010	0.810	0.107
X3.7	0.021	-0.062	0.710	0.069
Y1.4	0.594	0.679	0.116	0.840
Y1.5	0.683	0.613	0.082	0.841
Y2.1	0.231	0.222	0.076	0.183
Y2.2	0.116	0.110	0.106	0.053
Y2.4	0.251	0.247	0.026	0.105
Z1.1	0.083	0.120	0.541	0.124
Z1.2	-0.029	-0.012	0.568	0.034

Heterotrait-Monotrait Ratio (HTMT)

	X1	X2	X3	Y1
X1				
X2	0.901			
X3	0.121	0.193		
Y1	1.059	1.086	0.166	
Y2	0.292	0.265	0.135	0.192
Z1	0.082	0.102	0.660	0.134

Collinearity Statistics (VIF)

Outer VIF Values

	VIF
X1.1	2.349
X1.3	1.724
X1.5	2.349

X1.6	2.889
X1.7	1.716
X2.6	2.235
X2.7	2.329
X2.8	1.730
X2.9	2.164
X3.11	2.073
X3.14	2.035
X3.16	1.722
X3.3	1.906
X3.5	2.779
X3.7	1.999
Y1.4	1.205
Y1.5	1.205
Y2.1	1.452
Y2.2	2.483
Y2.4	2.827
Z1.1	2.500
Z1.2	2.500

Inner VIF Values

	X1	X2	X3	Y1
X1				2.652
X2				2.658
X3				1.574
Y1				
Y2				
Z1				1.560

Model_Fit

Fit Summary

	Saturated Model	Estimated Mode
SRMR	0.086	0.086
d_uls	1.873	1.893
d_g	0.868	0.873
Chi-Square	483.999	485.854
NFI	0.665	0.664

rms Theta

rms Theta	0.198
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Model Selection Criteria

	AIC (Akaike's In	AICu (Unbiased	AICc (Corrected A	BIC (Bayesian Inf
Y1	-100.251	-95.122	2.652	-87.226
Y2	-3.829	1.300	99.074	9.197

Z1	-37.458	-33.376	65.180	-27.038
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Interim Results

Stop Criterion Changes

	X1.1	X1.3	X1.5	X1.6
Iteration 0	0.248	0.248	0.248	0.248
Iteration 1	0.284	0.215	0.224	0.257
Iteration 2	0.285	0.215	0.224	0.257
Iteration 3	0.285	0.215	0.224	0.257
Iteration 4	0.285	0.215	0.224	0.257
Iteration 5	0.285	0.215	0.224	0.257
Iteration 6	0.285	0.215	0.224	0.257
Iteration 7	0.285	0.215	0.224	0.257

Base Data

Setting

Data file Setting	
Data file	tabulasi [100 records]
Missing value method	none
Data Setup Setting	
Algorithm to handle missing values	None
Weighting Vector	-
PLS Algorithm	
Data metric	Mean 0, Var 1
Initial Weights	1.0
Max. number of iterations	300
Stop criterion	7
Use Lohmoeller's criterion	No
Weighting scheme	Path
Construct Outer	
X1	Automatic
X2	Automatic
X3	Automatic
Y1	Automatic
Y2	Automatic
Z1	Automatic

Inner Model

	X1	X2	X3	Y1
X1				1.000
X2				1.000
X3				1.000
Y1				
Y2				
Z1				1.000

Outer Model

	X1	X2	X3	Y1
X1.1	-1.000			
X1.3	-1.000			
X1.5	-1.000			
X1.6	-1.000			
X1.7	-1.000			
X2.6		-1.000		
X2.7		-1.000		
X2.8		-1.000		
X2.9		-1.000		
X3.11			-1.000	
X3.14			-1.000	
X3.16			-1.000	
X3.3			-1.000	
X3.5			-1.000	
X3.7			-1.000	
Y1.4				-1.000
Y1.5				-1.000
Y2.1				
Y2.2				
Y2.4				
Z1.1				
Z1.2				

Indicator Data (Original)

Case ID	X1.1	X1.3	X1.5	X1.6
1	4.000	4.000	4.000	4.000
2	4.000	4.000	4.000	4.000
3	6.000	6.000	6.000	6.000
4	1.000	4.000	4.000	4.000
5	4.000	6.000	4.000	6.000
6	4.000	4.000	4.000	4.000
7	4.000	4.000	4.000	4.000
8	6.000	4.000	4.000	4.000
9	4.000	4.000	4.000	4.000
10	4.000	4.000	4.000	4.000
11	4.000	4.000	4.000	4.000
12	4.000	4.000	4.000	3.000
13	3.000	3.000	6.000	3.000
14	4.000	4.000	4.000	4.000
15	4.000	4.000	4.000	4.000
16	4.000	4.000	4.000	4.000
17	6.000	6.000	6.000	6.000
18	4.000	4.000	4.000	4.000
19	4.000	4.000	4.000	4.000
20	2.000	1.000	2.000	2.000

21	4.000	4.000	4.000	4.000
22	4.000	3.000	3.000	4.000
23	4.000	4.000	4.000	4.000
24	2.000	3.000	3.000	2.000
25	4.000	4.000	4.000	4.000
26	6.000	4.000	6.000	6.000
27	6.000	6.000	6.000	6.000
28	4.000	4.000	4.000	4.000
29	4.000	4.000	4.000	4.000
30	6.000	6.000	6.000	6.000
31	2.000	2.000	2.000	3.000
32	4.000	3.000	4.000	4.000
33	4.000	4.000	4.000	4.000
34	3.000	3.000	3.000	4.000
35	6.000	6.000	6.000	6.000
36	4.000	4.000	4.000	4.000
37	4.000	4.000	4.000	6.000
38	4.000	4.000	4.000	4.000
39	6.000	6.000	6.000	6.000
40	3.000	3.000	3.000	3.000
41	4.000	4.000	4.000	4.000
42	6.000	4.000	6.000	6.000
43	4.000	4.000	4.000	4.000
44	6.000	6.000	6.000	6.000
45	4.000	4.000	4.000	6.000
46	4.000	4.000	6.000	6.000
47	2.000	2.000	2.000	2.000
48	4.000	3.000	3.000	3.000
49	4.000	2.000	2.000	4.000
50	3.000	3.000	3.000	3.000
51	4.000	4.000	4.000	4.000
52	2.000	2.000	2.000	2.000
53	4.000	4.000	4.000	6.000
54	4.000	4.000	4.000	4.000
55	4.000	4.000	4.000	6.000
56	3.000	2.000	3.000	3.000
57	4.000	4.000	4.000	4.000
58	4.000	4.000	4.000	6.000
59	2.000	2.000	2.000	2.000
60	4.000	4.000	6.000	6.000
61	4.000	4.000	4.000	4.000
62	6.000	4.000	5.000	5.000
63	5.000	4.000	6.000	5.000
64	5.000	4.000	6.000	5.000
65	5.000	4.000	6.000	5.000
66	6.000	6.000	4.000	4.000
67	6.000	4.000	4.000	5.000
68	6.000	4.000	3.000	5.000
69	7.000	3.000	4.000	5.000
70	7.000	3.000	5.000	5.000

71	7.000	3.000	3.000	5.000
72	7.000	5.000	6.000	5.000
73	5.000	6.000	6.000	6.000
74	7.000	3.000	6.000	6.000
75	6.000	3.000	6.000	7.000
76	7.000	4.000	6.000	6.000
77	6.000	4.000	6.000	6.000
78	5.000	6.000	6.000	7.000
79	5.000	6.000	5.000	7.000
80	4.000	6.000	6.000	7.000
81	5.000	5.000	6.000	7.000
82	5.000	5.000	4.000	7.000
83	5.000	7.000	4.000	7.000
84	5.000	5.000	3.000	6.000
85	6.000	5.000	6.000	7.000
86	6.000	5.000	6.000	7.000
87	6.000	4.000	6.000	7.000
88	7.000	4.000	5.000	7.000
89	6.000	6.000	6.000	7.000
90	7.000	6.000	6.000	7.000
91	6.000	5.000	6.000	6.000
92	7.000	6.000	4.000	4.000
93	5.000	7.000	3.000	4.000
94	5.000	6.000	6.000	5.000
95	6.000	6.000	4.000	5.000
96	6.000	5.000	5.000	6.000
97	6.000	4.000	5.000	6.000
98	6.000	4.000	5.000	5.000
99	6.000	4.000	6.000	5.000
100	6.000	4.000	3.000	4.000

MV Descriptives

	Mean	Median	Min	Max
X1.1	4.730	4.000	1.000	7.000
X1.3	4.220	4.000	1.000	7.000
X1.5	4.470	4.000	2.000	6.000
X1.6	4.860	5.000	2.000	7.000
X1.7	4.970	4.000	3.000	7.000
X2.6	4.510	4.000	2.000	7.000
X2.7	4.870	4.000	3.000	7.000
X2.8	4.640	4.000	1.000	7.000
X2.9	4.440	4.000	1.000	7.000
X3.11	6.040	6.000	2.000	7.000
X3.14	6.290	6.000	2.000	7.000
X3.16	6.220	6.000	5.000	7.000
X3.3	6.040	6.000	3.000	7.000
X3.5	6.020	6.000	3.000	7.000
X3.7	6.160	6.000	2.000	7.000
Y1.4	5.760	6.000	5.000	7.000

Y1.5	5.240	5.000	2.000	7.000
Y2.1	5.550	6.000	1.000	7.000
Y2.2	5.640	6.000	1.000	7.000
Y2.4	5.400	6.000	1.000	7.000
Z1.1	5.870	6.000	2.000	7.000
Z1.2	5.930	6.000	2.000	7.000

Indicator Data (Standardized)

Case ID	X1.1	X1.3	X1.5	X1.6
1	-0.536	-0.186	-0.385	-0.634
2	-0.536	-0.186	-0.385	-0.634
3	0.932	1.509	1.254	0.840
4	-2.737	-0.186	-0.385	-0.634
5	-0.536	1.509	-0.385	0.840
6	-0.536	-0.186	-0.385	-0.634
7	-0.536	-0.186	-0.385	-0.634
8	0.932	-0.186	-0.385	-0.634
9	-0.536	-0.186	-0.385	-0.634
10	-0.536	-0.186	-0.385	-0.634
11	-0.536	-0.186	-0.385	-0.634
12	-0.536	-0.186	-0.385	-1.371
13	-1.269	-1.034	1.254	-1.371
14	-0.536	-0.186	-0.385	-0.634
15	-0.536	-0.186	-0.385	-0.634
16	-0.536	-0.186	-0.385	-0.634
17	0.932	1.509	1.254	0.840
18	-0.536	-0.186	-0.385	-0.634
19	-0.536	-0.186	-0.385	-0.634
20	-2.003	-2.730	-2.024	-2.108
21	-0.536	-0.186	-0.385	-0.634
22	-0.536	-1.034	-1.205	-0.634
23	-0.536	-0.186	-0.385	-0.634
24	-2.003	-1.034	-1.205	-2.108
25	-0.536	-0.186	-0.385	-0.634
26	0.932	-0.186	1.254	0.840
27	0.932	1.509	1.254	0.840
28	-0.536	-0.186	-0.385	-0.634
29	-0.536	-0.186	-0.385	-0.634
30	0.932	1.509	1.254	0.840
31	-2.003	-1.882	-2.024	-1.371
32	-0.536	-1.034	-0.385	-0.634
33	-0.536	-0.186	-0.385	-0.634
34	-1.269	-1.034	-1.205	-0.634
35	0.932	1.509	1.254	0.840
36	-0.536	-0.186	-0.385	-0.634
37	-0.536	-0.186	-0.385	0.840
38	-0.536	-0.186	-0.385	-0.634
39	0.932	1.509	1.254	0.840
40	-1.269	-1.034	-1.205	-1.371

41	-0.536	-0.186	-0.385	-0.634
42	0.932	-0.186	1.254	0.840
43	-0.536	-0.186	-0.385	-0.634
44	0.932	1.509	1.254	0.840
45	-0.536	-0.186	-0.385	0.840
46	-0.536	-0.186	1.254	0.840
47	-2.003	-1.882	-2.024	-2.108
48	-0.536	-1.034	-1.205	-1.371
49	-0.536	-1.882	-2.024	-0.634
50	-1.269	-1.034	-1.205	-1.371
51	-0.536	-0.186	-0.385	-0.634
52	-2.003	-1.882	-2.024	-2.108
53	-0.536	-0.186	-0.385	0.840
54	-0.536	-0.186	-0.385	-0.634
55	-0.536	-0.186	-0.385	0.840
56	-1.269	-1.882	-1.205	-1.371
57	-0.536	-0.186	-0.385	-0.634
58	-0.536	-0.186	-0.385	0.840
59	-2.003	-1.882	-2.024	-2.108
60	-0.536	-0.186	1.254	0.840
61	-0.536	-0.186	-0.385	-0.634
62	0.932	-0.186	0.434	0.103
63	0.198	-0.186	1.254	0.103
64	0.198	-0.186	1.254	0.103
65	0.198	-0.186	1.254	0.103
66	0.932	1.509	-0.385	-0.634
67	0.932	-0.186	-0.385	0.103
68	0.932	-0.186	-1.205	0.103
69	1.666	-1.034	-0.385	0.103
70	1.666	-1.034	0.434	0.103
71	1.666	-1.034	-1.205	0.103
72	1.666	0.661	1.254	0.103
73	0.198	1.509	1.254	0.840
74	1.666	-1.034	1.254	0.840
75	0.932	-1.034	1.254	1.577
76	1.666	-0.186	1.254	0.840
77	0.932	-0.186	1.254	0.840
78	0.198	1.509	1.254	1.577
79	0.198	1.509	0.434	1.577
80	-0.536	1.509	1.254	1.577
81	0.198	0.661	1.254	1.577
82	0.198	0.661	-0.385	1.577
83	0.198	2.357	-0.385	1.577
84	0.198	0.661	-1.205	0.840
85	0.932	0.661	1.254	1.577
86	0.932	0.661	1.254	1.577
87	0.932	-0.186	1.254	1.577
88	1.666	-0.186	0.434	1.577
89	0.932	1.509	1.254	1.577
90	1.666	1.509	1.254	1.577

91	0.932	0.661	1.254	0.840
92	1.666	1.509	-0.385	-0.634
93	0.198	2.357	-1.205	-0.634
94	0.198	1.509	1.254	0.103
95	0.932	1.509	-0.385	0.103
96	0.932	0.661	0.434	0.840
97	0.932	-0.186	0.434	0.840
98	0.932	-0.186	0.434	0.103
99	0.932	-0.186	1.254	0.103
100	0.932	-0.186	-1.205	-0.634

Indicator Data (Correlations)

Empirical Correlation Matrix

	X1.1	X1.3	X1.5	X1.6
X1.1	1.000	0.497	0.612	0.661
X1.3	0.497	1.000	0.546	0.619
X1.5	0.612	0.546	1.000	0.728
X1.6	0.661	0.619	0.728	1.000
X1.7	0.619	0.432	0.397	0.516
X2.6	0.669	0.458	0.393	0.583
X2.7	0.508	0.491	0.425	0.628
X2.8	0.581	0.337	0.326	0.473
X2.9	0.522	0.481	0.446	0.572
X3.11	0.078	-0.032	-0.053	0.025
X3.14	0.108	0.059	0.054	0.056
X3.16	0.156	-0.053	0.036	-0.023
X3.3	0.032	-0.083	-0.022	-0.046
X3.5	-0.005	-0.018	-0.012	-0.064
X3.7	0.053	-0.029	-0.017	-0.008
Y1.4	0.524	0.377	0.461	0.495
Y1.5	0.638	0.485	0.426	0.577
Y2.1	0.263	0.115	0.202	0.174
Y2.2	0.079	0.197	0.173	0.099
Y2.4	0.263	0.250	0.247	0.200
Z1.1	0.100	0.055	0.062	0.022
Z1.2	-0.006	-0.045	0.002	-0.114

Model Implied Saturated Correlation Matrix

	X1.1	X1.3	X1.5	X1.6
X1.1	1.000	0.641	0.689	0.748
X1.3	0.641	1.000	0.602	0.653
X1.5	0.689	0.602	1.000	0.702
X1.6	0.748	0.653	0.702	1.000
X1.7	0.640	0.559	0.600	0.652
X2.6	0.585	0.511	0.549	0.596
X2.7	0.569	0.497	0.534	0.580
X2.8	0.517	0.451	0.485	0.527

X2.9	0.559	0.488	0.525	0.570
X3.11	0.043	0.038	0.040	0.044
X3.14	0.044	0.038	0.041	0.045
X3.16	0.042	0.036	0.039	0.042
X3.3	0.040	0.035	0.038	0.041
X3.5	0.045	0.039	0.042	0.046
X3.7	0.040	0.035	0.037	0.040
Y1.4	0.547	0.478	0.513	0.557
Y1.5	0.547	0.478	0.514	0.558
Y2.1	0.173	0.151	0.162	0.176
Y2.2	0.176	0.154	0.165	0.180
Y2.4	0.194	0.170	0.182	0.198
Z1.1	0.025	0.022	0.023	0.025
Z1.2	0.025	0.022	0.023	0.025

Model Implied Estimated Correlation Matrix

	X1.1	X1.3	X1.5	X1.6
X1.1	1.000	0.641	0.689	0.748
X1.3	0.641	1.000	0.602	0.653
X1.5	0.689	0.602	1.000	0.702
X1.6	0.748	0.653	0.702	1.000
X1.7	0.640	0.559	0.600	0.652
X2.6	0.585	0.511	0.549	0.596
X2.7	0.569	0.497	0.534	0.580
X2.8	0.517	0.451	0.485	0.527
X2.9	0.559	0.488	0.525	0.570
X3.11	0.043	0.038	0.040	0.044
X3.14	0.044	0.038	0.041	0.045
X3.16	0.042	0.036	0.039	0.042
X3.3	0.040	0.035	0.038	0.041
X3.5	0.045	0.039	0.042	0.046
X3.7	0.040	0.035	0.037	0.040
Y1.4	0.547	0.478	0.513	0.557
Y1.5	0.547	0.478	0.514	0.558
Y2.1	0.173	0.151	0.162	0.176
Y2.2	0.176	0.154	0.165	0.180
Y2.4	0.194	0.170	0.182	0.198
Z1.1	0.025	0.022	0.023	0.025
Z1.2	0.025	0.022	0.023	0.025

Empirical Covariance Matrix

	X1.1	X1.3	X1.5	X1.6
X1.1	1.857	0.799	1.017	1.222
X1.3	0.799	1.392	0.787	0.991
X1.5	1.017	0.787	1.489	1.206
X1.6	1.222	0.991	1.206	1.840
X1.7	1.102	0.667	0.634	0.916
X2.6	1.178	0.698	0.620	1.021

X2.7	0.895	0.749	0.671	1.102
X2.8	0.913	0.459	0.459	0.740
X2.9	0.919	0.733	0.703	1.002
X3.11	0.081	-0.029	-0.049	0.026
X3.14	0.098	0.046	0.044	0.051
X3.16	0.129	-0.038	0.027	-0.019
X3.3	0.031	-0.069	-0.019	-0.044
X3.5	-0.005	-0.014	-0.009	-0.057
X3.7	0.053	-0.025	-0.015	-0.008
Y1.4	0.485	0.303	0.383	0.456
Y1.5	1.015	0.667	0.607	0.914
Y2.1	0.499	0.189	0.342	0.327
Y2.2	0.153	0.329	0.299	0.190
Y2.4	0.548	0.452	0.462	0.416
Z1.1	0.145	0.069	0.081	0.032
Z1.2	-0.009	-0.055	0.003	-0.160

5. "SmartPLS 3." Boenningstedt: SmartPLS GmbH, <http://www.smartpls.com>.

Y2	Z1
0.185	-0.152
0.078	0.184
-0.101	0.599
0.277	

Y2	Z1
-0.042	
0.051	
0.166	

Y2	Z1
0.143	-0.152
0.129	0.184
0.065	0.599
0.277	

	0.550
	0.512

Y2	Z1
0.391	0.102
-2.094	-0.415
1.004	0.102
0.583	0.102
0.696	0.102
-3.021	0.102
-1.905	0.102
0.391	-0.911
-1.339	0.102
-0.106	-3.948
0.391	0.102
-0.414	0.598
0.199	1.114
0.583	0.102
-0.414	0.102
-0.414	0.102
0.696	1.114
0.583	0.102
1.196	0.102
0.391	1.114
1.196	0.618
-2.829	0.102
0.391	0.102
-2.062	0.598
0.580	-2.460
0.391	0.102
-2.829	0.102
0.888	-0.394
0.696	-0.415
0.583	0.102
-3.635	-1.964
0.391	1.114
-0.031	0.102
-2.829	0.102
0.583	-0.911
0.083	0.102
-2.254	-3.948
0.391	1.114
0.083	-0.394
-1.330	0.102
-0.414	0.102
0.583	-0.415

0.580	0.102
0.391	-0.415
-1.905	-2.398
-0.223	0.598
0.391	0.102
-1.147	0.102
-0.106	1.114
0.391	1.114
0.391	0.102
0.391	-0.911
0.888	0.102
0.391	-0.911
0.583	1.114
-0.830	1.114
1.196	0.102
-0.295	0.102
0.391	0.102
-0.219	-1.923
0.586	0.102
0.696	0.102
0.696	0.102
0.888	0.102
0.586	1.114
0.086	0.618
0.391	0.102
0.391	1.114
0.699	1.114
-0.490	-1.923
0.507	1.114
-1.025	0.598
0.391	1.114
0.888	1.114
-0.603	0.102
0.007	1.114
0.391	0.598
1.004	0.102
0.699	0.102
0.086	1.114
0.891	-0.394
-0.531	0.102
-0.037	0.102
0.699	0.102
-0.226	1.114
-0.034	0.102
1.004	0.102
0.202	-2.419
0.699	0.102
0.199	1.114
0.391	0.102
0.699	1.114

0.083	0.102
0.086	0.102
0.391	-1.923
0.699	0.102
0.083	-0.394
-0.106	0.102
0.271	-1.923
0.394	0.102

Y2	Z1
0.248	0.031
0.240	0.060
0.074	0.588
0.142	0.085
1.000	0.228
0.228	1.000

Y2	Z1
0.248	0.031
0.240	0.060
0.074	0.588
0.142	0.085
1.000	0.228
0.228	1.000

Standard Devia	Excess Kurtosis	Skewness	Number of Observations Used
1.000	-0.431	-0.461	100.000
1.000	-0.706	0.141	100.000
1.000	1.506	-0.564	100.000
1.000	-0.153	0.005	100.000
1.000	2.865	-1.791	100.000
1.000	4.206	-1.789	100.000

X1.7	X2.6	X2.7	X2.8	X2.9	X3.11
-0.270	0.112	-0.179	-0.107	0.143	0.150
0.967	-0.486	0.012	0.231	0.346	-0.735
-1.411	-0.289	-0.570	0.405	0.534	0.150
0.198	-0.565	0.668	-1.939	1.750	0.150
0.413	0.112	-0.179	-0.107	0.143	-0.345
-0.270	0.112	-0.179	-0.107	0.143	0.451

0.967	0.112	-0.179	-0.107	0.143	-0.173
-0.583	0.708	-0.372	0.420	-0.836	0.150
-0.270	-0.088	-0.374	-0.284	0.727	0.873
0.967	-0.289	-0.570	0.405	0.534	-2.524
-0.270	-0.284	0.208	-0.457	0.539	0.150
1.108	0.511	0.209	0.246	-1.024	-0.284
-0.111	-0.831	-0.344	0.611	0.757	0.150
-0.270	-0.088	-0.374	-0.284	0.727	0.773
-0.270	-0.085	0.402	-0.281	-0.045	-0.273
-0.270	0.112	-0.179	-0.107	0.143	-1.029
-0.173	0.055	-0.215	0.026	0.124	-0.012
-0.270	0.457	0.176	-0.486	-0.267	-1.068
-0.270	0.112	-0.179	-0.107	0.143	0.150
0.387	-0.374	0.080	0.831	-0.392	-0.223
-0.270	0.457	0.176	-0.486	-0.267	-0.284
0.002	0.312	0.015	0.069	-0.441	0.622
0.967	0.110	-0.181	0.758	-0.633	0.150
-0.022	-0.173	0.276	0.142	-0.199	0.451
-0.270	0.312	0.015	0.069	-0.441	-0.445
-1.758	0.314	0.017	-0.796	0.336	0.611
-0.173	-1.027	0.238	0.437	0.569	0.582
-0.270	-0.088	-0.374	-0.284	0.727	1.045
-0.270	0.112	-0.179	-0.107	0.143	1.035
-1.411	0.115	0.596	-0.105	-0.629	0.873
0.729	-0.230	0.241	0.275	-0.218	0.410
-0.135	0.117	0.598	-0.970	0.148	-0.173
-0.270	0.112	-0.179	-0.107	0.143	-0.867
0.159	-0.429	0.047	0.098	0.365	0.150
-1.411	-0.284	0.208	-0.457	0.539	-0.907
-0.270	0.112	-0.179	-0.107	0.143	-0.345
-0.553	0.112	-0.179	-0.107	0.143	0.150
-0.270	0.112	-0.179	-0.107	0.143	0.150
-0.173	-0.486	0.012	0.231	0.346	-0.706
0.300	-0.230	0.241	0.275	-0.218	-0.647
-0.270	0.312	0.015	0.069	-0.441	-0.345
-1.139	-0.284	0.208	-0.457	0.539	-0.475
-0.270	0.112	-0.179	-0.107	0.143	-0.012
-1.411	-0.085	0.402	-0.281	-0.045	-0.907
-0.553	0.112	-0.179	-0.107	0.143	0.733
-0.827	0.115	0.596	-0.105	-0.629	-0.112
0.251	0.369	0.050	-0.064	-0.422	-0.907
0.144	0.112	-0.179	-0.107	0.143	0.150
0.275	-1.367	0.660	-0.047	0.983	0.611
-0.319	0.055	-0.215	0.026	0.124	-0.907
-0.270	0.112	-0.179	-0.107	0.143	-0.112
0.870	-0.771	0.467	0.480	0.004	1.299
-0.553	-0.486	0.012	0.231	0.346	0.411
-0.270	0.312	0.015	0.069	-0.441	-0.112
-0.553	0.112	-0.179	-0.107	0.143	-1.068
-0.183	0.027	0.471	0.318	-0.783	0.572

-0.270	0.112	-0.179	-0.107	0.143	0.945
-0.553	-0.230	0.241	0.275	-0.218	0.150
0.251	0.369	0.050	-0.064	-0.422	-0.012
0.411	-0.085	0.402	-0.281	-0.045	-0.907
-0.270	0.312	0.015	0.069	-0.441	-0.012
-1.480	0.369	0.050	-0.064	-0.422	0.421
-0.842	0.112	-0.179	-0.107	0.143	-1.108
-0.223	0.048	-0.995	1.754	-0.657	0.622
1.014	0.796	-0.247	-0.003	-0.682	-1.068
1.002	1.141	0.109	-0.382	-1.092	-0.012
1.132	0.739	-0.282	0.130	-0.701	-0.052
1.269	0.192	-1.608	0.330	1.065	-0.012
1.112	1.536	-1.053	-0.900	0.061	0.190
0.975	0.593	-0.445	1.551	-1.651	0.150
1.249	0.791	-1.025	0.860	-0.686	-0.012
0.566	0.786	-1.802	1.722	-0.691	-0.012
0.601	-0.154	-1.965	1.575	0.699	-0.375
0.078	-0.151	-1.189	1.577	-0.073	-1.068
0.712	-0.543	-0.024	0.364	0.327	0.249
-0.058	0.547	0.304	-1.774	0.664	0.150
0.717	-0.336	0.950	-1.187	0.525	0.622
0.460	-0.538	0.754	-0.498	0.332	-0.807
-0.640	0.746	0.498	-1.598	0.081	0.753
0.616	0.205	0.724	-1.392	0.303	0.623
-0.641	-0.058	-0.285	0.292	0.086	0.150
-0.367	0.341	0.103	0.645	-1.081	1.207
0.599	-0.200	0.330	0.850	-0.859	-0.113
0.530	-0.001	0.524	1.027	-1.443	0.150
0.440	-0.200	0.330	0.850	-0.859	0.883
0.440	-0.740	0.558	0.190	0.139	0.945
-0.043	-0.538	0.754	-0.498	0.332	-0.173
-0.062	0.003	0.528	-0.704	0.110	-0.617
-0.315	0.543	0.300	-0.044	-0.889	0.150
-1.089	0.741	-0.280	-0.735	0.076	-0.112
-0.038	0.200	-0.054	-0.530	0.298	-0.907
0.227	-1.079	0.980	-0.293	0.554	-0.012
0.540	-0.144	-0.409	-0.151	0.708	-0.435
0.124	0.003	0.528	-0.704	0.110	0.150
-0.377	-1.281	0.784	0.396	0.362	1.205
0.718	-0.198	0.332	-0.015	-0.083	-0.112
0.235	-0.198	0.332	-0.015	-0.083	0.582
-0.242	-0.740	0.558	0.190	0.139	0.150
0.239	-1.281	0.784	0.396	0.362	0.189
1.410	0.340	-0.671	-0.223	0.467	0.150

X1.7	X2.6	X2.7	X2.8	X2.9	X3.11
-0.061	0.209	-0.232	0.153	-0.156	0.057
-0.286	-0.066	0.140	-0.174	0.116	0.003

-0.513	-0.134	0.099	-0.113	0.163	-0.103
-0.418	-0.109	0.251	-0.164	0.046	0.145
1.000	0.059	-0.178	0.222	-0.124	-0.077
0.059	1.000	-0.420	-0.126	-0.504	-0.124
-0.178	-0.420	1.000	-0.483	-0.008	0.165
0.222	-0.126	-0.483	1.000	-0.454	0.000
-0.124	-0.504	-0.008	-0.454	1.000	-0.028
-0.077	-0.124	0.165	0.000	-0.028	1.000
-0.062	-0.159	0.162	-0.058	0.071	0.144
-0.032	0.077	-0.004	-0.094	0.023	-0.083
0.146	-0.063	-0.189	0.305	-0.074	-0.420
0.139	0.179	-0.147	-0.041	-0.002	-0.566
-0.083	0.187	-0.090	-0.095	-0.009	-0.407
-0.019	-0.262	0.250	0.016	0.018	0.063
0.019	0.262	-0.250	-0.016	-0.018	-0.063
0.185	0.130	-0.019	-0.074	-0.039	-0.160
-0.142	-0.043	0.071	0.030	-0.053	0.056
-0.130	-0.137	-0.031	0.074	0.094	0.166
-0.082	0.018	-0.040	-0.068	0.089	0.050
0.082	-0.018	0.040	0.068	-0.089	-0.050

Standard Devia	Excess Kurtosis	Skewness	Number of Observations Used
0.516	1.501	-0.223	100.000
0.663	1.042	-0.272	100.000
0.594	1.490	-0.436	100.000
0.487	0.584	0.100	100.000
0.665	0.023	-0.158	100.000
0.489	1.254	-0.244	100.000
0.529	2.701	-1.164	100.000
0.637	2.017	0.062	100.000
0.553	0.796	-0.320	100.000
0.635	1.411	-0.611	100.000
0.613	10.456	-1.739	100.000
0.665	1.062	-0.586	100.000
0.695	7.335	-0.786	100.000
0.586	5.468	0.749	100.000
0.704	15.962	-2.017	100.000
0.542	0.896	0.899	100.000
0.541	0.896	-0.899	100.000
0.583	2.104	-0.144	100.000
0.558	1.539	0.267	100.000
0.405	1.608	-0.487	100.000
0.324	14.243	-1.401	100.000
0.348	14.243	1.401	100.000

Standard Devia	Excess Kurtosis	Skewness	Number of Observations Used
0.579	3.114	-0.935	100.000
0.938	1.974	-1.399	100.000
0.801	4.120	-1.420	100.000

Y2	Z1
0.015	0.014
0.003	0.020
0.007	0.553
0.056	

xtracted (AVE)

Y2	Z1
0.853	
0.228	0.942

Y2	Z1
0.257	0.052
0.220	0.007
0.249	0.036
0.195	-0.046
0.085	0.072
0.261	0.127
0.193	-0.009

0.107	0.009
0.220	0.056
-0.027	0.518
0.035	0.567
0.090	0.402
0.048	0.364
0.145	0.430
0.067	0.320
0.105	0.091
0.133	0.053
0.813	0.202
0.830	0.179
0.914	0.200
0.277	0.946
0.148	0.938

Y2	Z1
0.265	

Y2	Z1
2.652	2.616
2.658	2.605
1.574	1.013
1.560	

HQ (Hannan Q)	HQc (Corrected Hannan-Quinn Criterion)
-94.980	-93.830
1.443	2.592

-33.241	-32.461
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X1.7	X2.6	X2.7	X2.8	X2.9	X3.11
0.248	0.301	0.301	0.301	0.301	0.219
0.256	0.344	0.292	0.268	0.295	0.253
0.256	0.344	0.292	0.267	0.296	0.254
0.256	0.344	0.292	0.267	0.296	0.254
0.256	0.344	0.292	0.267	0.296	0.254
0.256	0.344	0.292	0.267	0.296	0.254
0.256	0.344	0.292	0.267	0.296	0.254
0.256	0.344	0.292	0.267	0.296	0.254

Y2	Z1
1.000	1.000
1.000	1.000
1.000	1.000
1.000	

4.000	5.000	5.000	4.000	4.000	6.000
4.000	4.000	4.000	4.000	3.000	7.000
6.000	4.000	4.000	5.000	3.000	6.000
3.000	2.000	3.000	3.000	2.000	7.000
4.000	4.000	4.000	4.000	3.000	5.000
3.000	4.000	4.000	3.000	4.000	6.000
6.000	3.000	5.000	5.000	5.000	6.000
4.000	4.000	4.000	4.000	5.000	6.000
4.000	4.000	4.000	4.000	4.000	7.000
4.000	4.000	5.000	4.000	3.000	6.000
4.000	3.000	4.000	4.000	3.000	6.000
4.000	4.000	5.000	3.000	4.000	6.000
4.000	4.000	4.000	4.000	4.000	6.000
4.000	3.000	4.000	4.000	4.000	6.000
4.000	4.000	5.000	4.000	5.000	5.000
4.000	4.000	4.000	4.000	4.000	6.000
4.000	4.000	4.000	4.000	4.000	6.000
4.000	4.000	4.000	4.000	4.000	6.000
4.000	4.000	4.000	4.000	4.000	6.000
4.000	4.000	4.000	4.000	4.000	6.000
6.000	4.000	5.000	5.000	5.000	5.000
4.000	3.000	4.000	4.000	3.000	5.000
4.000	4.000	4.000	4.000	3.000	6.000
4.000	4.000	5.000	4.000	5.000	5.000
4.000	4.000	4.000	4.000	4.000	7.000
4.000	4.000	5.000	4.000	4.000	5.000
4.000	4.000	4.000	4.000	4.000	6.000
4.000	4.000	5.000	4.000	3.000	6.000
4.000	4.000	4.000	4.000	4.000	6.000
4.000	4.000	4.000	4.000	4.000	6.000
3.000	3.000	3.000	3.000	2.000	5.000
4.000	4.000	4.000	4.000	4.000	6.000
4.000	2.000	5.000	4.000	5.000	6.000
3.000	5.000	5.000	5.000	5.000	5.000
4.000	4.000	4.000	4.000	4.000	6.000
4.000	2.000	4.000	4.000	3.000	6.000
4.000	4.000	5.000	5.000	5.000	6.000
4.000	4.000	4.000	4.000	3.000	6.000
4.000	4.000	4.000	4.000	4.000	6.000
3.000	2.000	3.000	3.000	1.000	7.000
4.000	4.000	4.000	4.000	4.000	7.000
4.000	3.000	4.000	4.000	3.000	6.000
3.000	3.000	3.000	3.000	2.000	7.000
6.000	4.000	5.000	4.000	4.000	5.000
4.000	4.000	4.000	4.000	3.000	7.000
3.000	3.000	3.000	3.000	2.000	7.000
4.000	4.000	4.000	4.000	4.000	5.000
5.000	5.000	4.000	7.000	4.000	7.000
7.000	6.000	5.000	5.000	4.000	6.000
7.000	7.000	6.000	5.000	4.000	7.000
7.000	7.000	6.000	6.000	5.000	6.000
7.000	6.000	4.000	6.000	7.000	7.000
7.000	7.000	4.000	4.000	5.000	7.000
7.000	6.000	5.000	7.000	3.000	6.000

7.000	6.000	4.000	6.000	4.000	7.000
7.000	6.000	3.000	7.000	4.000	7.000
7.000	5.000	3.000	7.000	6.000	6.000
6.000	5.000	4.000	7.000	5.000	6.000
7.000	5.000	6.000	6.000	6.000	7.000
6.000	7.000	7.000	4.000	7.000	6.000
7.000	5.000	7.000	4.000	6.000	7.000
7.000	5.000	7.000	5.000	6.000	6.000
5.000	7.000	7.000	4.000	6.000	6.000
7.000	6.000	7.000	4.000	6.000	7.000
5.000	7.000	7.000	7.000	7.000	6.000
5.000	7.000	7.000	7.000	5.000	7.000
7.000	6.000	7.000	7.000	5.000	6.000
6.000	6.000	7.000	7.000	4.000	6.000
7.000	6.000	7.000	7.000	5.000	7.000
7.000	5.000	7.000	6.000	6.000	7.000
6.000	5.000	7.000	5.000	6.000	6.000
6.000	6.000	7.000	5.000	6.000	5.000
6.000	7.000	7.000	6.000	5.000	6.000
5.000	7.000	6.000	5.000	6.000	6.000
6.000	6.000	6.000	5.000	6.000	5.000
6.000	4.000	7.000	5.000	6.000	7.000
6.000	5.000	5.000	5.000	6.000	6.000
6.000	6.000	7.000	5.000	6.000	6.000
5.000	4.000	7.000	6.000	6.000	5.000
7.000	6.000	7.000	6.000	6.000	6.000
6.000	6.000	7.000	6.000	6.000	6.000
5.000	5.000	7.000	6.000	6.000	6.000
6.000	4.000	7.000	6.000	6.000	5.000
7.000	7.000	6.000	6.000	7.000	6.000

Standard Devia	Excess Kurtosis	Skewness	Number of Observations Used
1.363	-0.372	-0.219	100.000
1.180	0.086	0.155	100.000
1.220	-0.924	-0.097	100.000
1.357	-0.755	-0.083	100.000
1.307	-1.326	0.329	100.000
1.292	-0.293	0.330	100.000
1.293	-0.926	0.584	100.000
1.153	0.390	0.465	100.000
1.291	-0.321	-0.191	100.000
0.761	6.576	-1.453	100.000
0.668	15.613	-2.463	100.000
0.610	-0.493	-0.161	100.000
0.706	3.326	-1.096	100.000
0.663	3.322	-0.858	100.000
0.731	9.739	-1.977	100.000
0.680	-0.833	0.345	100.000

1.167	2.480	-1.363	100.000
1.388	2.151	-1.607	100.000
1.418	3.207	-1.839	100.000
1.530	1.251	-1.416	100.000
1.064	5.095	-2.008	100.000
1.032	5.107	-1.964	100.000

X1.7	X2.6	X2.7	X2.8	X2.9	X3.11
-0.742	-0.395	-0.673	-0.555	-0.341	-0.053
0.788	-0.395	0.101	0.312	0.434	-1.367
-0.742	-0.395	-0.673	0.312	0.434	-0.053
-0.742	-1.942	-0.673	-3.156	0.434	-0.053
0.788	-0.395	-0.673	-0.555	-0.341	-0.053
-0.742	-0.395	-0.673	-0.555	-0.341	1.262
0.788	-0.395	-0.673	-0.555	-0.341	-0.053
-0.742	-0.395	-1.446	-0.555	-1.890	-0.053
-0.742	-0.395	-0.673	-0.555	0.434	-0.053
0.788	-0.395	-0.673	0.312	0.434	-5.312
-0.742	-0.395	0.101	-0.555	0.434	-0.053
0.788	-0.395	-0.673	-0.555	-1.890	-0.053
-0.742	-1.169	-0.673	0.312	0.434	-0.053
-0.742	-0.395	-0.673	-0.555	0.434	1.262
-0.742	-0.395	0.101	-0.555	-0.341	-1.367
-0.742	-0.395	-0.673	-0.555	-0.341	-1.367
0.788	0.379	0.101	0.312	0.434	1.262
-0.742	0.379	0.101	-0.555	-0.341	-0.053
-0.742	-0.395	-0.673	-0.555	-0.341	-0.053
-1.507	-1.942	-1.446	-0.555	-1.890	-0.053
-0.742	0.379	0.101	-0.555	-0.341	-0.053
-0.742	-0.395	-0.673	-0.555	-1.116	1.262
0.788	-0.395	-0.673	0.312	-1.116	-0.053
-1.507	-1.942	-1.446	-1.422	-1.890	1.262
-0.742	-0.395	-0.673	-0.555	-1.116	-1.367
-1.507	-0.395	-0.673	-1.422	-0.341	-0.053
0.788	-1.169	0.101	0.312	0.434	-0.053
-0.742	-0.395	-0.673	-0.555	0.434	-0.053
-0.742	-0.395	-0.673	-0.555	-0.341	1.262
-0.742	-0.395	0.101	-0.555	-1.116	-0.053
-0.742	-1.169	-0.673	-0.555	-1.116	-0.053
-0.742	-0.395	0.101	-1.422	-0.341	-0.053
-0.742	-0.395	-0.673	-0.555	-0.341	-0.053
-0.742	-1.169	-0.673	-0.555	-0.341	-0.053
-0.742	-0.395	0.101	-0.555	0.434	-1.367
-0.742	-0.395	-0.673	-0.555	-0.341	-0.053
-0.742	-0.395	-0.673	-0.555	-0.341	-0.053
-0.742	-0.395	-0.673	-0.555	-0.341	-0.053
0.788	-0.395	0.101	0.312	0.434	-1.367
-0.742	-1.169	-0.673	-0.555	-1.116	-1.367

-0.742	-0.395	-0.673		-0.555	-1.116	-0.053
-0.742	-0.395	0.101		-0.555	0.434	-1.367
-0.742	-0.395	-0.673		-0.555	-0.341	1.262
-0.742	-0.395	0.101		-0.555	-0.341	-1.367
-0.742	-0.395	-0.673		-0.555	-0.341	-0.053
-0.742	-0.395	0.101		-0.555	-1.116	-0.053
-1.507	-1.169	-1.446		-1.422	-1.890	-1.367
-0.742	-0.395	-0.673		-0.555	-0.341	-0.053
-0.742	-1.942	0.101		-0.555	0.434	-0.053
-1.507	0.379	0.101		0.312	0.434	-1.367
-0.742	-0.395	-0.673		-0.555	-0.341	-0.053
-0.742	-1.942	-0.673		-0.555	-1.116	-0.053
-0.742	-0.395	0.101		0.312	0.434	-0.053
-0.742	-0.395	-0.673		-0.555	-1.116	-0.053
-0.742	-0.395	-0.673		-0.555	-0.341	-0.053
-1.507	-1.942	-1.446		-1.422	-2.665	1.262
-0.742	-0.395	-0.673		-0.555	-0.341	1.262
-0.742	-1.169	-0.673		-0.555	-1.116	-0.053
-1.507	-1.169	-1.446		-1.422	-1.890	1.262
0.788	-0.395	0.101		-0.555	-0.341	-1.367
-0.742	-0.395	-0.673		-0.555	-1.116	1.262
-1.507	-1.169	-1.446		-1.422	-1.890	1.262
-0.742	-0.395	-0.673		-0.555	-0.341	-1.367
0.023	0.379	-0.673		2.046	-0.341	1.262
1.553	1.153	0.101		0.312	-0.341	-0.053
1.553	1.927	0.874		0.312	-0.341	1.262
1.553	1.927	0.874		1.179	0.434	-0.053
1.553	1.153	-0.673		1.179	1.983	1.262
1.553	1.927	-0.673		-0.555	0.434	1.262
1.553	1.153	0.101		2.046	-1.116	-0.053
1.553	1.153	-0.673		1.179	-0.341	1.262
1.553	1.153	-1.446		2.046	-0.341	1.262
1.553	0.379	-1.446		2.046	1.208	-0.053
0.788	0.379	-0.673		2.046	0.434	-0.053
1.553	0.379	0.874		1.179	1.208	1.262
0.788	1.927	1.647		-0.555	1.983	-0.053
1.553	0.379	1.647		-0.555	1.208	1.262
1.553	0.379	1.647		0.312	1.208	-0.053
0.023	1.927	1.647		-0.555	1.208	-0.053
1.553	1.153	1.647		-0.555	1.208	1.262
0.023	1.927	1.647		2.046	1.983	-0.053
0.023	1.927	1.647		2.046	0.434	1.262
1.553	1.153	1.647		2.046	0.434	-0.053
0.788	1.153	1.647		2.046	-0.341	-0.053
1.553	1.153	1.647		2.046	0.434	1.262
1.553	0.379	1.647		1.179	1.208	1.262
0.788	0.379	1.647		0.312	1.208	-0.053
0.788	1.153	1.647		0.312	1.208	-1.367
0.788	1.927	1.647		1.179	0.434	-0.053
0.023	1.927	0.874		0.312	1.208	-0.053

0.788	1.153	0.874	0.312	1.208	-1.367
0.788	-0.395	1.647	0.312	1.208	1.262
0.788	0.379	0.101	0.312	1.208	-0.053
0.788	1.153	1.647	0.312	1.208	-0.053
0.023	-0.395	1.647	1.179	1.208	-1.367
1.553	1.153	1.647	1.179	1.208	-0.053
0.788	1.153	1.647	1.179	1.208	-0.053
0.023	0.379	1.647	1.179	1.208	-0.053
0.788	-0.395	1.647	1.179	1.208	-1.367
1.553	1.927	0.874	1.179	1.983	-0.053

X1.7	X2.6	X2.7	X2.8	X2.9	X3.11
0.619	0.669	0.508	0.581	0.522	0.078
0.432	0.458	0.491	0.337	0.481	-0.032
0.397	0.393	0.425	0.326	0.446	-0.053
0.516	0.583	0.628	0.473	0.572	0.025
1.000	0.684	0.559	0.669	0.571	0.092
0.684	1.000	0.632	0.633	0.591	0.132
0.559	0.632	1.000	0.491	0.705	-0.035
0.669	0.633	0.491	1.000	0.482	0.051
0.571	0.591	0.705	0.482	1.000	-0.079
0.092	0.132	-0.035	0.051	-0.079	1.000
0.159	0.130	-0.037	0.032	-0.044	0.666
0.134	0.162	-0.116	-0.015	-0.085	0.542
0.175	0.076	-0.213	0.128	-0.151	0.370
0.174	0.198	-0.172	0.009	-0.104	0.415
0.068	0.147	-0.190	-0.062	-0.138	0.366
0.521	0.560	0.624	0.527	0.553	0.115
0.601	0.642	0.425	0.465	0.487	0.046
0.163	0.273	0.173	0.080	0.189	-0.068
-0.049	0.127	0.105	0.031	0.092	0.032
0.061	0.236	0.193	0.138	0.245	-0.014
0.091	0.179	0.039	0.043	0.122	0.488
0.043	0.057	-0.059	-0.030	-0.022	0.488

X1.7	X2.6	X2.7	X2.8	X2.9	X3.11
0.640	0.585	0.569	0.517	0.559	0.043
0.559	0.511	0.497	0.451	0.488	0.038
0.600	0.549	0.534	0.485	0.525	0.040
0.652	0.596	0.580	0.527	0.570	0.044
1.000	0.510	0.496	0.450	0.487	0.037
0.510	1.000	0.740	0.672	0.727	-0.005
0.496	0.740	1.000	0.654	0.707	-0.005
0.450	0.672	0.654	1.000	0.642	-0.005

0.487	0.727	0.707	0.642	1.000	-0.005
0.037	-0.005	-0.005	-0.005	-0.005	1.000
0.038	-0.005	-0.005	-0.005	-0.005	0.610
0.036	-0.005	-0.005	-0.004	-0.005	0.577
0.035	-0.005	-0.005	-0.004	-0.005	0.555
0.039	-0.005	-0.005	-0.005	-0.005	0.626
0.034	-0.005	-0.005	-0.004	-0.005	0.548
0.477	0.563	0.548	0.498	0.538	0.076
0.477	0.564	0.549	0.498	0.539	0.076
0.150	0.170	0.166	0.150	0.163	0.046
0.153	0.174	0.169	0.153	0.166	0.047
0.169	0.191	0.186	0.169	0.183	0.052
0.022	0.050	0.048	0.044	0.047	0.430
0.021	0.049	0.048	0.043	0.047	0.426

X1.7	X2.6	X2.7	X2.8	X2.9	X3.11
0.640	0.585	0.569	0.517	0.559	0.043
0.559	0.511	0.497	0.451	0.488	0.038
0.600	0.549	0.534	0.485	0.525	0.040
0.652	0.596	0.580	0.527	0.570	0.044
1.000	0.510	0.496	0.450	0.487	0.037
0.510	1.000	0.740	0.672	0.727	-0.005
0.496	0.740	1.000	0.654	0.707	-0.005
0.450	0.672	0.654	1.000	0.642	-0.005
0.487	0.727	0.707	0.642	1.000	-0.005
0.037	-0.005	-0.005	-0.005	-0.005	1.000
0.038	-0.005	-0.005	-0.005	-0.005	0.610
0.036	-0.005	-0.005	-0.004	-0.005	0.577
0.035	-0.005	-0.005	-0.004	-0.005	0.555
0.039	-0.005	-0.005	-0.005	-0.005	0.626
0.034	-0.005	-0.005	-0.004	-0.005	0.548
0.477	0.563	0.548	0.498	0.538	0.076
0.477	0.564	0.549	0.498	0.539	0.076
0.150	0.170	0.166	0.150	0.163	0.046
0.153	0.174	0.169	0.153	0.166	0.047
0.169	0.191	0.186	0.169	0.183	0.052
0.022	0.050	0.048	0.044	0.047	0.430
0.021	0.049	0.048	0.043	0.047	0.426

X1.7	X2.6	X2.7	X2.8	X2.9	X3.11
1.102	1.178	0.895	0.913	0.919	0.081
0.667	0.698	0.749	0.459	0.733	-0.029
0.634	0.620	0.671	0.459	0.703	-0.049
0.916	1.021	1.102	0.740	1.002	0.026
1.709	1.155	0.946	1.009	0.963	0.091
1.155	1.670	1.056	0.944	0.986	0.130

0.946	1.056	1.673	0.733	1.177	-0.035
1.009	0.944	0.733	1.330	0.718	0.044
0.963	0.986	1.177	0.718	1.666	-0.078
0.091	0.130	-0.035	0.044	-0.078	0.578
0.139	0.112	-0.032	0.024	-0.038	0.338
0.107	0.128	-0.091	-0.011	-0.067	0.251
0.161	0.070	-0.195	0.104	-0.138	0.198
0.151	0.170	-0.147	0.007	-0.089	0.209
0.065	0.138	-0.179	-0.052	-0.130	0.204
0.463	0.492	0.549	0.414	0.486	0.060
0.917	0.968	0.641	0.626	0.734	0.040
0.297	0.490	0.312	0.128	0.338	-0.072
-0.091	0.234	0.193	0.050	0.168	0.034
0.122	0.466	0.382	0.244	0.484	-0.016
0.126	0.246	0.053	0.053	0.167	0.395
0.058	0.076	-0.079	-0.035	-0.029	0.383

X3.14	X3.16	X3.3	X3.5	X3.7	Y1.4	Y1.5	Y2.1	Y2.2	Y2.4	Z1.1	Z1.2
-0.227	-0.165	0.132	0.182	-0.033	-0.885	0.884	0.007	-0.070	0.035	0.026	-0.028
0.213	0.251	0.532	0.633	-1.006	0.280	-0.279	2.026	-1.536	-0.962	-0.425	0.457
-0.227	-0.165	0.132	0.182	-0.033	0.280	-0.279	0.228	-0.579	0.128	0.026	-0.028
-0.227	-0.165	0.132	0.182	-0.033	-0.457	0.456	-0.149	0.476	-0.140	0.026	-0.028
0.764	-0.644	-0.329	-0.337	0.880	-0.885	0.884	-0.241	-0.323	0.410	0.026	-0.028
0.233	-1.145	-0.812	0.627	0.404	-0.457	0.456	-0.102	-0.766	0.540	0.026	-0.028

0.940	-0.478	-0.169	-0.157	-0.330	-0.457	0.456	1.152	-0.987	-0.481	0.026	-0.028
-0.227	-0.165	0.132	0.182	-0.033	-0.457	0.456	0.007	-0.070	0.035	0.044	-0.047
0.513	-1.106	-0.612	-0.568	0.631	-0.457	0.456	-1.469	0.659	0.963	0.026	-0.028
-3.571	0.695	2.538	2.894	2.343	-0.885	0.884	0.410	-0.363	-0.164	0.099	-0.107
-0.227	-0.165	0.132	0.182	-0.033	0.280	-0.279	0.007	-0.070	0.035	0.026	-0.028
-0.671	1.056	-0.272	-0.272	0.937	-0.457	0.456	-0.060	-0.108	0.117	-0.443	0.476
-0.227	-0.165	0.132	0.182	-0.033	1.565	-1.563	0.162	-0.616	0.210	0.007	-0.008
-0.935	0.807	-0.512	-0.543	0.700	-0.457	0.456	-0.149	0.476	-0.140	0.026	-0.028
0.685	0.697	-0.455	-0.391	-0.581	-0.885	0.884	-0.060	-0.108	0.117	0.026	-0.028
1.410	-0.034	-1.158	0.325	0.092	-0.457	0.456	-0.060	-0.108	0.117	0.026	-0.028
-0.240	0.048	0.174	0.142	-0.022	-0.149	0.149	-0.241	-0.323	0.410	0.007	-0.008
0.024	0.297	0.414	0.413	0.216	-0.457	0.456	-0.149	0.476	-0.140	0.026	-0.028
-0.227	-0.165	0.132	0.182	-0.033	-0.457	0.456	0.073	-0.033	-0.047	0.026	-0.028
-0.608	-2.166	1.201	1.300	0.993	1.565	-1.563	0.007	-0.070	0.035	0.007	-0.008
-0.671	1.056	-0.272	-0.272	0.937	0.280	-0.279	0.073	-0.033	-0.047	0.477	-0.512
0.408	0.661	-0.652	-0.702	-0.807	-0.457	0.456	-0.258	-0.220	0.364	0.026	-0.028
-0.227	-0.165	0.132	0.182	-0.033	-0.457	0.456	0.007	-0.070	0.035	0.026	-0.028
0.233	-1.145	-0.812	0.627	0.404	1.565	-1.563	-0.881	1.965	-0.337	-0.443	0.476
0.510	-1.109	-0.614	0.938	0.629	-0.457	0.456	-0.867	0.478	0.516	-1.308	1.405
0.245	0.281	-0.855	-0.842	0.391	-0.457	0.456	0.007	-0.070	0.035	0.026	-0.028
0.215	0.253	0.534	-0.873	-1.003	-0.149	0.149	-0.258	-0.220	0.364	0.026	-0.028
0.689	-0.940	-0.452	-0.387	-0.578	-0.457	0.456	-0.397	0.223	0.234	0.495	-0.532
-0.667	-0.581	-0.269	-0.269	0.940	-0.457	0.456	-0.241	-0.323	0.410	-0.425	0.457
0.513	-1.106	-0.612	-0.568	0.631	0.280	-0.279	-0.149	0.476	-0.140	0.026	-0.028
0.039	0.087	0.374	-1.053	0.206	1.565	-1.563	-0.324	-0.258	0.447	-1.777	1.909
0.940	-0.478	-0.169	-0.157	-0.330	0.829	-0.828	0.007	-0.070	0.035	0.007	-0.008
0.230	0.492	-0.815	0.624	0.400	-0.457	0.456	-0.371	0.985	-0.233	0.026	-0.028
-0.227	-0.165	0.132	0.182	-0.033	-0.457	0.456	-0.258	-0.220	0.364	0.026	-0.028
0.037	0.084	0.372	0.453	0.204	0.280	-0.279	-0.149	0.476	-0.140	0.044	-0.047
0.764	-0.644	-0.329	-0.337	0.880	-0.457	0.456	-0.463	0.185	0.317	0.026	-0.028
-0.227	-0.165	0.132	0.182	-0.033	0.280	-0.279	-0.725	1.418	-0.162	0.099	-0.107
-0.227	-0.165	0.132	0.182	-0.033	-0.457	0.456	0.007	-0.070	0.035	0.007	-0.008
0.243	0.279	-0.857	0.664	0.389	-0.149	0.149	-0.463	0.185	0.317	0.495	-0.532
0.303	0.336	0.614	-0.782	0.443	-0.457	0.456	0.684	0.652	-1.007	0.026	-0.028
0.764	-0.644	-0.329	-0.337	0.880	-0.457	0.456	-0.060	-0.108	0.117	0.026	-0.028
0.479	0.502	0.774	-0.602	-0.766	0.280	-0.279	-0.149	0.476	-0.140	-0.425	0.457
-0.240	0.048	0.174	0.142	-0.022	0.280	-0.279	-0.867	0.478	0.516	0.026	-0.028
0.037	0.084	0.372	0.453	0.204	0.280	-0.279	0.007	-0.070	0.035	-0.425	0.457
-1.127	0.399	0.675	-0.714	0.503	0.280	-0.279	1.152	-0.987	-0.481	1.452	-1.559
-0.495	1.222	-0.112	-0.092	-0.273	-0.149	0.149	-0.215	0.438	-0.058	-0.443	0.476
0.037	0.084	0.372	0.453	0.204	0.829	-0.828	0.007	-0.070	0.035	0.026	-0.028
-0.227	-0.165	0.132	0.182	-0.033	-0.457	0.456	-1.625	1.205	0.787	0.026	-0.028
0.245	0.281	-0.855	-0.842	0.391	-0.885	0.884	0.410	-0.363	-0.164	0.007	-0.008
0.037	0.084	0.372	0.453	0.204	0.280	-0.279	0.007	-0.070	0.035	0.007	-0.008
-0.495	1.222	-0.112	-0.092	-0.273	-0.457	0.456	0.007	-0.070	0.035	0.026	-0.028
0.949	0.947	-0.215	-0.120	-4.448	0.829	-0.828	0.007	-0.070	0.035	0.044	-0.047
0.040	-1.553	0.375	0.456	0.207	0.280	-0.279	-0.397	0.223	0.234	0.026	-0.028
-0.495	1.222	-0.112	-0.092	-0.273	0.280	-0.279	0.007	-0.070	0.035	0.044	-0.047
0.024	0.297	0.414	0.413	0.216	0.280	-0.279	-0.149	0.476	-0.140	0.007	-0.008
-1.141	0.612	0.717	-0.754	0.515	-0.457	0.456	0.998	0.942	-1.464	0.007	-0.008

-0.759	0.973	-0.352	-0.363	-0.510	-0.457	0.456	0.073	-0.033	-0.047	0.026	-0.028
-0.227	-0.165	0.132	0.182	-0.033	-0.457	0.456	1.284	-0.912	-0.646	0.026	-0.028
-0.240	0.048	0.174	0.142	-0.022	0.829	-0.828	0.007	-0.070	0.035	0.026	-0.028
0.037	0.084	0.372	0.453	0.204	0.280	-0.279	0.502	0.436	-0.715	0.063	-0.067
-0.240	0.048	0.174	0.142	-0.022	0.280	-0.279	0.569	0.473	-0.797	0.026	-0.028
0.202	0.466	0.577	-0.913	-0.992	-0.457	0.456	-0.241	-0.323	0.410	0.026	-0.028
-0.169	-0.110	1.601	0.241	0.019	0.280	-0.279	-0.241	-0.323	0.410	0.026	-0.028
0.408	0.661	-0.652	-0.702	-0.807	-0.149	0.149	-0.397	0.223	0.234	0.026	-0.028
0.024	0.297	0.414	0.413	0.216	-0.149	0.149	0.569	0.473	-0.797	0.007	-0.008
-0.240	0.048	0.174	0.142	-0.022	-0.149	0.149	0.255	0.183	-0.340	0.477	-0.512
-0.433	-0.360	1.361	-0.029	-0.218	-0.149	0.149	0.007	-0.070	0.035	0.026	-0.028
-0.240	0.048	0.174	0.142	-0.022	-0.149	0.149	0.007	-0.070	0.035	0.007	-0.008
-0.034	0.242	-1.055	0.353	0.163	-0.578	0.577	0.476	-0.326	-0.247	0.007	-0.008
-0.227	-0.165	0.132	0.182	-0.033	-0.578	0.577	0.722	-1.456	0.186	0.063	-0.067
-0.240	0.048	0.174	0.142	-0.022	-0.578	0.577	0.632	-0.872	-0.072	0.007	-0.008
-0.240	0.048	0.174	0.142	-0.022	0.158	-0.158	0.436	0.399	-0.632	-0.443	0.476
0.734	-0.672	1.060	-0.368	-0.515	-0.149	0.149	0.007	-0.070	0.035	0.007	-0.008
0.024	0.297	0.414	0.413	0.216	-0.149	0.149	-0.397	0.223	0.234	0.007	-0.008
0.026	0.300	0.417	-1.093	0.218	-0.149	0.149	0.814	-0.656	-0.364	0.026	-0.028
-0.227	-0.165	0.132	0.182	-0.033	0.158	-0.158	0.318	-1.163	0.386	0.007	-0.008
0.408	0.661	-0.652	-0.702	-0.807	0.158	-0.158	0.007	-0.070	0.035	-0.443	0.476
0.291	-1.091	0.658	0.687	0.456	0.587	-0.586	0.228	-0.579	0.128	0.026	-0.028
0.391	0.419	-3.556	0.815	0.522	-0.149	0.149	0.476	-0.326	-0.247	0.026	-0.028
0.409	-0.979	-0.652	0.808	-0.806	0.158	-0.158	0.255	0.183	-0.340	0.007	-0.008
-0.227	-0.165	0.132	0.182	-0.033	-0.149	0.149	0.321	0.220	-0.422	0.495	-0.532
-0.491	-0.415	-0.108	-0.089	-0.270	0.158	-0.158	-0.685	0.694	0.224	0.026	-0.028
1.001	-2.060	1.303	-0.094	-0.275	-0.149	0.149	-1.807	0.990	1.080	0.026	-0.028
-0.227	-0.165	0.132	0.182	-0.033	-0.149	0.149	0.476	-0.326	-0.247	0.026	-0.028
0.676	-0.727	-0.409	-0.427	-0.567	0.587	-0.586	-0.933	0.441	0.598	0.007	-0.008
-0.759	0.973	-0.352	-0.363	-0.510	-0.028	0.028	-1.089	0.987	0.423	0.026	-0.028
0.940	-0.478	-0.169	-0.157	-0.330	0.708	-0.707	0.228	-0.579	0.128	0.026	-0.028
0.333	0.364	-0.775	-0.752	1.838	-0.149	0.149	0.880	-0.619	-0.446	0.532	-0.571
-0.227	-0.165	0.132	0.182	-0.033	0.280	-0.279	0.476	-0.326	-0.247	0.026	-0.028
-0.495	1.222	-0.112	-0.092	-0.273	0.587	-0.586	0.162	-0.616	0.210	0.007	-0.008
0.037	0.084	0.372	0.453	0.204	-0.149	0.149	0.007	-0.070	0.035	0.026	-0.028
-0.240	0.048	0.174	0.142	-0.022	1.016	-1.014	0.476	-0.326	-0.247	0.007	-0.008
0.672	0.910	-0.412	-0.431	-0.570	-0.149	0.149	-0.463	0.185	0.317	0.026	-0.028
-0.227	-0.165	0.132	0.182	-0.033	0.158	-0.158	0.255	0.183	-0.340	0.026	-0.028
0.701	0.487	-0.495	-1.856	-0.591	0.280	-0.279	0.007	-0.070	0.035	0.063	-0.067
-0.495	1.222	-0.112	-0.092	-0.273	-0.149	0.149	0.476	-0.326	-0.247	0.026	-0.028
0.215	0.253	0.534	-0.873	-1.003	0.587	-0.586	-0.463	0.185	0.317	0.495	-0.532
-0.227	-0.165	0.132	0.182	-0.033	0.587	-0.586	0.410	-0.363	-0.164	0.026	-0.028
1.159	-0.496	-1.441	0.094	-0.156	0.587	-0.586	-1.337	0.734	0.798	0.063	-0.067
-0.227	-0.165	0.132	0.182	-0.033	0.587	-0.586	0.724	-0.073	-0.622	0.026	-0.028

X3.14	X3.16	X3.3	X3.5	X3.7	Y1.4	Y1.5	Y2.1	Y2.2	Y2.4	Z1.1	Z1.2
-0.057	0.194	-0.037	-0.181	0.021	-0.068	0.068	0.096	-0.200	0.033	0.028	-0.028
0.088	-0.111	-0.093	0.071	0.019	-0.056	0.056	-0.222	0.219	0.116	0.035	-0.035

0.018	0.049	0.001	0.043	0.009	0.166	-0.166	-0.071	0.116	0.001	-0.076	0.076
0.033	-0.112	-0.052	-0.104	0.057	-0.008	0.008	-0.038	0.055	0.005	0.119	-0.119
-0.062	-0.032	0.146	0.139	-0.083	-0.019	0.019	0.185	-0.142	-0.130	-0.082	0.082
-0.159	0.077	-0.063	0.179	0.187	-0.262	0.262	0.130	-0.043	-0.137	0.018	-0.018
0.162	-0.004	-0.189	-0.147	-0.090	0.250	-0.250	-0.019	0.071	-0.031	-0.040	0.040
-0.058	-0.094	0.305	-0.041	-0.095	0.016	-0.016	-0.074	0.030	0.074	-0.068	0.068
0.071	0.023	-0.074	-0.002	-0.009	0.018	-0.018	-0.039	-0.053	0.094	0.089	-0.089
0.144	-0.083	-0.420	-0.566	-0.407	0.063	-0.063	-0.160	0.056	0.166	0.050	-0.050
1.000	-0.326	-0.446	-0.373	-0.381	0.085	-0.085	-0.236	0.072	0.254	-0.103	0.103
-0.326	1.000	-0.100	-0.247	-0.198	-0.182	0.182	0.264	-0.106	-0.263	0.067	-0.067
-0.446	-0.100	1.000	0.192	0.041	0.116	-0.116	0.121	-0.071	-0.103	0.028	-0.028
-0.373	-0.247	0.192	1.000	0.290	0.056	-0.056	0.058	0.001	-0.077	-0.043	0.043
-0.381	-0.198	0.041	0.290	1.000	-0.192	0.192	0.060	0.018	-0.093	0.022	-0.022
0.085	-0.182	0.116	0.056	-0.192	1.000	-1.000	-0.040	0.075	-0.008	-0.157	0.157
-0.085	0.182	-0.116	-0.056	0.192	-1.000	1.000	0.040	-0.075	0.008	0.157	-0.157
-0.236	0.264	0.121	0.058	0.060	-0.040	0.040	1.000	-0.654	-0.794	0.160	-0.160
0.072	-0.106	-0.071	0.001	0.018	0.075	-0.075	-0.654	1.000	0.059	-0.106	0.106
0.254	-0.263	-0.103	-0.077	-0.093	-0.008	0.008	-0.794	0.059	1.000	-0.126	0.126
-0.103	0.067	0.028	-0.043	0.022	-0.157	0.157	0.160	-0.106	-0.126	1.000	-1.000
0.103	-0.067	-0.028	0.043	-0.022	0.157	-0.157	-0.160	0.106	0.126	-1.000	1.000

X3.14	X3.16	X3.3	X3.5	X3.7	Y1.4	Y1.5	Y2.1	Y2.2	Y2.4	Z1.1	Z1.2
0.219	0.219	0.219	0.219	0.219	0.595	0.595	0.390	0.390	0.390	0.531	0.531
0.279	0.206	0.184	0.225	0.163	0.597	0.593	0.419	0.283	0.465	0.551	0.510
0.279	0.206	0.184	0.224	0.163	0.595	0.595	0.428	0.272	0.467	0.550	0.512
0.279	0.206	0.184	0.224	0.163	0.594	0.595	0.428	0.272	0.467	0.550	0.512
0.279	0.206	0.184	0.224	0.163	0.594	0.595	0.428	0.272	0.467	0.550	0.512
0.279	0.206	0.184	0.224	0.163	0.594	0.595	0.428	0.272	0.467	0.550	0.512
0.279	0.206	0.184	0.224	0.163	0.594	0.595	0.428	0.272	0.467	0.550	0.512
0.279	0.206	0.184	0.224	0.163	0.594	0.595	0.428	0.272	0.467	0.550	0.512

X3.14	X3.16	X3.3	X3.5	X3.7	Y1.4	Y1.5	Y2.1	Y2.2	Y2.4	Z1.1	Z1.2
6.000	6.000	6.000	6.000	6.000	5.000	6.000	6.000	6.000	6.000	6.000	6.000
6.000	6.000	6.000	6.000	5.000	6.000	5.000	6.000	1.000	1.000	5.000	6.000
6.000	6.000	6.000	6.000	6.000	6.000	5.000	7.000	6.000	7.000	6.000	6.000
6.000	6.000	6.000	6.000	6.000	5.000	5.000	6.000	7.000	6.000	6.000	6.000
7.000	6.000	6.000	6.000	7.000	5.000	6.000	6.000	6.000	7.000	6.000	6.000
7.000	6.000	6.000	7.000	7.000	5.000	5.000	2.000	1.000	2.000	6.000	6.000
7.000	6.000	6.000	6.000	6.000	5.000	5.000	5.000	2.000	2.000	6.000	6.000
6.000	6.000	6.000	6.000	6.000	5.000	5.000	6.000	6.000	6.000	5.000	5.000
6.000	5.000	5.000	5.000	6.000	5.000	5.000	2.000	5.000	5.000	6.000	6.000
2.000	5.000	6.000	6.000	6.000	5.000	6.000	6.000	5.000	5.000	2.000	2.000
6.000	6.000	6.000	6.000	6.000	6.000	5.000	6.000	6.000	6.000	6.000	6.000
6.000	7.000	6.000	6.000	7.000	5.000	5.000	5.000	5.000	5.000	6.000	7.000
6.000	6.000	6.000	6.000	6.000	6.000	2.000	6.000	5.000	6.000	7.000	7.000
6.000	7.000	6.000	6.000	7.000	5.000	5.000	6.000	7.000	6.000	6.000	6.000
6.000	6.000	5.000	5.000	5.000	5.000	6.000	5.000	5.000	5.000	6.000	6.000
7.000	6.000	5.000	6.000	6.000	5.000	5.000	5.000	5.000	5.000	6.000	6.000
7.000	7.000	7.000	7.000	7.000	6.000	6.000	6.000	6.000	7.000	7.000	7.000
7.000	7.000	7.000	7.000	7.000	5.000	5.000	6.000	7.000	6.000	6.000	6.000
6.000	6.000	6.000	6.000	6.000	5.000	5.000	7.000	7.000	7.000	6.000	6.000
6.000	5.000	7.000	7.000	7.000	6.000	2.000	6.000	6.000	6.000	7.000	7.000

7.000	7.000	7.000	7.000	7.000	6.000	7.000	7.000	5.000	6.000	7.000	7.000
7.000	7.000	7.000	7.000	7.000	7.000	7.000	5.000	5.000	3.000	6.000	7.000
7.000	6.000	7.000	6.000	6.000	6.000	6.000	6.000	6.000	6.000	7.000	7.000
7.000	7.000	7.000	7.000	7.000	6.000	6.000	6.000	7.000	7.000	7.000	7.000
7.000	7.000	7.000	6.000	7.000	6.000	6.000	6.000	4.000	4.000	6.000	6.000
6.000	6.000	6.000	6.000	6.000	7.000	7.000	6.000	4.000	6.000	7.000	7.000
7.000	7.000	6.000	6.000	6.000	7.000	7.000	6.000	6.000	6.000	6.000	7.000
7.000	6.000	7.000	7.000	7.000	7.000	6.000	7.000	6.000	7.000	6.000	6.000
6.000	6.000	3.000	6.000	6.000	6.000	6.000	7.000	6.000	6.000	6.000	6.000
7.000	6.000	6.000	7.000	6.000	7.000	7.000	6.000	6.000	5.000	7.000	7.000
6.000	6.000	6.000	6.000	6.000	6.000	6.000	7.000	7.000	6.000	6.000	5.000
6.000	6.000	6.000	6.000	6.000	7.000	7.000	4.000	6.000	5.000	6.000	6.000
7.000	5.000	7.000	6.000	6.000	6.000	6.000	3.000	7.000	7.000	6.000	6.000
6.000	6.000	6.000	6.000	6.000	6.000	6.000	7.000	6.000	6.000	6.000	6.000
7.000	6.000	6.000	6.000	6.000	7.000	6.000	4.000	6.000	6.000	7.000	7.000
6.000	7.000	6.000	6.000	6.000	5.000	4.000	4.000	7.000	6.000	6.000	6.000
7.000	6.000	6.000	6.000	6.000	6.000	4.000	7.000	6.000	7.000	6.000	6.000
6.000	6.000	5.000	5.000	7.000	6.000	6.000	7.000	5.000	5.000	4.000	3.000
6.000	6.000	6.000	6.000	6.000	6.000	5.000	7.000	6.000	6.000	6.000	6.000
6.000	7.000	6.000	6.000	6.000	7.000	6.000	6.000	5.000	6.000	7.000	7.000
6.000	6.000	6.000	6.000	6.000	6.000	6.000	6.000	6.000	6.000	6.000	6.000
7.000	7.000	7.000	7.000	7.000	7.000	5.000	7.000	6.000	6.000	7.000	7.000
7.000	7.000	6.000	6.000	6.000	6.000	6.000	5.000	6.000	6.000	6.000	6.000
6.000	6.000	6.000	6.000	6.000	7.000	7.000	6.000	6.000	5.000	6.000	6.000
5.000	5.000	4.000	3.000	4.000	6.000	5.000	6.000	6.000	6.000	4.000	4.000
6.000	7.000	6.000	6.000	6.000	6.000	6.000	7.000	6.000	6.000	6.000	6.000
6.000	6.000	6.000	5.000	5.000	7.000	6.000	5.000	6.000	6.000	6.000	5.000
6.000	6.000	6.000	6.000	6.000	7.000	6.000	6.000	5.000	5.000	6.000	6.000
6.000	5.000	4.000	5.000	5.000	7.000	6.000	4.000	7.000	7.000	4.000	4.000
6.000	6.000	6.000	6.000	6.000	7.000	6.000	7.000	6.000	5.000	6.000	6.000

X3.14	X3.16	X3.3	X3.5	X3.7	Y1.4	Y1.5	Y2.1	Y2.2	Y2.4	Z1.1	Z1.2
-0.434	-0.361	-0.057	-0.030	-0.219	-1.118	0.651	0.324	0.254	0.392	0.122	0.068
-0.434	-0.361	-0.057	-0.030	-1.587	0.353	-0.206	0.324	-3.272	-2.876	-0.817	0.068
-0.434	-0.361	-0.057	-0.030	-0.219	0.353	-0.206	1.044	0.254	1.046	0.122	0.068
-0.434	-0.361	-0.057	-0.030	-0.219	-1.118	-0.206	0.324	0.959	0.392	0.122	0.068
1.063	-0.361	-0.057	-0.030	1.149	-1.118	0.651	0.324	0.254	1.046	0.122	0.068
1.063	-0.361	-0.057	1.478	1.149	-1.118	-0.206	-2.557	-3.272	-2.223	0.122	0.068
1.063	-0.361	-0.057	-0.030	-0.219	-1.118	-0.206	-0.396	-2.567	-2.223	0.122	0.068
-0.434	-0.361	-0.057	-0.030	-0.219	-1.118	-0.206	0.324	0.254	0.392	-0.817	-0.901
-0.434	-2.001	-1.473	-1.538	-0.219	-1.118	-0.206	-2.557	-0.451	-0.261	0.122	0.068
-6.424	-2.001	-0.057	-0.030	-0.219	-1.118	0.651	0.324	-0.451	-0.261	-3.636	-3.808
-0.434	-0.361	-0.057	-0.030	-0.219	0.353	-0.206	0.324	0.254	0.392	0.122	0.068
-0.434	1.280	-0.057	-0.030	1.149	-1.118	-0.206	-0.396	-0.451	-0.261	0.122	1.037
-0.434	-0.361	-0.057	-0.030	-0.219	0.353	-2.776	0.324	-0.451	0.392	1.062	1.037
-0.434	1.280	-0.057	-0.030	1.149	-1.118	-0.206	0.324	0.959	0.392	0.122	0.068
-0.434	-0.361	-1.473	-1.538	-1.587	-1.118	0.651	-0.396	-0.451	-0.261	0.122	0.068
1.063	-0.361	-1.473	-0.030	-0.219	-1.118	-0.206	-0.396	-0.451	-0.261	0.122	0.068
1.063	1.280	1.360	1.478	1.149	0.353	0.651	0.324	0.254	1.046	1.062	1.037
1.063	1.280	1.360	1.478	1.149	-1.118	-0.206	0.324	0.959	0.392	0.122	0.068
-0.434	-0.361	-0.057	-0.030	-0.219	-1.118	-0.206	1.044	0.959	1.046	0.122	0.068
-0.434	-2.001	1.360	1.478	1.149	0.353	-2.776	0.324	0.254	0.392	1.062	1.037
-0.434	1.280	-0.057	-0.030	1.149	0.353	-0.206	1.044	0.959	1.046	1.062	0.068
1.063	1.280	-0.057	-0.030	-0.219	-1.118	-0.206	-2.557	-2.567	-2.223	0.122	0.068
-0.434	-0.361	-0.057	-0.030	-0.219	-1.118	-0.206	0.324	0.254	0.392	0.122	0.068
1.063	-0.361	-0.057	1.478	1.149	0.353	-2.776	-2.557	0.254	-2.223	0.122	1.037
-0.434	-2.001	-1.473	-0.030	-0.219	-1.118	-0.206	-0.396	0.959	1.046	-3.636	-0.901
-0.434	-0.361	-1.473	-1.538	-0.219	-1.118	-0.206	0.324	0.254	0.392	0.122	0.068
-0.434	-0.361	-0.057	-1.538	-1.587	0.353	0.651	-2.557	-2.567	-2.223	0.122	0.068
-0.434	-2.001	-1.473	-1.538	-1.587	-1.118	-0.206	0.324	0.959	1.046	0.122	-0.901
-0.434	-0.361	-0.057	-0.030	1.149	-1.118	-0.206	0.324	0.254	1.046	-0.817	0.068
-0.434	-2.001	-1.473	-1.538	-0.219	0.353	-0.206	0.324	0.959	0.392	0.122	0.068
-0.434	-0.361	-0.057	-1.538	-0.219	0.353	-2.776	-3.277	-3.272	-2.876	-3.636	0.068
1.063	-0.361	-0.057	-0.030	-0.219	-1.118	-2.776	0.324	0.254	0.392	1.062	1.037
1.063	1.280	-0.057	1.478	1.149	-1.118	-0.206	-0.396	0.959	-0.261	0.122	0.068
-0.434	-0.361	-0.057	-0.030	-0.219	-1.118	-0.206	-2.557	-2.567	-2.223	0.122	0.068
-0.434	-0.361	-0.057	-0.030	-0.219	0.353	-0.206	0.324	0.959	0.392	-0.817	-0.901
1.063	-0.361	-0.057	-0.030	1.149	-1.118	-0.206	-0.396	0.254	0.392	0.122	0.068
-0.434	-0.361	-0.057	-0.030	-0.219	0.353	-0.206	-2.557	-0.451	-2.223	-3.636	-3.808
-0.434	-0.361	-0.057	-0.030	-0.219	-1.118	-0.206	0.324	0.254	0.392	1.062	1.037
-0.434	-0.361	-1.473	-0.030	-0.219	0.353	0.651	-0.396	0.254	0.392	0.122	-0.901
-0.434	-0.361	-0.057	-1.538	-0.219	-1.118	-0.206	-0.396	-0.451	-2.223	0.122	0.068

1.063	-0.361	-0.057	-0.030	1.149	-1.118	-0.206	-0.396	-0.451	-0.261	0.122	0.068
-0.434	-0.361	-0.057	-1.538	-1.587	0.353	-0.206	0.324	0.959	0.392	-0.817	0.068
1.063	1.280	1.360	1.478	1.149	0.353	-0.206	-0.396	0.959	1.046	0.122	0.068
-0.434	-0.361	-0.057	-0.030	-0.219	0.353	-0.206	0.324	0.254	0.392	-0.817	0.068
-1.932	-0.361	-0.057	-1.538	-0.219	0.353	-0.206	-0.396	-2.567	-2.223	-0.817	-3.808
-0.434	1.280	-0.057	-0.030	-0.219	0.353	0.651	-0.396	0.254	-0.261	0.122	1.037
-0.434	-0.361	-0.057	-0.030	-0.219	-1.118	-2.776	0.324	0.254	0.392	0.122	0.068
-0.434	-0.361	-0.057	-0.030	-0.219	-1.118	-0.206	-2.557	0.254	-0.261	0.122	0.068
-0.434	-0.361	-1.473	-1.538	-0.219	-1.118	0.651	0.324	-0.451	-0.261	1.062	1.037
-0.434	-0.361	-0.057	-0.030	-0.219	0.353	-0.206	0.324	0.254	0.392	1.062	1.037
-0.434	1.280	-0.057	-0.030	-0.219	-1.118	-0.206	0.324	0.254	0.392	0.122	0.068
-0.434	-0.361	-1.473	-1.538	-5.691	-1.118	-2.776	0.324	0.254	0.392	-0.817	-0.901
-0.434	-2.001	-0.057	-0.030	-0.219	0.353	-0.206	0.324	0.959	1.046	0.122	0.068
-0.434	1.280	-0.057	-0.030	-0.219	0.353	-0.206	0.324	0.254	0.392	-0.817	-0.901
1.063	1.280	1.360	1.478	1.149	0.353	-0.206	0.324	0.959	0.392	1.062	1.037
-0.434	1.280	1.360	-0.030	1.149	-1.118	-0.206	0.324	0.254	-2.223	1.062	1.037
-0.434	1.280	-0.057	-0.030	-0.219	-1.118	-0.206	1.044	0.959	1.046	0.122	0.068
-0.434	-0.361	-0.057	-0.030	-0.219	-1.118	-0.206	1.044	-1.157	-0.915	0.122	0.068
1.063	1.280	1.360	1.478	1.149	-1.118	-2.776	0.324	0.254	0.392	0.122	0.068
-0.434	-0.361	-0.057	-0.030	-0.219	0.353	-0.206	0.324	0.254	-0.915	-1.757	-1.870
1.063	1.280	1.360	1.478	1.149	0.353	-0.206	1.044	0.959	-0.261	0.122	0.068
1.063	1.280	1.360	-0.030	-0.219	-1.118	-0.206	0.324	0.254	1.046	0.122	0.068
-0.434	-0.361	1.360	-0.030	-0.219	0.353	-0.206	0.324	0.254	1.046	0.122	0.068
1.063	1.280	-0.057	-0.030	-0.219	0.353	0.651	0.324	0.959	1.046	0.122	0.068
1.063	1.280	1.360	1.478	1.149	0.353	0.651	1.044	0.959	-0.261	1.062	1.037
1.063	1.280	1.360	1.478	1.149	0.353	0.651	0.324	0.254	-0.261	1.062	0.068
-0.434	-0.361	1.360	-0.030	-0.219	0.353	0.651	0.324	0.254	0.392	0.122	0.068
1.063	1.280	1.360	1.478	1.149	0.353	0.651	0.324	0.254	0.392	1.062	1.037
1.063	1.280	-0.057	1.478	1.149	0.353	1.508	1.044	0.254	0.392	1.062	1.037
-0.434	-0.361	-0.057	-0.030	-0.219	0.353	1.508	0.324	-1.862	-0.261	-1.757	-1.870
1.063	1.280	1.360	1.478	1.149	0.353	1.508	1.044	-0.451	0.392	1.062	1.037
1.063	1.280	1.360	1.478	1.149	1.824	1.508	-0.396	-0.451	-1.569	0.122	1.037
1.063	-0.361	1.360	-0.030	-0.219	0.353	0.651	0.324	0.254	0.392	1.062	1.037
1.063	1.280	1.360	1.478	1.149	0.353	0.651	0.324	0.959	1.046	1.062	1.037
1.063	1.280	1.360	-0.030	1.149	0.353	0.651	0.324	-1.157	-0.915	0.122	0.068
-0.434	-0.361	-0.057	-0.030	-0.219	1.824	1.508	0.324	-1.157	0.392	1.062	1.037
1.063	1.280	-0.057	-0.030	-0.219	1.824	1.508	0.324	0.254	0.392	0.122	1.037
1.063	-0.361	1.360	1.478	1.149	1.824	0.651	1.044	0.254	1.046	0.122	0.068
-0.434	-0.361	-4.306	-0.030	-0.219	0.353	0.651	1.044	0.254	0.392	0.122	0.068
1.063	-0.361	-0.057	1.478	-0.219	1.824	1.508	0.324	0.254	-0.261	1.062	1.037
-0.434	-0.361	-0.057	-0.030	-0.219	0.353	0.651	1.044	0.959	0.392	0.122	-0.901
-0.434	-0.361	-0.057	-0.030	-0.219	1.824	1.508	-1.116	0.254	-0.261	0.122	0.068
1.063	-2.001	1.360	-0.030	-0.219	0.353	0.651	-1.837	0.959	1.046	0.122	0.068
-0.434	-0.361	-0.057	-0.030	-0.219	0.353	0.651	1.044	0.254	0.392	0.122	0.068
1.063	-0.361	-0.057	-0.030	-0.219	1.824	0.651	-1.116	0.254	0.392	1.062	1.037
-0.434	1.280	-0.057	-0.030	-0.219	-1.118	-1.062	-1.116	0.959	0.392	0.122	0.068
1.063	-0.361	-0.057	-0.030	-0.219	0.353	-1.062	1.044	0.254	1.046	0.122	0.068
-0.434	-0.361	-1.473	-1.538	1.149	0.353	0.651	1.044	-0.451	-0.261	-1.757	-2.839
-0.434	-0.361	-0.057	-0.030	-0.219	0.353	-0.206	1.044	0.254	0.392	0.122	0.068
-0.434	1.280	-0.057	-0.030	-0.219	1.824	0.651	0.324	-0.451	0.392	1.062	1.037

-0.434	-0.361	-0.057	-0.030	-0.219	0.353	0.651	0.324	0.254	0.392	0.122	0.068
1.063	1.280	1.360	1.478	1.149	1.824	-0.206	1.044	0.254	0.392	1.062	1.037
1.063	1.280	-0.057	-0.030	-0.219	0.353	0.651	-0.396	0.254	0.392	0.122	0.068
-0.434	-0.361	-0.057	-0.030	-0.219	1.824	1.508	0.324	0.254	-0.261	0.122	0.068
-1.932	-2.001	-2.890	-4.555	-2.955	0.353	-0.206	0.324	0.254	0.392	-1.757	-1.870
-0.434	1.280	-0.057	-0.030	-0.219	0.353	0.651	1.044	0.254	0.392	0.122	0.068
-0.434	-0.361	-0.057	-1.538	-1.587	1.824	0.651	-0.396	0.254	0.392	0.122	-0.901
-0.434	-0.361	-0.057	-0.030	-0.219	1.824	0.651	0.324	-0.451	-0.261	0.122	0.068
-0.434	-2.001	-2.890	-1.538	-1.587	1.824	0.651	-1.116	0.959	1.046	-1.757	-1.870
-0.434	-0.361	-0.057	-0.030	-0.219	1.824	0.651	1.044	0.254	-0.261	0.122	0.068

X3.14	X3.16	X3.3	X3.5	X3.7	Y1.4	Y1.5	Y2.1	Y2.2	Y2.4	Z1.1	Z1.2
0.108	0.156	0.032	-0.005	0.053	0.524	0.638	0.263	0.079	0.263	0.100	-0.006
0.059	-0.053	-0.083	-0.018	-0.029	0.377	0.485	0.115	0.197	0.250	0.055	-0.045
0.054	0.036	-0.022	-0.012	-0.017	0.461	0.426	0.202	0.173	0.247	0.062	0.002
0.056	-0.023	-0.046	-0.064	-0.008	0.495	0.577	0.174	0.099	0.200	0.022	-0.114
0.159	0.134	0.175	0.174	0.068	0.521	0.601	0.163	-0.049	0.061	0.091	0.043
0.130	0.162	0.076	0.198	0.147	0.560	0.642	0.273	0.127	0.236	0.179	0.057
-0.037	-0.116	-0.213	-0.172	-0.190	0.624	0.425	0.173	0.105	0.193	0.039	-0.059
0.032	-0.015	0.128	0.009	-0.062	0.527	0.465	0.080	0.031	0.138	0.043	-0.030
-0.044	-0.085	-0.151	-0.104	-0.138	0.553	0.487	0.189	0.092	0.245	0.122	-0.022
0.666	0.542	0.370	0.415	0.366	0.115	0.046	-0.068	0.032	-0.014	0.488	0.488
1.000	0.457	0.378	0.506	0.397	0.109	0.026	-0.043	0.089	0.063	0.503	0.566
0.457	1.000	0.491	0.509	0.437	0.031	0.137	0.188	0.068	-0.019	0.383	0.374
0.378	0.491	1.000	0.661	0.530	0.124	0.013	0.100	0.044	-0.015	0.340	0.347
0.506	0.509	0.661	1.000	0.695	0.122	0.058	0.151	0.157	0.081	0.386	0.426
0.397	0.437	0.530	0.695	1.000	-0.003	0.119	0.091	0.094	0.005	0.297	0.306
0.109	0.031	0.124	0.122	-0.003	1.000	0.413	0.129	0.056	0.073	0.095	0.076
0.026	0.137	0.013	0.058	0.119	0.413	1.000	0.178	0.034	0.103	0.114	-0.019
-0.043	0.188	0.100	0.151	0.091	0.129	0.178	1.000	0.461	0.556	0.272	0.104
0.089	0.068	0.044	0.157	0.094	0.056	0.034	0.461	1.000	0.772	0.201	0.133
0.063	-0.019	-0.015	0.081	0.005	0.073	0.103	0.556	0.772	1.000	0.228	0.144
0.503	0.383	0.340	0.386	0.297	0.095	0.114	0.272	0.201	0.228	1.000	0.775
0.566	0.374	0.347	0.426	0.306	0.076	-0.019	0.104	0.133	0.144	0.775	1.000

X3.14	X3.16	X3.3	X3.5	X3.7	Y1.4	Y1.5	Y2.1	Y2.2	Y2.4	Z1.1	Z1.2
0.044	0.042	0.040	0.045	0.040	0.547	0.547	0.173	0.176	0.194	0.025	0.025
0.038	0.036	0.035	0.039	0.035	0.478	0.478	0.151	0.154	0.170	0.022	0.022
0.041	0.039	0.038	0.042	0.037	0.513	0.514	0.162	0.165	0.182	0.023	0.023
0.045	0.042	0.041	0.046	0.040	0.557	0.558	0.176	0.180	0.198	0.025	0.025
0.038	0.036	0.035	0.039	0.034	0.477	0.477	0.150	0.153	0.169	0.022	0.021
-0.005	-0.005	-0.005	-0.005	-0.005	0.563	0.564	0.170	0.174	0.191	0.050	0.049
-0.005	-0.005	-0.005	-0.005	-0.005	0.548	0.549	0.166	0.169	0.186	0.048	0.048
-0.005	-0.004	-0.004	-0.005	-0.004	0.498	0.498	0.150	0.153	0.169	0.044	0.043

-0.005	-0.005	-0.005	-0.005	-0.005	0.538	0.539	0.163	0.166	0.183	0.047	0.047
0.610	0.577	0.555	0.626	0.548	0.076	0.076	0.046	0.047	0.052	0.430	0.426
1.000	0.590	0.568	0.640	0.561	0.078	0.078	0.047	0.048	0.053	0.440	0.436
0.590	1.000	0.537	0.605	0.530	0.074	0.074	0.045	0.046	0.050	0.416	0.412
0.568	0.537	1.000	0.582	0.510	0.071	0.071	0.043	0.044	0.048	0.400	0.396
0.640	0.605	0.582	1.000	0.575	0.080	0.080	0.049	0.050	0.055	0.451	0.447
0.561	0.530	0.510	0.575	1.000	0.070	0.070	0.042	0.043	0.048	0.395	0.391
0.078	0.074	0.071	0.080	0.070	1.000	0.706	0.097	0.099	0.109	0.068	0.067
0.078	0.074	0.071	0.080	0.070	0.706	1.000	0.097	0.099	0.109	0.068	0.067
0.047	0.045	0.043	0.049	0.042	0.097	0.097	1.000	0.674	0.743	0.176	0.174
0.048	0.046	0.044	0.050	0.043	0.099	0.099	0.674	1.000	0.758	0.179	0.178
0.053	0.050	0.048	0.055	0.048	0.109	0.109	0.743	0.758	1.000	0.197	0.196
0.440	0.416	0.400	0.451	0.395	0.068	0.068	0.176	0.179	0.197	1.000	0.887
0.436	0.412	0.396	0.447	0.391	0.067	0.067	0.174	0.178	0.196	0.887	1.000

X3.14	X3.16	X3.3	X3.5	X3.7	Y1.4	Y1.5	Y2.1	Y2.2	Y2.4	Z1.1	Z1.2
0.044	0.042	0.040	0.045	0.040	0.547	0.547	0.173	0.176	0.194	0.025	0.025
0.038	0.036	0.035	0.039	0.035	0.478	0.478	0.151	0.154	0.170	0.022	0.022
0.041	0.039	0.038	0.042	0.037	0.513	0.514	0.162	0.165	0.182	0.023	0.023
0.045	0.042	0.041	0.046	0.040	0.557	0.558	0.176	0.180	0.198	0.025	0.025
0.038	0.036	0.035	0.039	0.034	0.477	0.477	0.150	0.153	0.169	0.022	0.021
-0.005	-0.005	-0.005	-0.005	-0.005	0.563	0.564	0.170	0.174	0.191	0.050	0.049
-0.005	-0.005	-0.005	-0.005	-0.005	0.548	0.549	0.166	0.169	0.186	0.048	0.048
-0.005	-0.004	-0.004	-0.005	-0.004	0.498	0.498	0.150	0.153	0.169	0.044	0.043
-0.005	-0.005	-0.005	-0.005	-0.005	0.538	0.539	0.163	0.166	0.183	0.047	0.047
0.610	0.577	0.555	0.626	0.548	0.076	0.076	0.046	0.047	0.052	0.430	0.426
1.000	0.590	0.568	0.640	0.561	0.078	0.078	0.047	0.048	0.053	0.440	0.436
0.590	1.000	0.537	0.605	0.530	0.074	0.074	0.045	0.046	0.050	0.416	0.412
0.568	0.537	1.000	0.582	0.510	0.071	0.071	0.043	0.044	0.048	0.400	0.396
0.640	0.605	0.582	1.000	0.575	0.080	0.080	0.049	0.050	0.055	0.451	0.447
0.561	0.530	0.510	0.575	1.000	0.070	0.070	0.042	0.043	0.048	0.395	0.391
0.078	0.074	0.071	0.080	0.070	1.000	0.706	0.145	0.148	0.163	0.068	0.067
0.078	0.074	0.071	0.080	0.070	0.706	1.000	0.145	0.148	0.163	0.068	0.067
0.047	0.045	0.043	0.049	0.042	0.145	0.145	1.000	0.674	0.743	0.176	0.174
0.048	0.046	0.044	0.050	0.043	0.148	0.148	0.674	1.000	0.758	0.179	0.178
0.053	0.050	0.048	0.055	0.048	0.163	0.163	0.743	0.758	1.000	0.197	0.196
0.440	0.416	0.400	0.451	0.395	0.068	0.068	0.176	0.179	0.197	1.000	0.887
0.436	0.412	0.396	0.447	0.391	0.067	0.067	0.174	0.178	0.196	0.887	1.000

X3.14	X3.16	X3.3	X3.5	X3.7	Y1.4	Y1.5	Y2.1	Y2.2	Y2.4	Z1.1	Z1.2
0.098	0.129	0.031	-0.005	0.053	0.485	1.015	0.499	0.153	0.548	0.145	-0.009
0.046	-0.038	-0.069	-0.014	-0.025	0.303	0.667	0.189	0.329	0.452	0.069	-0.055
0.044	0.027	-0.019	-0.009	-0.015	0.383	0.607	0.342	0.299	0.462	0.081	0.003
0.051	-0.019	-0.044	-0.057	-0.008	0.456	0.914	0.327	0.190	0.416	0.032	-0.160
0.139	0.107	0.161	0.151	0.065	0.463	0.917	0.297	-0.091	0.122	0.126	0.058
0.112	0.128	0.070	0.170	0.138	0.492	0.968	0.490	0.234	0.466	0.246	0.076

-0.032	-0.091	-0.195	-0.147	-0.179	0.549	0.641	0.312	0.193	0.382	0.053	-0.079
0.024	-0.011	0.104	0.007	-0.052	0.414	0.626	0.128	0.050	0.244	0.053	-0.035
-0.038	-0.067	-0.138	-0.089	-0.130	0.486	0.734	0.338	0.168	0.484	0.167	-0.029
0.338	0.251	0.198	0.209	0.204	0.060	0.040	-0.072	0.034	-0.016	0.395	0.383
0.446	0.186	0.178	0.224	0.194	0.050	0.020	-0.040	0.084	0.064	0.358	0.390
0.186	0.372	0.211	0.206	0.195	0.013	0.097	0.159	0.059	-0.018	0.249	0.235
0.178	0.211	0.498	0.309	0.274	0.060	0.010	0.098	0.044	-0.016	0.255	0.253
0.224	0.206	0.309	0.440	0.337	0.055	0.045	0.139	0.147	0.082	0.273	0.291
0.194	0.195	0.274	0.337	0.534	-0.002	0.102	0.092	0.098	0.006	0.231	0.231
0.050	0.013	0.060	0.055	-0.002	0.462	0.328	0.122	0.054	0.076	0.069	0.053
0.020	0.097	0.010	0.045	0.102	0.328	1.362	0.288	0.056	0.184	0.141	-0.023
-0.040	0.159	0.098	0.139	0.092	0.122	0.288	1.928	0.908	1.180	0.402	0.149
0.084	0.059	0.044	0.147	0.098	0.054	0.056	0.908	2.010	1.674	0.303	0.195
0.064	-0.018	-0.016	0.082	0.006	0.076	0.184	1.180	1.674	2.340	0.372	0.228
0.358	0.249	0.255	0.273	0.231	0.069	0.141	0.402	0.303	0.372	1.133	0.851
0.390	0.235	0.253	0.291	0.231	0.053	-0.023	0.149	0.195	0.228	0.851	1.065

SmartPLS Report

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R Square Adjusted

f Square

Cronbach's Alpha

Average Variance Extracted (AVE)

Heterotrait-Monotrait Ratio (HTMT)

15. "SmartPLS 3." Boenningstedt: SmartPLS GmbH, <http://www.smartpls.com>.

